

Cluster Based Development of Indian Leather Industry: The Case Study of Kolkata

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Declaration

I declare that no outputs submitted for this degree have been submitted for a research degree of any other institution. I also confirm that this work fully acknowledges opinions, ideas and contributions from the work of others.

Any ethical clearance for the research presented in this commentary has been approved. Approval has been sought and granted by the Faculty Ethics Committee.

I declare that the Word Count of this DBA Thesis is approximately 57,809 words

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Abstract

The leather industry has played a crucial role in human civilizations, giving rise to clusters of specialized production across various regions. In India, the Kolkata leather cluster stands out as a significant contributor to the economy, producing a diverse range of leather goods. However, limited research has been conducted on the unit-level challenges and potential within this cluster. This thesis adopts a case study approach to explore the growth and development of different products and units within the Kolkata cluster, delving into the unique characteristics and factors that contribute to the growth and success of leather clusters in India. Through a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods, data was collected from surveys, interviews, and government reports. The study formulated three hypotheses to explore the cluster's impact on units of differing scales and products. Moreover, the derived seven factors including financial support, government policy, government programs, research and development, commercial and legal infrastructure, internal market openness, and physical infrastructure contribute significantly to the cluster's growth and development. Notably, commercial, and legal infrastructure emerged as the most influential factor, highlighting its crucial role in supporting the growth of leather units within the cluster. Moreover, the study unveiled distinct patterns in the growth of different leather products within the cluster. Footwear emerged as the most supported product category, followed closely by bags, indicating the cluster's potential to drive growth and innovation in specific segments. The results also indicated that medium-sized units with fixed investments ranging from 1.1 to 2.2 million INR experienced significantly higher average scores across factors, demonstrating their favourable position within the cluster. The qualitative analysis through interviews further reinforced the cluster's impact, with entrepreneurs highlighting the benefits of shared resources, collaboration, and access to skilled labour that the cluster offers. The findings also emphasized the need for continuous efforts to improve logistics solutions and create personalized products to enhance competitiveness in the highly fragmented footwear market. The research findings indicate that cluster development positively influences unit productivity and fosters innovation in leather products.

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List of Abbreviations

CAGR:	Compound annual growth rate
CLRI:	Central leather research institute.
CLC:	Calcutta leather complex.
FS:	Financial support.
GPS:	Government policy support
GP	Government programs.
R&D:	Research and development.
CLI:	Commercial and legal infrastructure.
IMO:	Internal market openness.
PI:	Physical infrastructure
DGCIS:	Directorate of commercial intelligence and statistics.
ILDLP:	The Indian leather development program me.
CETPs:	Common effluent treatment plants
IDLS	Integrated Development of leather sector
MLC:	Mega leather cluster.
MLFAC:	Mega leather footwear and accessories cluster.
SIDBI:	Small industrial development bank of India
CGTMSE:	The Credit guarantee fund trust for micro and small enterprises.

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Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Motivation

India's leather sector has long been a crucial part of the country's economy, with significant presence in states like Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Gujarat, West Bengal, Madhya Pradesh, and Karnataka. It specializes in producing a wide range of leather goods, from footwear and finished leather to wallets, garments, and travel accessories (CLE, 2022). Despite recent setbacks, the industry is making a comeback through innovative strategies and technologies. As India attracts more fashion companies and multinational players, the demand for high-quality leather products is expected to grow further (Nayeem, 2020). However, the sector faces challenges, including untrained employees, lack of organization, and a shortage of key resources like hides and skins, partly due to the declining cattle population driven by religious beliefs. Consequently, some leather industries are establishing operations in developing countries with abundant labor, favorable environmental norms, and better approaches to leather unit development (Expo, 2023). The Indian leather industry operates in clusters, with specific regions contributing specialized infrastructure, labor markets, and services, while facing common opportunities and threats. Major clusters are found in Kolkata, Chennai, Uttar Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, and Kanpur (Sharma and Varma, 2012 and (CLE, 2022)).

Mumbai, a major economic hub in India, lacks the historical association and specialized infrastructure for the leather industry compared to Kolkata. Meanwhile, Chennai, another significant leather cluster, faces water scarcity, impacting tanneries due to rapid urbanization, groundwater overexploitation, and deficient monsoon seasons (Bloomberg, 2021). To cope, tanneries in Chennai adopt water conservation measures and seek alternative sources. This highlights how regional factors, like water access, can influence the development and sustainability of leather clusters. On the other hand, Kolkata has a long-standing presence in the leather industry, with proximity to abundant raw materials and skilled artisans. The state of West Bengal, where Kolkata is located, offers high-quality hides and skins from a substantial cattle population. The city's strong domestic market,

thriving retail sector, and access to major ports make it convenient for exporting finished leather goods (Mishra and Pal, 2015). The government's support through financial incentives, infrastructure development, and specialized zones aids in attracting investment and fostering leather cluster growth. By integrating eco-friendly practices with government support, Kolkata's leather industry can address environmental concerns, reduce its ecological footprint, and meet the demands of environmentally conscious consumers, contributing to sustainable development (Chen *et al.*, 2022). The growth of leather clusters and the factors influencing their development play a crucial role in supporting diverse types of leather products and production units. While existing reports have focused on macro-level analysis of cluster growth, there is a significant gap in understanding the specific impact of various factors on regional leather clusters and the support they provide to units and products.

To address this gap, this research aims to examine into the importance of these factors in the growth and development of leather clusters and their diverse units and products. In particular, the focus will be on a case study of the Kolkata leather industry in India. By employing a comprehensive approach, the research will gather data from multiple sources, including insightful interviews with industry stakeholders, surveys of leather unit owners and workers, analysis of government policies, and a thorough examination of historical trends and economic indicators within the industry.

Through this in-depth investigation, the research intends to provide valuable insights into the dynamics of cluster-based development, shedding light on the specific factors that have contributed to the success and growth of the Kolkata leather cluster. The findings of this study will not only contribute to filling the research gap but also serve as a valuable reference for policymakers, industry leaders, and researchers seeking to enhance cluster development and support in the leather industry and other related sectors.

1.2 Research Background

1.2.1 History of Leather

Leather has had a worldwide appeal from time out of mind. Its history dates back to the days when humans hunted animals for food. They started using the hides of those animals for shelter and clothing so as to protect themselves against the climate. A hide is the skin of an animal that has been killed. Early humans handled hides using primitive techniques like sun-drying, salting, and smoking to preserve them and make them usable. The tanning of hides and skins to make leather is a centuries-old process (Roy, 2012) , and animal skins have been used for shelter, clothing, tools, and transportation since approximately 8,000 BC. Animal skins were preserved and treated in a variety of ways across the ancient world. In the fifth century BC, Aristotle wrote about the tanning process, and Pliny the Elder documented the use of bark and leaves from particular plants to preserve animal hides in the first century AD in Rome (Expo, 2023).

1.2.2 Usage of Leather

It is evident from Egyptian tombs dating back to almost 5000 BC that humans used the hides of animals for gloves, buckets, footwear, clothes, bottles, and shrouds for the burial of the dead, and military equipment. However, credit goes to the ancient Greeks for developing ways of tanning and preserving leather. They used certain tree barks within a process which yielded the first ever vegetable-tanned leather, which was one of Greece's most traded products around 500 BC. The utilization of vegetable-tanned leather remains prevalent even today, and it is among the most commonly used materials in tanneries. (Covington, 2009).

Throughout history, leather has been and still is used for seating in transportation and furniture due to its durability and luxury. These qualities also make it fit for footwear and sandals. During the Middle Ages it also became the perfect material for seating in restaurants, because it was easy to take care of, dust-free, and did not absorb the odour of the food.

With the arrival of industrialisation during the 18th and 19th centuries, new demand was created for leather. Then, with the growth of the automobile sector, the utilisation of leather for belting increased significantly. Also, the preference of consumers changed towards more light, fashionable, and comfortable footwear, thanks to a general rise in standards of living, and this created demand for soft, colourful, and versatile leather. Since vegetable-tanned leather was too rigid for these requirements, the utilization of chromium salt was introduced, thus making chrome-tanning the new norm in the leather industry (Covington, 2009).

Nowadays, with awareness of the extent of environmental degradation and the immense harm subsequently caused to wildlife, the utilisation of leather has been criticised in certain regions and as a result a replacement product called ‘faux leather’ has evolved which makes a superb substitute for leather (Sharma and Varma, 2012).

1.2.3 The Economies of Leather

The worldwide leather business is presently valued at US \$100 billion and is predicted to increase at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of over 6%, reaching \$130 billion by 2020. This rise might be attributed to an increased desire for luxury products, particularly in developing nations like China and India. Hides and skins, leather products, and leather garments are the three divisions that make up the current status of the business. The largest sector is hides and skins, which accounts for more than 60% of the overall market (Sharma and Varma, 2012) .

1.2.4 History of the Leather Industry in India

The oldest known reference to leather in India goes back to 3000 BC in the Rig Veda, with the usage of ‘Mashaks’ or leather bags. Leather was also used for sacks, handles, water bottles, and sails. In fact, one of Sage Agasthya’s proverbs mentions a ‘leather bottle,’ indicating that they had been used at that time. Leather has also been mentioned in different legal writings dating back to 2000 BC. The extensive usage of leather in sacred scriptures, as well as its close ties to religion, attest to its historical significance and inexhaustible novelty value for Indians (Damodaran and Mansingh, 2008) .

The next mention of leather occurs in the 1800s during the Industrial Revolution, when the curing of hides and production of leather were two of Gujrat's 42 industries. The 'Silk Route' was used to export the leather to numerous nations. Leather was used to produce the famed 'Jootis' in Uttar Pradesh, which were appealing to the Mughals and the aristocratic members of the Mughal court. In the South, where most leather manufacturing was in the hands of village low cast people, output was limited to meeting local demand. However, around 1880, exports to Roman and Greek countries began.

According to some studies, leather production in India may date back thousands of years, as evidenced by allusions to it in our ancient texts and Marco Polo's findings. Traditional leather-making operations were mostly carried out by village communities on a small enough scale to fulfil local requirements (Damodaran and Mansingh, 2008).

Research by economists conducted at the beginning of this millennium has demonstrated that leather is unusual in that it connects the poor country farmer to the world of fashion. The leather goods market has witnessed remarkable growth in recent years, with a global market size valued at USD 242.85 billion in 2022. The leather industry is projected to experience continued expansion, with an anticipated compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 6.6% from 2023 to 2030. These promising growth figures signify the increasing demand for leather products and reflect the industry's ability to adapt to changing consumer preferences and trends. As consumers seek high-quality and fashionable leather goods, businesses in this sector have an opportunity to capitalize on the market's potential and drive innovation and competitiveness in the coming years (Research, 2023). Leather manufacturing and commerce has created good economic prospects for many countries. India has a large supply of raw hides and skins, as well as trained labour and established knowledge (Chakraborty and Chakraborty, 2007). During recent decades, the country has achieved significant progress with export profits more than doubling, during which time the leather industry has been one of the top five foreign exchange earners (Sharma and Varma, 2012). Furthermore, Indian leather goods generate headlines in the fashion industry throughout the world, and Indian businesses are well-versed in global trends. They are able to build their brands in certain product categories because they have a strong awareness of

the global market, where Indian manufacturers offer superior value at lower pricing which helps them to compete in the global market (Saraswathi, 2001).

With the outbreak of World War 2, Indian leather experienced a surge in exports because of a surge in global leather consumption, despite the fact that most countries' leather supply was adversely affected. There were 114 production units in India in 1940, employing around 26,056 people, compared to 25 units in 1913-14 employing 2,753 workers (Mishra and Pal, 2015). With the passage of the Export Policy Resolution in 1970 and the execution of the Seetharamiah Committee's recommendations, the government set out to promote and grow export commerce after independence. This has resulted positively in the growth of the tanning industry (Mishra and Pal, 2015). Over the past two decades, India's leather products industry has risen to become one of the country's top five foreign exchange providers. It has experienced a dramatic transformation, emerging as one of the world's major leather manufacturers.

1.2.5 Manufacturing Centers for Leather in India

The Indian leather-based industry consists of approximately 42,000 Small-Scale Industries (SSI) units which account for 75 % of the total manufacturing capacity. The most important manufacturing centres for leather enterprises are located in the following regions: Tamil Nadu (Chennai, Ranipet, Ambur, Vaniyambadi, Dindigal, and Trichy); West Bengal (Kolkata); Uttar Pradesh (Kanpur, Agra, and Noida); Punjab (Jalandhar); Haryana (Ambala, Gurgaon, Panchkula, and Karnal); Delhi; Karnataka (Bangalore); Andhra Pradesh (Hyderabad); and Maharashtra (Mumbai) (Mishra and Pal, 2015). Below Table 1-1 gives a pictorial presentation of the important leather-based manufacturing centres in India.

Table 1- 1 State-wise Manufacturing Units (Source: CLRI – Central Leather Research Institute)

STATES	FOOTWEAR UNITS	LEATHER GOODS + GARMENTS UNITS	TOTAL
TAMIL NADU	160	598	758
WEST BENGAL	230	436	666
UTTAR PRADESH	268	22	290
HARYANA & PUNJAB	163	8	171
NEW DELHI	112	43	155
ANDHRA PRADESH	128	10	138
KARNATAKA	48	40	88
MAHARASHTRA	20	48	68

According to Gupta *et al.* (2018) studies, crucial leather-based manufacturing states are Uttar Pradesh (UP), Tamil Nadu (TN) and West Bengal (WB). An evaluation of total turnover (home plus exports) suggests that Uttar Pradesh has witnessed the highest CAGR (22.5%), West Bengal has the second fastest increase (CAGR of 12.8%) and Tamil Nadu (CAGR of 10.4%) has the slowest boom among the three. Figure 1-1 highlights details of the evaluation of the boom in leather in those three states.

Figure 1- 1 Comparison of growth in total turnover (Source: (Gupta et al., 2018))

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It is also observed that Uttar Pradesh showed the most stable growth during the period from 1998 to 2013, while Tamil Nadu's growth has been the most erratic among the three states studied. The stability in Uttar Pradesh's growth pattern can be attributed to the presence of large export players; a fact also attested to by the Largest Exporter Awards in one or more categories of leather products won by the key large players in Uttar Pradesh such as Mirza International, Super House, and Rahman. These firms have also been strongly positioning their brands (for example, Red Tape) in the domestic market (Gupta *et al.*, 2018).

An analysis of Indian livestock population data by the Government of India (2012) over a five-year period from 2007 to 2012 has revealed the competitive advantages of Uttar Pradesh over Tamil Nadu and West Bengal. Significant increases are evident in UP's share of the livestock population across all categories: cattle (8%), buffalo (24.6%), sheep (25.3%) and goat (9.5%), whereas declines have been recorded in Tamil Nadu (cattle, -17.8%; buffalo, -62.4%; sheep, -34.1%; goat, -8.6%) and West Bengal (cattle, -10.3%; buffalo, -16.67%; sheep, -25.0%; goat, -20.6%) (CLRI, 2022). Table 1-2 presents data on the livestock population.

Table 1- 2 State-wise livestock population data (Source: CLRI – Central Leather Research Institute)

	UP			TN			WB		
	2007	2012	%Change	2007	2012	%Change	2007	2012	%Change
Cattle	18.88	19.55	3.57	11.2	8.82	-21.2	19.18	16.51	-13.94
% Share	9.48	10.24	8.02	5.62	4.62	-17.80	9.64	8.65	-10.3
Buffalo	23.81	30.62	28.6	13.99	5.43	-61.12	0.7	0.6	-14.29
% Share	22.6	28.17	24.64	13.28	5	-62.40	0.66	0.55	-16.67
Sheep	1.19	1.35	13.45	8	4.79	-40.16	1.57	1.07	-31.77
% Share	1.66	2.08	25.3	11.17	7.36	-34.11	2.2	1.65	-25.00
Goat	14.79	15.59	5.36	9.27	8.14	-12.20	15.07	11.5	-23.65
% Share	10.53	11.53	9.5	6.59	6.02	-8.65	10.72	8.51	-20.61
Total	58.66	67.11	14.39	42.45	27.18	-35.97	36.52	29.69	-18.72

All three states have displayed positive operating profitability during the years 1998-2012. Uttar Pradesh displays the highest profitability among the three states, posting a median operating profitability of 16.3%, with the second highest in West Bengal (14.9%) while Tamil Nadu had the lowest of the three (12.3%). The environmental compliance costs of the manufacturers in Tamil Nadu are higher due to requirements of higher export quality as well as regulatory pressures (Gupta *et al.*, 2018). Figure 1-2 gives a comparison of operating profitability for different leather clusters in Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal, and the estimated leather production capacity in India is summarised in Table 1-3.

Figure 1- 2 Comparison of operating profitability (Source:(Gupta et al., 2018))

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Table 1- 3 Product Capacity (Source: Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics (DGCI&S))

ITEMS	PRODUCTION CAPACITY
HIDES	65 million pieces
SKINS	170 million pieces
LEATHER FOOTWEAR	909 million pairs
LEATHER SHOE UPPERS	100 million pairs
NON-LEATHER FOOTWEAR	1056 million pairs
LEATHER GARMENTS	16 million pieces
LEATHER GOODS	63 million pieces
INDUSTRIAL GLOVES	52 million pairs
SADDLERY & HARNESS	12.50 million pieces

1.2.6 The Indian Leather Industry: Major Hubs and Clusters

The leather industry in India is dominated by tiny manufacturing operations which are mostly located in rural areas in groupings throughout various parts of the nation. The industry employs a large number of people and provides the country with vital foreign exchange. The leather industry connects India's rural areas with visitors from other parts of the world, yet an Indian peasant may be unaware of the horizontal in addition to vertical distance that his animal skins cover in being converted into stylish articles.

Consumer goods have the potential to travel. The industry has a lot of supply-side as well as demand-side advantages. Demand-side benefits include a plentiful supply of raw materials and the availability of low-cost skilled labour. To assure the delivery of high-quality products at a reasonable price, factors such as labour and the availability of supporting institutions should be taken into consideration. Key variables include cheap prices a sizeable and expanding domestic market as well as regulatory assistance, which all affect the growth in demand.

The Indian leather industry is divided into clusters. Every cluster has a diverse range of business models. Traditional artists contribute to some clusters, while substantial production and processing facilities contribute to others (Das, 2017). The following are India's biggest leather-producing and processing clusters:

1.2.6.1 Chennai Leather Cluster

Chennai alone accounts for 25% of Tamil Nadu's manufacturing units and is responsible for 15% of India's total production. The cluster has many units in the micro category. Chennai has a crucial place in the global value chain due to its access to unprocessed materials and port facilities (Damodaran and Mansingh, 2008).

1.2.6.2 Kanpur Leather Cluster

The Kanpur leather-based cluster emerged during the time of British rule in India because of the demands of the navy located there. After the East India Company took over, the leather-based industry became more organized, and Kanpur ultimately emerged as the

largest manufacturer of shoes during World War 2. Even today, the city produces massive numbers of leather slippers. Leather enterprises in Kanpur thrive because of the infrastructural connectivity furnished by the River Ganges (Sharma and Varma, 2012).

1.2.6.3 West Bengal Leather Industry

West Bengal, with two large manufacturing clusters in Kolkata and Shantiniketan, is one of the states that has long been connected with the leather industry. The Kolkata leather cluster contains 4000 firms (both organised and unstructured) and employs over 62,000 people directly (Sharma and Varma, 2012).

Shantiniketan's creative legacy in leather crafts evolved during the time of Shri Rabindranath Tagore, a Nobel Laureate poet, writer, prominent philosopher, humanist, and social reformer. He established the Visva-Bharati University, and his son Rathindranath Tagore and daughter-in-law Protima Devi devoted their time to rural development activities as a result of his influence and started a craft wing at the university with Andrew Karpele. Visva-Bharati University's Pally Sangathan Vibhag was instrumental in the establishment of leather hicraft units in this city, well-known artist Shri Nandalal Bose was also instrumental in the development of leather crafts there. Meanwhile a local organisation, ShilpaSadhana, contributed to the growth of the local economy by promoting the unique handicrafts created by local artisans (Pal, 2013; Swadesi, 2021).

Manufacturing facilities for leather products are the key players in Santiniketan's leather cluster. It's 'Shanti leather items' are products with exquisitely coloured graphic patterns, with embossing and batik prints. The batik prints have distinct aesthetic value and display considerable artistic flair in a blend of folk art and tradition. Traditional portrayals of 'Shakuntala' frequently include deer, while the folk dimension includes the 'Shanthal' custom. The goods are manufactured with E.I tanned⁹ leather, which is a vegetable-tanned type. The patterns on the surface of the leather items are accomplished by hand, and the dexterity of talent involved can be seen in the shapes of the fascinating designs (Pal, 2013). The leather goods cluster in Shantiniketan is made up of micro and domestic units, and the items created here are largely marketed within India. A few goods also find their way to international markets. Apart from few, the cluster is dominated by artisan-based businesses

that operate with little infrastructure and resources. They are not typically involved in direct exporting due to their lack of understanding of what this involves, and a few merchant exporters based in Kolkata and Sodhpur bridge the gap between this cluster the international market (Pal, 2013).

1.2.6.3.1 Kolkata Leather Cluster Profile (SIDBI, 2014)

The Kolkata Leather Cluster, also known as the Calcutta Leather Complex (CLC), is an organized concentration of leather industry-related businesses and institutions in the city of Kolkata, India. Kolkata, the capital of West Bengal, is India's major leather-producing city. Kolkata has facilities for all of the steps of manufacturing leather, but it is by some distance the principal tanning centre in India, and 22-25% of the nation's tanning is accomplished in Kolkata. The Kolkata leather cluster continues to hold a 60% share of India's leather export market. The domestic economy is divided into sub-sectors that operate at various levels of the value chain, with the most important sub-sectors being dyeing, leather items, industrial products, and footwear. The Calcutta Leather Complex was established on the eastern outskirts of Kolkata in Bantala due to the significance of the leather industry to West Bengal. All operations relating to the leather industry are expected to be housed there. With a daily tanning capacity of about 1,000 tonnes of raw hides, it is expected that, when fully operational, this complex would generate approximately 5,000 crore in exports and employ nearly 10,000 people (Gupta, Gupta and Dhamija, 2019). This cluster manufactures a wide range of commodities, including finished leather, leather goods such as purses, wallets and other accessories, footwear, and industrial gloves. The leather used here is of high quality, and value is added via design, finishing, and professional operations. The addition of value ranges from Rs. 272 for the cost of hides to Rs. 1200 for the export of a standard women's bag using 8 sq ft of leather. The leather used in industrial gloves is of less superior quality. The cost of labour is mostly used to increase value. The leather used in the footwear industry is of great value, and the added value is determined according to the quality, design, and style of the shoes. The price of finished leather varies from Rs. 50 to Rs. 80 per sq. ft., depending on the quality and value added throughout the manufacturing process. Although the leather complex was inaugurated with much fanfare,

it has recently been beset by infrastructural challenges, leading to the relocation of several of the tanneries.

Note: Although the report of SIDBI (2014) published in 2014 and the data is not recent, the profiling of the cluster and evolution details are useful. The researcher expresses the gratitude towards SIDBI and EDII for their information and analysis.

Figure 1-3 depicts a map of the Kolkata Leather Cluster. The thickness of the lines is an indicator of strength of the network.

Figure 1- 3 Cluster Map of Kolkata Leather Cluster (Source: Diagnostic Study Report of Kolkata Leather Cluster. (2014))

1.2.6.3.2 Geography of the Kolkata Leather Cluster

The Calcutta Leather Complex project was planned by the West Bengal government in the early 1990s. It was designed as an integrated structure that would house all leather-related operations in a contemporary and environmentally sustainable manner. When the Supreme Court of India ordered that Kolkata's tanneries be relocated outside of the city boundaries to avoid pollution in residential areas, the Leather Complex was born. The West Bengal government concluded pre-construction agreements and infrastructure development between 1995 and 1997.

The tannery units are centred at the Kolkata Leather Complex. Following the Supreme Court's decision, tanneries that had previously operated in locales such as Tangra and Topsia in Kolkata relocated to the Kolkata Leather Complex. Topsia, Janbazar, and Rajabazar are home to the majority of leather footwear manufacturing facilities, while leather products and glove manufacturing facilities are sited in Kosba. The Tangra region is home to a large number of Chinese manufacturers and Tangra and Topsia both have leather glove manufacturing facilities. On Bentinck Street, there are a plethora of dwellings that double as retail establishments for footwear, most of which are owned by Chinese people. Micro household level footwear manufacturing units may also be found in Janbazaar and Rajabazar. A huge number of experts known as 'fabricators¹⁰' may be found in various regions of the city (Sharma and Varma, 2012).

Both organised and unorganised operations are accommodated in the Kolkata Leather Complex. Loosely organized units have been characterised as those that do not have formal government registration. Unorganized units include 'fabricators' that perform jobbing labour and micro units that make leather items in their backyards. The District Industries Centre (DIC) has formalised the registration of organised units, and around 50,000 people are employed in the cluster.

1.2.6.3.3 Advantages of Leather Cluster in Kolkata

The leather cluster in Kolkata offers numerous benefits that contribute to increased productivity, innovation, and competitiveness within the industry (Mishra and Pal, 2015). One key advantage is the realization of economies of scale, as a concentrated presence of leather businesses in one location allows companies to benefit from shared infrastructure,

specialized suppliers, and services, leading to lower production costs and enhanced competitiveness. One of its core strengths lies in the age-old practice of tanning, combined with the modern infrastructure and ample water supply provided by the recently established Calcutta Leather Complex (EEAS, 2020). Additionally, Kolkata is a powerhouse in the export market for leather goods and gloves, accounting for a significant portion of India's total exports in these categories. Access to a skilled labor force further strengthens the cluster's success, as the leather sector in Kolkata draws professionals from across the region, facilitating the recruitment of talented workers and fostering niche expertise within the cluster (Mishra and Pal, 2015). Moreover, the cluster encourages knowledge sharing and innovation by fostering connections between firms, academic institutions, and other key players in the leather industry. Through this exchange of knowledge, businesses within the cluster can boost their competitiveness by driving innovation, creating new technologies, and refining manufacturing methods. Additionally, the close proximity of businesses within the cluster facilitates networking and collaboration, enabling firms to form joint ventures, partnerships, and other cooperative arrangements that facilitate growth, market expansion, and access to valuable resources. The cluster's uninterrupted supply of raw materials, driven by India's substantial cattle population, ensures a steady stream of high-quality hides and skins (IBEF, 2023). The abundance of water in the region, sourced from the Sunderbans delta, further enhances the tanning process (De, 2021). Kolkata-made leather products are known for their exceptional quality, adhering to international standards, which has contributed to the development of a trusted brand in the global market. The strong network of households involved as fabricators and laborers for exporters or major corporations ensures a consistent supply of high-quality goods (CLE, 2022). This, coupled with the economy of operations, enabled by the availability of raw materials and cost-effective skilled labor, has further reduced production costs, enhancing the cluster's competitiveness. With its vast potential for future expansion, supported by infrastructure, technology, and quality business development services, the Kolkata leather cluster is poised for further growth in both domestic consumption and international trade (Mishra and Pal, 2015).

Furthermore, the Kolkata Leather Cluster benefits from substantial support from both the government and various institutions, including investments in infrastructure, the establishment of research and training centers, and the implementation of policies and programs aimed at promoting the cluster's growth and development. Such comprehensive support has played a vital role in ensuring the cluster's success and continued advancement in the highly competitive leather industry.

1.2.7 Comparison of Dhaka Cluster and Kolkata Leather Cluster in India

While the apparel and garment export clusters in Dhaka and the leather industry cluster in Kolkata are in different sectors, there are still some valuable lessons that can be drawn from a comparison of the two clusters.

1.2.7.1 Role of government support and policies

Government support and policies are vital in determining how the clusters expand and develop in both the leather and garment industries of Kolkata and Dhaka. The lessons learned from Dhaka's experience demonstrate that a proactive government may promote international trade links while offering regulatory incentives, infrastructure support, and other measures to help the industry develop (Giest, 2021) and (Policy, 2019). A similar strategy in Kolkata might help the development of the leather industry.

1.2.7.2 Compliance with labor and environmental regulations

Dhaka's garment industry has come under international spotlight for terrible labour conditions and environmental problems. This experience emphasises the need of ensuring labour and environmental compliance within industry clusters (Policy, 2019). To achieve sustainable growth and a positive worldwide reputation, the Kolkata leather industry should learn from this and prioritise the execution of strict labour and environmental regulations.

1.2.7.3 Skill development and training

The Dhaka apparel industry has invested in skill development and training programs to improve the quality of its workforce, contributing to its competitiveness in the global market (Saxena, 2019) and (Haque and Bari, 2021). The Kolkata leather industry could

benefit from a similar focus on human capital development, which would enhance the skills and expertise of workers, thereby increasing productivity and competitiveness.

1.2.7.4 Collaboration and knowledge sharing

In Dhaka's apparel industry, firms within the cluster collaborate and share knowledge to gain a competitive advantage. This collective learning helps the industry to innovate and adapt to changing market conditions (Saxena, 2019). The Kolkata leather industry could also benefit from increased collaboration among firms within the cluster, fostering innovation and adaptation to the ever-evolving global market demands.

1.2.7.5 Diversification and value addition

Dhaka's apparel industry has focused on diversifying its product offerings and adding value to its products to remain competitive in the global market (Sanad, 2023). The Kolkata leather industry could adopt a similar strategy, focusing on producing a wide range of high-quality leather products, investing in design and innovation, and targeting niche markets to remain competitive and increase the overall value of exports.

By learning from these lessons, the Kolkata leather industry can focus on government support, compliance with labor and environmental regulations, skill development, collaboration, and diversification to enhance its growth and competitiveness in the global market.

1.2.8 Justification for the choice of the company used for the case study

The selection of the Kolkata leather industry as the case study is well-justified due to its unique combination of factors that have contributed to the development of the leather cluster. The availability of water resources from the Hooghly River has been advantageous for leather tanning, while Kanpur benefits from proximity to the Ganges River. Chennai, although facing water scarcity, has managed to sustain its leather cluster through innovative water conservation measures (Bloomberg, 2021). Additionally, Kolkata's historical connection to the leather industry and its well-established market for leather products make it an ideal candidate for examination. The city's strategic location with access to the Haldia port for export further enhances its appeal as a case study. In the Kolkata leather cluster,

there is a strong interconnection between the various leather products and production units. The specialization of units in specific products, such as footwear, bags, or accessories, has led to a cohesive network of complementary units (Nayeem, 2020; Zaidi, 2020-2023). This specialization fosters a spirit of collaboration, promoting the sharing of knowledge, best practices, and resources among the units, which in turn drives innovation and heightens competitiveness. Furthermore, the choice of Kolkata considers the regulatory environment, which has seen an increasing focus on environmental regulations and sustainable practices in the leather industry (Zaidi, 2020-2023). Altogether, the combination of water availability, market access, historical significance, and evolving regulations in Kolkata makes it a compelling and relevant subject for exploring the development of leather clusters in India. As a result, studying the interplay between products and units in the Kolkata leather cluster offers valuable insights into how collaborative networks can boost productivity, innovation, and overall competitiveness in the Indian leather industry.

1.3 Problem Statement

In India, the leather industry is a thriving business with enormous development potential. The country boasts the second-largest cow population in the world and is a significant hide and skin producer. With more than 200 tanneries scattered across Gujarat, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, West Bengal and Tamil Nadu, India has a robust tanning finishing infrastructure. Despite its promise, the Indian leather sector is beset by a slew of issues that have hampered its expansion. The absence of proper infrastructure is one of these. Although the leather industry in India is one of the country's oldest and most traditional industries, it has, nevertheless, encountered several obstacles in recent years, including high manufacturing costs, a lack of infrastructure, and environmental concerns. Furthermore, the sector is beset by high taxes and customs expenses, making it impossible to compete with other nations. The government has acknowledged these issues and taken measures to solve them, but there is still much more to be done. The completed leather sector is similarly seasonal, with demand almost non-existent during the monsoon season. The bulk of makers of leather products and industrial gloves export their commodities in terms of forward linkages, while some of the companies have long-lasting contacts with

overseas customers and communicate with them directly whereas the remainder rely on buyer-seller meetings to market their goods.

The rapid development of the COVID-19 epidemic has been dubbed the 'Black Swan of 2020', representing a catastrophe on a scale that was never anticipated but with consequences far greater than would ordinarily be expected. Many nations around the world have been forced to impose lockdowns as a result of increased domestic and international terrorism. These lockdowns, which have effectively halted the flow of people and goods across national borders, are believed to be caused by border security measures that were originally put into place following the September 11th terrorist attacks on the USA World Trade Centre in 2001. The COVID-19 epidemic has wreaked havoc on the global economy and trade, since output and consumption have been curtailed across the world. To combat the slump and give temporary income assistance to firms and individuals, governments have engaged through monetary and fiscal policy. However, limits on movement and social isolation to prevent the spread of the disease have a direct impact on the labour supply, transportation, and travel, which in turn has an impact on commerce. Hotels, restaurants, non-essential retail commerce, tourism, and large portions of manufacturing have all been shut down.

The leather and footwear sectors were negatively impacted by COVID-19's market downturn in 2020-21. The sector lost around Rs.7000 crores in overseas orders. As a result of COVID's negative impact on Europe and the United States, exports from India's leather footwear sector fell by 27.72%, from USD 5093.09 million in 2019-20 to USD 3681.53 million in 2020-21 (DGCI&S). However, the export order situation has begun to stabilise, and the industry is presently receiving orders from Europe and the United States, which are the primary markets. Furthermore, salesperson samples for the Spring/Summer 2022 season are being delivered to international conferences and meetings in the United States and Europe where meetings have already been organised. When compared to 2020-21, the sector anticipates increased exports in 2021-22 (Leather News India | Council For Leather Exports, 2015).

There are only few numbers of studies focused on the leather clusters in different regions of India. For instance, Sharma and Varma (2012) study focused on the improvement of export competitiveness of Kanpur leather cluster. Also, this study examined number of factors that contribute to the leather cluster's low export performance in Kanpur region of India. The Indian leather industry plays a crucial role in the country's economy, employing millions of people and being an important contributor to export earnings. The leather cluster in India is a crucial component of this industry, with a concentration of interconnected companies, suppliers, and institutions involved in various stages of leather production, including tanning, processing, and manufacturing (CLE, 2022). The Sharma and Varma (2012) study aimed to better understand the dynamics of the leather cluster, specifically focusing on the Kanpur Leather Cluster in Uttar Pradesh, one of the largest leather production centers in India. The research objectives of Sharma and Varma (2012) were analyzing how the cluster encourages growth and competitiveness in the leather sector through the dissemination of information and the development of new technologies, recognizing environmental pollution, waste management, access to skilled labor, and infrastructure as only some of the issues and limits facing Kanpur's leather industry cluster. Also, the objectives were to studying how the government's policies and supporting institutions have influenced the expansion and longevity of the Kanpur Leather Cluster, impact analysis of the Kanpur Leather Cluster on regional growth, job creation, and income distribution and educating policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers on how to improve the leather cluster's performance in light of shifting global markets and consumer preferences. In addition, Sharma and Varma's (2012) study of the leather cluster aimed to shed light on the factors that affect the leather industry's growth and performance and provide useful recommendations for fostering long-term prosperity in the leather business.

However, Mishra and Pal (2015) study was based on the internationalisation of the Kolkata Leather Cluster to grow market share and expand their development opportunities to meet the needs of international markets. The study's key goal was to help the Kolkata Leather Cluster become more competitive and sustainable by illuminating the opportunities and threats it faces in the context of global markets. Another study such as Gupta *et al.* (2018) examine the sustainability strategies of three major Indian leather-producing cluster in

states such as: Tamil Nadu (TN), West Bengal (WB), and Uttar Pradesh (UP), to gain insight in generating economic, social, and environmental values. Moreover, Gupta, Gupta and Dhamija (2019) research explored that how far the Indian leather industry has progressed in terms of individual and total factor productivity. They also evaluated and analysed the performance of the Indian leather sector in Tamil Nadu (TN), West Bengal (WB), and Uttar Pradesh (UP) using productivity analysis, geographical variations determinants in productivity, and the technology closeness ratio. According to the results of the productivity research, WB leather clusters outperformed TN and UP leather clusters in terms of partial factor productivity and technical efficiency (TE). This is due to the transformation of WB's leather cluster into a state-of-the-art leather complex with several opportunities for resource conservation. The purpose of the research conducted by Gupta, Gupta, and Dharmija et al. (2018 & 2019) was to better understand the structure and dynamics of the leather cluster, as well as the interplay between its many constituents (including suppliers, manufacturers, and governmental agencies). Therefore, it is necessary to analyse the role of government policies and institutions in the formation and evolution of the leather cluster by identifying the elements that contribute to the success or failure of the leather cluster, such as access to raw materials, skilled labor, technology, and markets. Their studies objectives were to assess the leather cluster's contribution to regional growth, employment, and tax revenue, examining the leather cluster's impact on the environment and its ability to remain competitive by analysing factors including resource use, pollution, and waste management, and then recommending improvements.

However, it is observed that there are some macro studies and statistics are available, but only a few of them address the problems of prospects for regional clusters, and the Kolkata cluster is still unexplored in terms of the problems faced by production units and stakeholders in the development of different leather products. The Kolkata leather cluster plays a pivotal role in the growth and development of different leather products and production units, making it essential to address the environmental challenges it faces. The tanning process alone generates significant solid waste, wastewater, and air emissions, posing a threat to the local ecosystem and nearby communities. Ensuring effective waste management and pollution control measures are in place is crucial to preserve the ecological

balance and protect the environment. Moreover, the extensive water consumption during leather processing can strain water resources in areas where water is scarce, necessitating the adoption of water-saving technologies. Additionally, the leather industry's heavy energy use contributes to greenhouse gas emissions, emphasizing the need for energy-efficient technologies to reduce its environmental impact. Addressing these challenges requires adopting cleaner production methods, using less hazardous chemicals, and supporting reforestation efforts to mitigate deforestation and land use issues associated with raw material sourcing. To achieve this, government support, research and development initiatives, internal market openness, commercial legal services, and funding are vital in driving the adoption of sustainable practices and technologies within the Kolkata leather cluster. Research into the cluster's environmental elements and addressing unique problems through rigorous study are crucial for its continued viability and contribution to the leather industry in India. By implementing sustainable practices and cleaner technologies, the cluster can not only enhance its productivity, competitiveness, and sustainability but also demonstrate a commitment to environmental stewardship and safeguarding the well-being of local communities and ecosystems. The growth and development of units and products within the Kolkata leather cluster are integral to its overall success (EEAS, 2020). Collaboration and specialization among units enhance innovation and competitiveness, while government support and funding are vital in mitigating environmental pollution and promoting sustainable practices. Research and market openness drive continuous improvement and adaptation, and legal services protect and foster an environment of innovation. By harnessing these elements, the Kolkata leather cluster can thrive and continue to be a significant contributor to India's leather industry.

1.4 Research Aim

The main aim of this thesis is to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the leather clusters in India, with a specific focus on the Kolkata leather cluster. The research seeks to examine and understand the impact of the support provided to these clusters on the development of various leather products and production units within them. To achieve this aim, the study will delve into the unique characteristics and factors that contribute to the growth and

success of leather clusters in India. It will explore the specific types of support and resources that are being allocated to the Kolkata leather cluster and how these initiatives have influenced the development of different leather products and units.

The research will also investigate the interconnection between various leather product manufacturers and production units within the cluster. By understanding the dynamics of collaboration and specialization, the study aims to unravel how units mutually benefit from shared knowledge, best practices, and resources, leading to increased innovation and competitiveness.

1.5 Research Objectives

- To study the evolution and emergence of the Kolkata leather cluster.
- To study the effect of the cluster on the growth of units in all respects.
- To determine if the cluster helps equally in the development of all products.
- To study if the cluster helps in the development of units of different sizes.
- To investigate the interplay of relevant indicators and firmographics.

1.6 Contribution of the Thesis

The following contributions of thesis are described as follows:

This thesis has made a significant contribution to the understanding of the crucial factors that foster the growth of the leather cluster in Kolkata. The factors, such as financial support, government policies, government programs and support, research and development, commercial and legal infrastructure, internal market openness, and physical infrastructure, have been developed and showed the potential to significantly contribute to the overall growth and development of the leather clusters in Kolkata. These factors play a vital role in encouraging investments, driving innovation, providing resources, facilitating market access, sharing knowledge and ensuring long-term sustainability within the leather cluster.

By analyzing the impact of various factors on units, the study highlights the role of commercial and legal infrastructure as a key driver of cluster benefits. This emphasizes the importance of effective commercialization and protection of intellectual property rights in

fostering innovation and investment within the cluster. By commercializing products effectively, units can access larger markets and attract more customers, ultimately contributing to the cluster's growth. Legal services help protect intellectual property rights, ensuring that innovations and unique designs are safeguarded from unauthorized use, which fosters an environment of innovation and encourages investment in product development. Another most important aspect is financial support, followed by government policy support. Government support and funding are instrumental in addressing environmental pollution and water waste management within the Kolkata leather cluster. By providing financial incentives and investing in infrastructure for effluent treatment plants, solid waste disposal facilities, and air pollution control equipment, the government can help mitigate the cluster's environmental impact. Supportive policies and regulations can drive the adoption of cleaner production technologies, promoting energy efficiency and reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

This thesis also shows that various factors affecting the leather cluster development are impacted differently, which means that certain elements have a more significant influence on the cluster's growth compared to others. This research contribution helps to provide valuable guidance for policymakers and industry stakeholders to prioritize their efforts and resources, focusing on areas that contribute the most to the cluster's growth. Additionally, understanding the varying impacts can create a competitive advantage for the leather cluster, attracting more businesses and investments.

The research provides valuable insights into the diverse performance levels of the various products within the leather cluster. By identifying these significant differences, the study empowers industry stakeholders to make informed decisions and tailor strategies that are specific to each product category. This knowledge is instrumental in allocating resources effectively and fostering a more targeted approach towards enhancing the growth and competitiveness of individual products within the leather industry. Their success can attract more investors, businesses, and entrepreneurs to join the cluster, leading to further expansion and increased competitiveness in the market. In addition, the thesis shows that footwear, being a prominent segment within the leather industry, receives the highest level of support from the cluster, followed closely by bags. The prominence of these segments

can attract government support and investment in initiatives targeted at enhancing their growth potential.

Furthermore, the research delves into the effect of cluster support on units of different scales, revealing the strong performance of medium-sized units with specific levels of fixed investment. Furthermore, it highlights the importance of encouraging medium-scale units, as they demonstrate a promising potential for further expansion and success within the supportive cluster environment. To address the imbalance of units with different scale, it provides valuable guidance for the cluster management and policymakers to design strategies that cater to the specific needs and challenges of units of different scales. Providing targeted assistance to smaller units, such as financial incentives, skill development programs, and easier access to shared facilities, can help level the playing field and ensure equitable support for all units within the Kolkata leather cluster.

The inclusion of sentiment and word cloud analyses adds depth to the knowledge, capturing the perspectives and sentiments of respondents. This approach offers a nuanced understanding of the perceptions and attitudes of stakeholders within the leather cluster, further enriching the research's insights.

This thesis also has made a significant contribution to qualitative interview analysis by employing rigorous coding techniques and category development. Through the process of analyzing the interview data, the researcher identified key themes and patterns that emerged from the responses of the participants. By systematically coding the data and developing categories based on recurring themes, this thesis provides valuable insights into the perspectives and experiences of the participants regarding the leather industry cluster in Kolkata. By carefully interpreting the interview data, the thesis identifies the importance of various elements, such as financial support, government policies, and market openness, in contributing to the growth of the leather cluster. Moreover, the qualitative analysis helped shed light on the challenges faced by the industry and the opportunities that could be leveraged to further enhance cluster development.

Moreover, the thesis sheds light on the importance of environmental considerations within the leather industry, highlighting the need for sustainable practices and government support

in addressing environmental challenges. This aspect contributes to the broader discourse on responsible and sustainable development in industrial clusters.

1.7 Thesis Outline

The structure of thesis is outlined below.

Chapter two presents a literature review which covers the history and evolution of leather and leather products. This chapter also provides an overview of the theory of clusters in different cities in India. Moreover, this chapter explores the evolution and emergence of the Kolkata leather cluster. Chapter three then explains the research methodology, tools and techniques used to identify the impact of the development of the Kolkata cluster on the different manufacturing units for all products. Chapter four of this thesis presents the results and analysis based on the data collected. Chapter five discusses the findings, conclusion and recommendations of the study.

Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1 Evolution of the Use of Leather in Human History

Leather has a long and illustrious history in human history. Leather items from some of the oldest human civilizations have been discovered by archaeologists. Leather has been utilised for a number of reasons throughout history, ranging from clothing and shelter to furnishings and toolmaking. The leather business has witnessed a metamorphosis in recent years, with shifting customer needs and new technical advances influencing its progress. This section looks at the leather industry's history from its humble origins to the present day.

Leather is a strong and flexible material made by tanning rawhide and skin from animals, most often cattle hide. It may be made in a variety of ways, including wet blue, chrome-free, vegetable-tanned, and other tanning processes. Different finishes may be used to produce a variety of textures and looks. Leather has been utilised for a number of purposes for thousands of years, including garments, shoes, furniture, and automotive upholstery.

Leather is a one-of-a-kind material the features of which cannot be easily or fully replicated in other materials. Leather is made from animal hide or skin that has been chemically treated and processed to yield into a stable and finished process called tanning. Tanning is a process that is reliant on the suppliers of skins and hides as well as being crucial for manufacturers of leather goods. Leather, unlike raw hides and skins, is resistant to degradation over a short period of time, especially when moist. Leather is tanned to provide certain qualities for specific applications. The goals of tanning are to make hides and skins resistant to decomposition and bacterial decay, to improve physical properties like tensile strength, flexibility, abrasion resistance, and water permeability, and to impart chemical properties such as non-solubility in water at relatively high temperatures. Leather also has significant aesthetic aspects due to the appealing look of its grain (Covington, 2009).

Over time, leather has progressed from being a necessity to a luxury item. Increased demand for leather and leather items indicates that this industry has a lot of room for expansion. The leather industry's global commercial value increased to \$116.5 billion in 2006 from

just \$4 billion in 1971. During the late 1970s and early 1980s, rising labour costs and environmental concerns in industrialised nations led to the closure of several manufacturing plants. This aided the development of the leather industry in emerging nations such as Indonesia, Thailand, India, and China, among others (SIDBI, 2014).

Leather manufacturing is a traditional craft that is intertwined with the fabric of our land. Kingdoms have come and gone, battles have been waged, and our wonderful country of India has earned freedom, and the leather industry along with the history of leather production has survived it all. India aspires to carry on the tradition of the first leather objects manufactured in our lands about five thousand years ago, transmitting the passion and workmanship that has been passed down through generations for many more years to come.

Leather is a versatile material that has been used for many different purposes over the years. It is strong, durable, and long lasting, making it the perfect choice for a variety of products. Leather has been used to make clothes, shoes, furniture, and many other items. It is also popular for use in cars and motorcycles. There are many different types of leather, and each has its own unique characteristics.

Leather is a natural product that has been used to make clothing and other items for centuries. Although it used to be commonplace to use animal skins, nowadays there are many different types of leather made from different animal or plant materials. Leather is strong and durable, and can be dyed in any colour. It is also comfortable to wear, and it lasts a long time.

2.2 Evolution of the Leather Industry in India

The Indian leather industry dates back to the 12th century, when artisans created footwear, bags, and other accessories out of cowhide. However, the business began to take off in the 1970s as a consequence of government initiatives that encouraged exports and eased import prohibitions. Since then, the sector has developed dramatically, with 2016 sales exceeding \$17.5 billion. Over four million people are employed in the sector, which represents a significant contribution to India's economy (Roy, 2012).

The leather industry in India is one of the country's oldest industries. The business has a long and illustrious history. It has had a significant impact not just on our country's economic progress, but also on our society's overall social and cultural fabric. The tanning and processing of leather is one of the most polluting industrial operations, resulting in significant volumes of hazardous waste. This is an unintended consequence of a sector that employs millions of people and contributes considerably to India's gross domestic product.

In India, three billion square feet of leather are produced each year. Because of its enormous potential for expansion and job creation, the leather industry is a key component of the Indian economy and contributes significantly to the country's exports as one of the country's top ten foreign exchange earners. The meat business generates leather as a by-product, and sheep, goats, and cattle raised for the production of meat, dairy products, and wool are the principal source of raw materials for the leather industry. India is home to 11% of the world's sheep and goats and 21% of its buffalo and cattle (Roy, 2012; Sharma and Varma, 2012; Roy, 2013) .

The Indian leather industry is valued at \$17.85 billion (with exports worth \$5.85 billion and domestic consumption \$12 billion) (Muthusamy and Ganesh). Footwear exports, including leather, non-leather, and footwear components, account for 50.3% of total exports. The Indian leather industry employs around 4.42 million individuals, the majority of whom are from economically disadvantaged backgrounds. The leather sector employs a substantial number of women, accounting for 30% of total employment. India is the world's second-largest manufacturer of both footwear and leather garments, the fourth-largest exporter of leather goods, and the third-largest exporter of saddlery and harness products (Nayeem, 2020; IBEF, 2023). The Indian leather industry is now placing a greater focus on planned expansion through the optimal usage of raw material in order to maximise profits, notably through exports. The domestic market for fashion accessories is expected to grow twofold by 2020 to \$18 billion, while exports are forecast to reach \$9 billion by 2020 (Gupta *et al.*, 2018).

2.3 The Value Chain in the Indian Leather Industry

Due to environmental concerns and steep rises in labour costs within developed nations in the late 1970s and through the 1980s, the leather industry in the majority of developed countries is decreased. This increased the potential for leather production nations like India and other developing economies to achieve higher positioning in the worldwide alternate leather goods. Presently, footwear production has declined in the USA, and a significant proportion of the shoes required in most EU countries (except Italy and Spain) is imported. A similar state of affairs exists for other leather-based products such as garments, gloves and purses.

India is the world’s greatest producer of live animals. The leather industry in India is supported by a plentiful supply of cow and buffalo hides and goat and sheep skins, as shown in Figure 2-1.

Figure 2- 1 Flowchart of supply of animals hides and skins

India was primarily a raw material exporter in the 1960s. The government’s strategy since of restricting semi-finished product exports and encouraging export after value addition has tied the leather industry to the global value chain. This sector plays a significant part in the Indian economy, with exports of leather and leather goods totalling Rs. 14,900 crores and the employment of around 2.5 million people (Pal, 2013; Mishra and Pal, 2015).

International locations like Italy operate at the pinnacle of the leather with excessively priced exports and high unit-cost realisation. The advantages of countries such as Italy are

in the design and styling of vast products, and the ability to produce first-class leather out of distinctly poor unfinished leather. Italian leather production is orientated towards meeting foreign demand, whereas it's domestic requirements are met by means of less expensive leather imports from international locations like India and China.

However, an empirical study (Chakrabarti, 2009) has found that, even in the recent past, the methods used to gather hides and skins was not very advanced. According to a CLRI estimate from 1987, around 9 million hides and nearly as many skins were lost owing to non-recovery from carcasses in outlying settlements. Losses due to non-recovery are anticipated to have decreased dramatically in recent years, with hides and skins commanding a strong market. A network of butchers and animal breeders, small and large dealers and agents, and tanners is being formed. Small feeder towns and villages act as intermediaries for large dealers in bigger markets. These agents source hides and skins from butchers or their sub-agents in communities.

Villagers frequently take raw hides and skins to weekly marketplaces, when the agents of large dealers acquire them for major markets. Agents may also pay butchers in advance. Hides and skins typically take one to three weeks to reach a tannery from the moment they are removed from animals. Wet salting is the most commonly used method of preservation in India. The industry is a traditional one, with significant caste-based ties to the social structure. As a result, even today, a considerable percentage of industry operators among both entrepreneurs and employees originate from the traditional leather working classes (Oberai and Chadha, 2001).

2.4 Exports of Leather and Leather Products from India

Footwear is the major contributor to export volumes of leather and leather products, and accounted for 49.23% of all leather exports. Product mixes of exported footwear consist of those for men (55%), women (35%), and children (10%). However, 90% of the footwear manufactured in India is consumed domestically.

Leather products and accessories, including saddlery and harnesses, account for 23.79% of the market, while saddlery and harnesses account for roughly 2.7%. Annual production

totals include 63 million pieces of leather articles, 52 million pairs of industrial gloves, and 12.5 million pieces of harnesses and saddlery goods (Mishra and Pal, 2015).

Finished leather contributes 15.2% to the total exports of leather and leather products, while leather garments represent 9.04%. Table 2-1 and Table 2-2 highlight the export data of different products by value as well as volume.

Table 2- 1 Product-wise Export Segmentation – By Value (Mn USD) (Source: Directorate of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics (DGCI&S))

PRODUCTS	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18
FINISHED LEATHER	1046.45	886.39	874.23
LEATHER FOOTWEAR	2147.98	2128.87	2193.61
FOOTWEAR COMPONENTS	284.34	298.69	335.24
LEATHER GARMENTS	553.11	535.66	518.96
LEATHER GOODS	1370.04	1316.63	1365.33
SADDLERY AND HARNESS	146.38	142.35	155.88
NON-LEATHER FOOTWEAR	306.74	338.21	296.68
TOTAL	5855.04	5646.8	5739.93

Table 2- 2 Product-wise Export Segmentation – (Units) (Source: Council for Leather Exports)

PRODUCTS	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18
FINISHED LEATHER (SQ. FT)	836.88	688.81	705.87
LEATHER FOOTWEAR(PAIRS)	105.54	104.38	112.19
FOOTWEAR COMPONENTS(PAIRS)	64.03	44.61	46.41
LEATHER GARMENTS(PIECES)	9.38	7.43	8.16
LEATHER GLOVES(PAIRS)	149.05	156.69	148.76
LEATHER GOODS(PIECES)	157.22	141.09	143.8
SADDLERY AND HARNESS(PIECES)	19.41	19.36	32.49
NON-LEATHER FOOTWEAR(PAIRS)	13.6	24.22	24.04

Some of the key trends, information and most significant data points concerning the export of leather and leather products from India are shown in Figures 2-2, 2-3, and 2-4.

Figure 2- 2 Major importer of Footwear and related items (2001-2018) (Source: Directorate of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics (DGCI&S))

Figure 2- 3 Major importer of Raw Hides and Skins (2001-2018) (Source: Directorate of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics (DGCI&S))

Figure 2- 4 Major importers of Articles of Leather (Source: Directorate of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics (DGCI&S))

Over the last few years, the export curve for leather products from India has been decreased, and Figure 2-5 presents evidence of this trend.

Figure 2- 5 Leather Exports of India – Trendline 2014-18 (Source: Directorate of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics (DGCI&S))

The USA and Germany have been amongst the major importers of Indian leather and leather products in recent years according to data from 2014-2018, during which time these two

countries accounted for goods worth \$2.89 billion and 2.38 billion respectively. Figure 2-6 presents information on the major importers of leather products from India.

Figure 2- 6 Leather Exports of India – Major Importers 2014-18 (Source: Directorate of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics (DGCI&S))

India has moved towards being a supplier of value-added leather products rather than raw hides and skins. Official data indicate that the value of exports in 2018 reached \$1420 million. The leather industry has grown over the decades from a value of \$1.42 billion in 1990-91 to about \$4 billion in 2010-11 and then \$6.5 billion in 2014-15. Thus, this industry has secured its place amongst the top ten industries in India in terms of foreign exchange. The growth potential of the leather industry is still immense, and growth in the financial year 2018-19 was 8%. The Council of Leather Exports is targeting a growth rate of 9% -10% for the next coming years. The industry is also one of the main areas of focus in the foreign policy of the Indian government, with its primary competition coming from countries like China and Vietnam. Leather exports from China declined by 11%, but those from Vietnam increased by 46%.

The leather-based shoe market segment is the primary driver of the boom for complete leather-based enterprises. India exports approximately 115 million pairs of shoes annually. The main markets for Indian footwear in 2013-14 were the United Kingdom at 16.8% of the total, Germany (13.6%), the USA (12.3%), Italy (7.3%), and France (7.2%). Approximately 78% of Indian footwear exports go to European Currency Units (ECU) nations and the USA.

India is the fifth biggest exporter of leather goods and add-ons, including gloves, in the world. Those add-ons are produced via huge brands like Coach, Pierre Cardin, Yves St Laurent, Etienne Aigner, Geoffrey Beane, Harrods, Marks & Spencer, Liz Claiborne, Tommy Hilfiger, Kieffer, Waldhausen, Biemen, Nederinum, Zaldi, Kallquists, Shires, GFS, and Millers.

The next most important market segment is leather garments. India is the second-biggest manufacturer of leather clothes after China. India has also emerged as the second-largest exporter of saddlery and harnesses across the world, with products including saddles, bridles, harnesses, and various saddlery goods. The major production sectors of leather and leather-related products in India are given in Table 2-3.

Table 2- 3 Leather Production Centres of India

STATES TERRIRORIES	& CITIES
TAMIL NADU	Chennai, Ambur, Ranipet, Vaniyambadi, Vellore, Pernambut, Trichy, Dindigul and Erode
WEST BENGAL	Kolkata
UTTAR PRADESH	Kanpur, Agra, Noida, Saharanpur
MAHARASHTRA	Mumbai
PUNJAB	Jallandhar
KARNATAKA	Bengaluru
ANDHRA PRADESH	Hyderabad
HARYANA	Ambala, Gurgaon, Panchkula, Karnal and Faridabad
DELHI	
MADHYA PRADESH	Dewas
KERALA	Calicul and Ernakulam / Cochin
RAJASTHAN	Jaipur
JAMMU AND KASHMIR	

2.5 Leather Products in India

2.5.1 Leather Hides

Leather hides are an important by-product of the meat industry. Unfortunately, there is often little incentive for farmers to keep hides intact on the animal until slaughter. This has resulted in a decrease in the quality and size of hides, making it more difficult to find quality leather. There are a number of different ways to improve the quality and size of leather hides, but most of them require significant investment. If farmers are paid properly for keeping their hides intact, it would create more value for them.

The production of leather is a long and complicated process that begins with the removal of the animal's skin. This is usually accomplished soon after the death of the animal, but in some cases the hide may be tanned and stored for later use. The next step is to remove all of the hair and fat in a process which can take up to two months. Once this is completed, the hide is divided into different grades and types depending on how it will be used.

2.5.2 Wallets

People carry their money and personal possessions in wallets, which are small everyday accessories. The traditional method of wallet making in India uses a special stitching procedure passed down through the generations, and the end results are frequently works of art.

2.5.3 Belts

India's belt output has hugely increased in recent years. This is due to the country's extensive belt manufacturing infrastructure which is backed up by a solid supply chain. Furthermore, the quality of Indian-made belts is equivalent to those from China and other wealthy countries. As a result, Indian belt exports to wealthy nations have increased.

There are several belt producers in India; however, the sector is relatively unorganised. The product line is extensive and diverse, but quality and standardisation may be lacking in which case buyers do not have many options. In this area, there is also no good brand positioning, which indicates that there is a lot of room for development.

Men wear leather belts as one of their most popular accessories. They come in a range of forms and sizes, as well as a variety of fabrics, making them a versatile wardrobe essential. Because it is both durable and attractive, leather is the most popular material used to produce belts. The calfskin belt manufacturing sector in India is rapidly expanding, and hundreds of belt manufacturers currently operate in the nation. Their business is anticipated to expand further in the coming years.

2.5.4 Footwear

The footwear industry in India is a significant contributor to the country's economy, generating annual revenues of over Rs. 25,000 crore and providing employment to over 650,000 people. Despite this, the industry faces several challenges which are adversely impacting its growth. These include inadequate infrastructure, the lack of raw materials and skilled manpower, and high taxation levels. In order to overcome these hurdles and to enable the footwear industry to reach its full potential, the government needs to take concerted action and provide support in the form of improved infrastructure.

India's footwear industry is a major contributor to the country's economy. It is a significant exporter of shoes and one of the main employers in the manufacturing sector. In recent years, the business has experienced rapid expansion thanks to increased demand from both local and foreign consumers. Several international corporations have recently entered the Indian market, and the industry is expected to grow further in the future.

Growth in the footwear industry can be attributed to various factors, such as rising income levels, changing demographics, and the expansion of organised retail activities. The market is also witnessing increasing participation from foreign players. All of these trends point towards a bright future for the Indian footwear industry.

In India, the footwear business is rapidly expanding. The entire market size was Rs. 41,000 crores in 2017, and it is expected to expand at a CAGR of 11% to Rs. 60,700 crores by 2021. By 2025, the sector is predicted to be valued at Rs. 1, 24,400 crores. The rise in disposable income, improved knowledge of footwear, and the growing desire for branded

fashionable footwear are all factors contributing to this expansion. The Indian footwear market is, however, very fragmented.

2.5.5 Leather Garments

India's leather garment manufacturing business is a vital part of the country's economy, employing over three million people and contributing more than \$6 billion to the country's GDP. The sector has grown considerably in recent years, with yearly exports exceeding \$2 billion. Despite its tremendous expansion, the business has a number of obstacles, including poor labour productivity levels, insufficient infrastructure, and shortages of trained staff (Mishra and Pal, 2015).

2.6 Initiatives by the Indian and State Governments to Promote or Enhance the Competitiveness of the Industry

The leather sector has been designated by the Indian government as an area of focus in foreign trade policy due to its enormous potential for export growth and job creation. As a result, the government is pursuing a number of Special Focus Initiatives in order to help the leather industry thrive. With the implementation of various industrial development programmes and export promotional activities, as well as the industry's inherent strengths of skilled manpower, innovative technology, increased industry compliance with international environmental standards, and dedicated support from allied industries, the Indian leather industry aims to increase production and exports, thereby creating additional employment opportunities.

The leather footwear sector is one of twelve where India may be considered to be a global supplier, according to the Indian government. The following schemes have been undertaken by the Government of India to promote foster the leather industry in India as part of the support provided by the Indian Leather Development Programme (ILDLP):

- Under the Leather Technology, Innovative and Environmental Issues scheme, support available includes: up to 50% of the project cost to a maximum of \$7.69 million for upgrading or installing Common Effluent Treatment Plants (CETPs);

addressing the pollutants created by leather units in the environment; and providing environmental workshops on solid waste management.

- Under the Integrated Development of the Leather Sector (IDLS) scheme, micro small units can receive a 30% grant for plant machinery costs, while other units receive a 20% grant, with a maximum total grant of \$307,000 for each product line.
- The ILDP Mega Leather Cluster (MLC) scheme provides a 50% grant with a ceiling of \$19.23 million based on size. This is primarily for the purpose of establishing very large leather clusters in order to improve infrastructure and support services for production and export.
- Under the scheme for Human Resource Development (HRD), people who are unemployed can get help with placement-linked skills development training at \$230 per person, while employed workers can get training to upgrade their skills for \$76 per employee, and trainers can receive instruction for \$3,076 per person. The Footwear Design and Development Institute (FDDI) has established itself as the leading training institute for the leather industry's qualified employees, and has 55 training centres and eight subsidiaries across India. Four more branches are being established, and 25,643 people were trained in the primary skills development programme in 2018-19.
- The Mega Leather, Footwear, and Accessories Cluster (MLFAC) scheme supports infrastructure development for the leather, footwear, and accessories industry. Government assistance is limited to \$19 million and may offer up to 50% of the cost of an approved project (excluding land costs).
- The Leather Technology, Innovation, and the Environment scheme grants assistance for the upgrading or installation of Common Effluent Treatment Plants (CETPs) at 70% of the project cost. Assistance is also provided to national-level sectoral industry councils or associations, as well as in the drafting of a vision plan for the Leather Footwear Accessories Sector.
- Eligible units are recognised for Brand Promotion of Indian Brands in the Leather, Footwear, and Accessories scheme. Government funding is limited to 50% of overall project costs, with a maximum of \$461,538 per brand every year for three years.

- The Leather, Footwear, and Accessories Sector Additional Employment Incentive Scheme provides that employers in the leather, footwear, accessories sector contribute 3.67% to their employees' provident fund and, for their first three years of employment, new employees are enrolled in the Employees' Provident Fund Organization (EPFO).
- Goods and Services Tax (GST) reductions for leather sector items include the following: finished leather from 12% to 5%; certain leather chemicals, leather goods, leather garments, and saddlery items from 28% to 18%; Common Effluent Treatment Plants (CETPs) from 18% to 12%; and footwear from 18% to 5%.
- The Integrated Development of Leather Sector (IDLS) project is one of the most significant government efforts. It aims to help existing tanneries and production units for footwear, footwear components, and leather products to upgrade, resulting in increased productivity, cost reductions, and design development, while also encouraging entrepreneurs to diversify and open new businesses. The scheme provides financial assistance in the form of an investment grant covering 30% of the cost of plant and machinery for MSEs and 20% of the cost of plant and machinery for other non-small-scale units up to a maximum of Rs. 50 lakhs for technology upgrades, modernization, expansion, and/or the establishment of a new unit.
- For all units (including both MSEs and non-MSEs) with a turnover of more than 50 lakh and a maximum of Rs. 2 crore, the rate of support is 20%. Obtaining a bank loan without collateral has also been a major issue for small business owners. Furthermore, the banks view the financing of small businesses as a high-risk option. To address this issue, the Ministry of Small-Scale Industries introduced the Credit Guarantee Fund Trust Scheme for Micro and Small Enterprises (CGTMSE) in May 2000 with the goal of making credit available to small-scale industrial units, and particularly micro units (with an investment in plant machinery of less than ₹ 25 lakh) for loans up to ₹ 10 lakh without the need for collateral or third-party guarantees. The CGTMSE was set up jointly by the government of India and the Small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI) which administers the

initiative. The scheme's lending ceiling was originally set at ₹ 10 lakh per borrower but this has recently been raised to Rs. 25 lakh (Kumar, 2012).

- A large percentage of micro and small businesses rely only on sensory quality control for their products. Medium-sized businesses, on the other hand, have a high level of understanding standard quality criteria. These regulations are also well understood by companies that are actively involved in exporting. Micro and small business owners need to be educated on quality standards and the requirement to develop a consistent quality procedure for their business. Manufacturers of leather items must utilise finished leather that has been approved by the Central Leather Research Institute (CLRI) or other recognised bodies. In the case of tanneries, the owners must guarantee that the chemicals used are compliant with international standards (Kumar, 2012).
- Purchasers usually need a 30-day credit term. The SIDBI-implemented MSME-FDP has recently allowed businesses in the Kolkata cluster to climb the value-added ladder and produce high-end fashion gloves with a greater margin in the worldwide market (Kumar, 2012).

2.7 Current Status and Statistics

India's leather industry produces approximately 13% of the world's hides and skins and produces over 3 billion square feet of leather annually. The country's footwear output represents 9% of the global total. The industry is noted for consistently strong export revenues and is one of the country's top 10 foreign exchange-earners.

With access to 20% of the world's cattle and buffalo, as well as 11% of the goat and sheep populations, India has a plethora of raw resources.

Leather is a high-wage sector with approximately 4 million workers, the bulk of them from lower socioeconomic classes. Women account for around 30% of the workforce in the leather goods business. India's leather industry has one of the youngest workforces in the world, with 55% of employees under the age of 35.

The major markets for Indian leather and leather products are the United States (17.22%), Germany (11.98%), the United Kingdom (10.43%), Italy (6.33%), France (5.94%), Spain (5.01%), the Netherlands (3.52%), the United Arab Emirates (3.35%), China (2.61%), Hong Kong (2.15%), Belgium (2.21%), and Poland (2.11%). 250 jobs are produced for every \$0.2 million spent in the leather industry. (Sagar, 2020) .

2.7.1 Exports

Table 2-4 presents the percentage of exports value between 2019-20 and 2020-21. It is clear from this table that, except for the saddlery and harness segment, export levels have decreased due to COVID-19.

Table 2- 4 INDIA'S EXPORT OF LEATHER & LEATHER PRODUCTS 2019-20 vis-a-vis 2020-21 (Value in US\$ Mn) (Source DGCI&S)

CATEGORY	APR	APR	%	%
	MAR	MAR	VARIATION	SHARE
-	2019-2020	2020-2021		2021
FINISHED LEATHER	524.15	378.23	-27.84%	10.27%
LEATHER FOOTWEAR	2081.67	1485.55	-28.64%	40.35%
FOOTWEAR COMPONENTS				
LEATHER GARMENTS	429.11	295.56	-31.12%	8.03%
LEATHER GOODS	1353.74	944.31	-30.24%	25.65%
SADDLERY AND HARNESS	151.44	186.18	22.94%	5.06%
NON-LEATHER FOOTWEAR	281.97	194.16	-31.14%	5.27%
TOTAL	5083.76	3681.58	-27.58%	100.00%

Further, information on India's exports to various countries for the last five financial years is presented in Table 2-5.

Table 2- 5 India's Leather and Leather Products Exports (US \$ Mn) (Source: DGCI&S)

COUNTRY	2016- 17	2017- 18	2018- 19	2019- 20	2020- 21	%SHARE OF 2020-21
USA	867.19	847.30	893.68	873.29	645.03	17.52%
GERMANY	657.37	684.41	659.18	607.44	481.44	13.08%
UK	606.18	616.41	597.30	528.84	326.98	8.88%
ITALY	374.09	389.06	368.71	320.75	248.6	6.75%
FRANCE	287.74	326.38	323.02	301.07	245.42	6.67%
SPAIN	293.43	281.30	258.26	254.13	154.06	4.18%
U.A.E.	226.72	161.27	226.18	169.86	80.05	2.17%
NETHERLANDS	169.00	196.98	194.43	178.68	155.42	4.22%
HONG KONG	265.60	248.07	190.31	109.16	58.48	1.59%
CHINA	173.72	170.34	148.21	132.12	95.15	2.58%
POLAND	101.06	144.47	115.02	106.78	86.26	2.34%
BELGIUM	104.90	114.80	114.09	112.16	80.02	2.17%
SOMALIA	94.12	58.82	102.24	57.94	42.42	1.15%
VIETNAM	92.38	104.81	98.44	82.48	53.33	1.45%
AUSTRALIA	82.66	91.16	95.36	85.15	74.95	2.04%
PORTUGAL	67.61	68.62	68.77	58.38	44.45	1.21%
DENMARK	77.22	69.35	67.39	68.36	61.24	1.66%
KOREA REP.	68.65	67.22	66.12	57.32	35.91	0.98%
JAPAN	63.87	71.42	65.53	59.48	45.69	1.24%
RUSSIA	51.15	56.08	52.59	46.58	39.28	1.07%
SOUTH AFRICA	44.13	43.80	52.28	44.68	26.17	0.71%
CHILE	41.85	44.90	48.87	39.97	31.92	0.87%
MALAYSIA	48.60	48.77	46.32	33.67	32.4	0.88%
AUSTRIA	27.86	46.26	43.82	46.00	27.72	0.75%
CANADA	46.94	50.50	43.27	47.06	35.81	0.97%
SWEDEN	40.83	43.20	40.02	34.54	28.1	0.76%

NIGERIA	20.29	24.75	37.53	19.26	12.79	0.35%
INDONESIA	26.97	33.82	37.23	34.35	17.94	0.49%
MEXICO	12.14	19.36	36.07	29.68	17.69	0.48%
SAUDI ARABIA	40.86	37.87	33.65	38.96	23.23	0.63%
KENYA	30.25	22.04	32.29	16.38	11.52	0.31%
SWITZERLAND	24.83	30.37	31.41	37.17	29.5	0.80%
SLOVAK REP	31.48	36.44	26.61	20.29	14.48	0.39%
HUNGARY	28.23	24.65	24.31	20.04	20.9	0.57%
THAILAND	19.82	19.82	20.20	16.99	14.92	0.41%
BANGLADESH	34.98	27.59	19.84	20.42	13.51	0.37%
FINLAND	17.25	19.76	18.64	16.32	11.66	0.32%
TURKEY	19.96	22.63	16.31	11.30	11.85	0.32%
ISRAEL	13.24	15.87	15.86	17.13	13.46	0.37%
CAMBODIA	10.37	7.27	10.84	9.07	4.7	0.13%
CZECH REPUBLIC	9.34	11.91	10.52	11.48	8.35	0.23%
GREECE	10.16	10.28	10.46	9.61	8.25	0.22%
NEW ZEALAND	9.82	9.88	10.16	8.88	8.6	0.23%
OMAN	12.29	9.32	9.46	7.46	6.68	0.18%
SRI LANKA DES	14.42	12.34	9.39	8.60	4.57	0.12%
SINGAPORE	33.04	14.42	9.22	8.71	4.59	0.12%
SUDAN	14.63	8.86	9.10	14.11	11	0.30%
TAIWAN	8.97	8.07	8.44	5.84	4.38	0.12%
NORWAY	7.54	8.76	6.32	6.77	6.49	0.18%
DJIBOUTI	11.19	8.56	6.28	3.94	3.13	0.09%
OTHERS	209.98	249.40	261.02	221.90	161.09	4.38%
TOTAL	5646.80	5740.97	5691.00	5070.55	3681.58	100.00%

The contribution of countries in India's leather exports is presented in Figure 2-7, for the financial year 2020-21.

Figure 2- 7 Percent Share of Countries in Indian Leather Exports Source: ((CLE), 2022)

2.8 Recent Macro Level Updates

1. The Mega Cluster Leather scheme proposes to develop huge Greenfield leather clusters in states with high concentrations of leather production, as well as in states with growth potential in the leather sector. In addition to providing drainage and power supplies, co-production centres, raw material processing units and advanced training centres are currently being planned in each leather district (CLE, 2022).
2. Ramaipur's leather goods mega-district will employ about a million people. Muhatrul Amin, former president of the Leather Export Council, said the approval of the project was a great gift for the leather industry (CLE, 2022).
3. Prime Minister Narendra Modi announced the establishment of a leather district in Kanpur. The launch of Kanpur's Mega Leather Park at Ramaipur Village will further enhance its position in the top 10 leather producing states in the country. The city of Kanpur was once known as East Manchester due to its vibrant textile industry, although the city lost its identity over time due to abandonment by previous governments. Kanpur was called East Manchester because of its textile industry and was also called Leather City because of the presence of many tanneries. Officials say the leather park will give a new identity to the industrial city of Kanpurnagar, which dominates the leather industry. The leather park could create indirect employment for 150,000 people. This will help lead a sustainable transformation of

the leather industry in Kanpur (Sharma and Varma, 2012). The main focus of the programme is the development and implementation of technologically environmentally friendly processes for the leather industry. The project will enable around 350 tanneries to meet increasingly high international quality environmental standards, thereby increasing the competitiveness of the Indian leather industry and improving working conditions and health in surrounding communities. The state central government have been working hard to develop leather districts, but there is still a lot of work to be done to help the leather industry reach the heights it deserves (CLE, 2022).

4. The leather industry has been designated as an industry of special interest in the National Industrial Policy and is supported by the Leather Industry Skills Council (LSSC), which was established with the sole purpose of bridging the skills gap in the leather industry by connecting all regions of the country. The leather-based footwear cluster is one of five supported through the Personal Sector Improvement Cluster undertaking (PSDCP) implemented by the national Ministry of the Economy in cooperation with the Palestinian Federation of Chambers of commerce and industry (FPCCIA) (CLE, 2022).
5. The government of India has approved the Indian Leather Development Plan (ILDLP). A programme under the Indian Leather Development Plan (ILDLP) called ‘Large Leather Clusters’ 2012-17 annual plan.
6. The Uttar Pradesh government is developing the country’s first leather park, the Mega Leather Park, as part of the 235-acre Mega Leather Cluster project in Kanpur. In a major push for the leather industry, Prime Minister Akhilesh Yadav approved two new large-scale leather cluster (MLC) projects to bring in the Hardoi and Ramapur districts of Kanpur region. This cluster will produce leather shoes, bags, jackets and other world-class products using state-of-the-art equipment. The Kanpur leather complex was opened by Maarten van den Berg, Ambassador of the Netherlands to India. Stahl CEO Huub van Beijeren, also present at the opening, said the partnership with Solidaridad was a “great opportunity” to bring about positive change in the Kanpur Unnao leather district. Van Beijeren said that Stahls’

approach to a more sustainable transparent leather industry is based on encouraging collaboration across the entire supply chain, and that the Centre of Excellence programmes are the result of effective collaboration. In 2008-2009, export-oriented investments from China, as well as from Europe and India, began to flow into the footwear industry. The leather districts of Chennai, Kanpur, Agra and Kolkata produce 90% of all leather goods in India and contribute enormously to the economic development of India. Kolkata, the largest cluster in West Bengal, also generates a significant share of the leather industry’s revenue (CLE, 2022).

7. The literature suggests that foreign investors can be catalysts in helping an industrial cluster to overcome barriers to transformation, but they can also provide ‘unfair’ competition. Kanpur’s tanneries, especially the smaller ones, have been operating well below their production capacity in recent years. The health and safety conditions of tannery workers are also not optimal, due to a lack of awareness. Therefore, skin respiratory diseases are common among workers in the leather industry.

(CLE, 2022)

2.8.1 Macro Picture

This section describes national trends for products like footwear, leather-related products, bags and wallets. As evident from Figures 2-8, 2-9 and 2-10, bags and wallets have smaller market shares and the growth of these segments is also slower compared to others.

Figure 2- 8 Annual Survey (Footwear)

Figure 2- 9 Leather and Related Products

Figure 2- 10 Bags and Wallets

2.9 Theoretical and Practical Approaches to Industrial Clusters Globally

Industrial clusters, agglomeration economies, and their implications for economic growth and development have been extensively studied in the literature. The theories on industrial clusters have undergone continuous development and refinement, building upon existing related theories. These theories have progressed through different stages of development, emerging in response to specific situational needs and demands. Concepts related to industrial clusters draw inspiration from various theories, including Von Thunen's location theory (Von Thünen, 1966), agglomeration theory, Marshall's industrial district theory (Marshall, 1890), Weber's industrial complex theory (Weber and Friedrich, 1929), and

Michael Porter's cluster theory (Porter, 1998). The phenomenon of economic agglomeration, where production and commercial activities concentrate in specific regions, has been a subject of study by economists and geographers for over two centuries. Different models are adopted for economic agglomeration and industrial clusters, considering the unique geographic characteristics of each location. Scholars like Von Thunen, Alfred Weber, and Oskar Englund (Englund, 2014) have formulated theories to understand the fundamental factors contributing to economic agglomeration as a universal phenomenon (Weber and Friedrich, 1929). Von Thunen's location theory in 1826, proposed more than 200 years ago, aimed to predict the specialization of countries in the production of specific goods and remains widely utilized in modern economic studies and international economic theory. Launhardt and Weber further developed the location theory, identifying three key location forces: transport cost, labor cost differential, and agglomeration economies (Launhardt, 1885). However, it was Cambridge economist Alfred Marshall who first presented the concept of geographic concentration of trade and industry in his 1890 publication "Principles of Economics (Marshall, 1890)." He has promulgated the idea of the cluster. Marshall highlighted external and internal economies that prevail among industries in British industrial districts, emphasizing knowledge spillover, labor market pooling, and cost advantages achieved through sharing industry-specific non-trade inputs, as later suggested by Hofe and Chen in 2006. Marshall's concept of economies related to localization posits that concentrating firms and businesses within the same industry in a specific geographic area enhances the innovation capabilities of the entire industry (Groenewegen, 1990; Marshall, 1890).

Marshall introduced the term 'industrial districts', having observed that the co-presence of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) represented a position of considerable authority concerning similar products in specific districts of the UK; for example, Lancashire cotton, Staffordshire pottery, and Sheffield cutlery. Organisations working in these commercial zones could profit by reserve funds (for example, lower input costs) and higher specialization. These advantages were understood as being external to every individual firm in the zone, yet internal to the gathering of organisations found there. Marshall distinguished a set of three of elements, which were later called agglomeration economies,

as the wellsprings of these positive externalities: a gifted labour pool; nearby non-exchange sources of information; and high data flows due to proximity. Subsequently, Krugman (1991) created the "New Economic Geography," which placed an emphasis on agglomeration economies emphasises the importance of factors such as transport costs, customer preferences, and increasing returns to scale in influencing the geographic distribution of economic activities. In the 1970s, monetary students of history and sociologists created the neo-Marshallian mechanical region custom to depict the efficacy of sectoral gatherings of SMEs in north-east Italy (the so-called 'Third Italy'). In these neo-Marshallian zones, creativity takes place in thick modern systems through an "increased division of labour among small and medium-sized enterprises that invest significant time in specific stages or integral activities inside a typical mechanical segment." (Groenewegen, 1990). These studies have three major flaws in common with the previous grants: they fail to fully clarify the connections between territorial and national administrative systems; they represent the relationship between these mechanical structures and universal markets in an incomplete manner; and they focus on cutting-edge economies in generally late times.

In terms of the interaction between territorial and national geologies, (Porter, 2000) made a substantial commitment, returning to the Marshallian idea of financial focus in the realm of business technique to understand its impact on nation-state competitiveness. Porter (1998) developed the idea of "clusters" to analyse competitiveness and regional economic performance. Fujita and Thisse (1996) conduct a thorough investigation into how geographical factors influence economic activities, such as the growth of industrial hubs. To account for the uneven distribution of businesses around the country, the authors propose a paradigm that brings together the concepts of growing returns to scale, transportation costs, and location choice.

Saxenian (1994) contrasts the rise of Silicon Valley with that of Massachusetts' Route 128 technological corridor. The author highlighted that distinctions in local culture, institutional systems, and collaborative networks account for the successes shown in each case. Firms in clusters are more likely to innovate because of knowledge spillovers, specialised labor, and shared infrastructure, as studied by Beaudry and Breschi (2003). The favourable impacts of industry clustering on productivity, innovation, and regional

development are demonstrated in this meta-analysis of empirical studies on agglomeration economies. Successful industrial clusters tend to share characteristics including robust local and global networks, specialised resources, supportive institutions, and a culture of collaboration and invention (Ketels, 2013; Asheim and Isaksen, 1997).

2.10 Different policy instruments for Growth of Industrial Clusters

Clusters play a crucial role in promoting local economic development by acting as catalysts for international connections, attracting skilled labor, facilitating technological advancements, and fostering the creation of tacit knowledge. The establishment and growth of clusters are driven by the pursuit of tangible economic benefits. Economic geographers have examined economic performance through various perspectives, with one approach focusing on clusters rather than individual firms. For instance, Li et al. (2012) explored the relationship between cluster size and the size of firms within the cluster, while Beaudry and Breschi (2003) demonstrated the impact of cluster strength on firm growth. Another approach shifts the focus to the contribution of clusters to regional economic development, considering the interconnectedness between clusters and the broader region. Portnov (2006) found that even low-density clusters can have a positive influence on regional economies. The other approach investigates the geographical distribution of clusters across different regions, with studies by Bottazzi and Dindo (2013) examining this influence from a technological perspective and Ezcurra et al. (2006) analyzing the distribution and concentration of industries across various European countries. These multidimensional perspectives shed light on the significance of clusters in driving local economic development and provide insights into their dynamics within regional and global contexts. Different policy instruments have been developed and implemented by governments worldwide to foster the growth of industrial clusters. These include setting up industry-specific structures, encouraging collaboration amongst cluster members, and providing financial incentives (Ketels, 2013). Clusters have been encouraged in many countries as a part of the suburbanisation of enterprises. Industrial zones were a means to promote the geographical concentration of similar units and favourable policies were offered for them to become part of clusters (Zou *et al.*, 2021). Meanwhile, in some places, immigrants have

gradually developed industrial clusters over a period of time; for example, Collins (2021) presents an intriguing case of first-generation Korean immigrants and their restaurant industry cluster in Sydney. While each cluster's policy is unique, they all share a common goal of fostering an environment that encourages innovation and competitiveness. (Bathelt et al., 2004). The Silicon Valley in California has set the standard for prosperous business communities around the world. Reasons for its success include a supportive regulatory climate, a skilled labour force, and access to venture capital (Saxenian, 1994). While both industrial clusters and export processing zones (EPZs) aim to promote economic growth, they differ in several key respects. Replicating this model has proven difficult for other regions due to differences in local contexts, the presence of pre-existing networks, and the complex interplay of various factors contributing to cluster success (Ketels, Lindqvist and Sölvell, 2006). EPZs often have preferential tax and regulatory treatment and a focus on export-oriented industry, while industrial clusters are characterised by geographic concentration, interdependence, and positive externalities (Wu, 2009). In the comparison of clusters and export processing zones (EPZs), Ketels (2013), Glaeser (2010) and Asheim and Isaksen (1997) highlighted that both forms of industrial agglomerations can contribute to economic development by attracting investment, creating jobs, and boosting exports. Clusters arise naturally through market dynamics and inter-firm relationships, while EPZs are planned and regulated areas established by governments to attract export-oriented businesses. Clusters foster innovation and knowledge sharing among firms, leading to enhanced competitiveness, while EPZs primarily focus on attracting foreign direct investment and promoting export activities through incentives and infrastructure support. The choice between these models depends on specific objectives, industrial context, and policy priorities of a given region or country (Madani, 2003; Engman, Onodera and Pinali, 2007).

State industrial companies (SICs) and industrial estates played a significant role in early phases of India's policy to promote industrial growth, while leather clusters emerged as a more contemporary, region-specific solution. The effectiveness and implications of these two approaches, particularly for the Indian economy, are discussed in the next section.

2.11 State Industrial Corporations (SICs) and Industrial Estates

After India gained independence, SICs were founded to promote industrialization and economic development. These state industrial firms were instrumental in establishing industrial estates or zones, which supplied necessary infrastructure, land, and other resources to local businesses. The fundamental goal of SICs was to foster a setting that encouraged industrial development, attracted investments, and produced new jobs. The development of industrial estates with reliable sources of energy, water, and transportation was important in achieving this goal. Heavy engineering, textiles, chemicals, food processing, and many more industries were all served by SICs. State governments typically own SICs and supervise their management and daily operations. India's early industrial development relied heavily on SICs and industrial estates, both of which contributed significantly to regional economic growth. Gujarat's state government has constructed and managed industrial zones very well, resulting in significant industrial expansion and economic development, making it a shining example of a successful industrial estate. These estates have helped small and medium-sized businesses thrive by providing a supportive setting, pooled resources, and easy access to utilities (Abhishek and Biswas, 2018).

However, they have encountered difficulties, such as bureaucracy, which can cause delays in decision-making and the execution of programmes in industrial estates. This can limit the range of motion and responsiveness available to firms in these estates. Furthermore, industrial estates may be hampered by inefficiencies, lack of flexibility, and restricted creativity, which could make them less efficient at encouraging corporate collaboration and innovation than private sector-led clusters in responding to shifting market conditions (Rodrik, 2004) and (Warwick, 2013).

To simulate the natural agglomeration economies that have developed through time when many enterprises of the same type settle in the same geographic area, industrial clusters have been developed (Glaeser, 2010). Cost savings, higher productivity, and better innovation are all the result of the agglomeration economies that occur from variables like common infrastructure, access to a skilled labour pool, and closeness to suppliers and customers (Fujita, Krugman and Venables, 2001; Krugman, 1991; Glaeser, 2010). Industrial clusters are artificially formed by governments and policymakers to achieve the same goals

of increased economic growth and competitiveness as their more organic counterparts (Rosenthal and Strange, 2004). It is important to note, however, that the success of artificially cultivated industrial clusters is contingent on a number of factors, including the nature of the sector, the resources already present in the location, and the regulations that have been put in place (Porter, 2000; Martin and Sunley, 2003). In the study of Das and Das (2011) which suggests that industrial clusters are likely to have long-term advantages, fostering innovation and productivity growth. The success of these entities is influenced by factors such as location, targeted industry, infrastructure, amenities, and government support. This study provides valuable insights into the characteristics and potential benefits of industrial estates and industrial clusters, highlighting the superior long-term effectiveness of clusters.

2.12 Industrial Leather Clusters

Clusters can also be used to learn about different supply chain and value chain strategies in a specific industry. By examining the dynamics of clusters, studies like those by (Chhetri *et al.*, 2021) have generated mathematical optimization models. In an interesting study (O'Clery and Kinsella, 2022), investigated the availability and ease of access to labour due to the presence of clusters. Workforce availability and employment are some of the most vital benefits of industrial clusters. Clusters, on the other hand, have been seen to survive by changing their formats and matching their rate of development to scientific and technological breakthroughs (Lamberty and Nevers, 2022). A meta-analytical study by (Fang and Drucker, 2021), examined the breadth and depth of the impact of a cluster on the functioning of participants. It was concluded that clusters should be directed to geographical locations where they yield maximum benefits for specific local requirements. Clusters of businesses involved in the tanning, processing, and manufacture of leather items constitute industrial leather clusters. They hope that by collaborating, manufacturers, suppliers, and support services can increase the sector's competitiveness and productivity. The major objective of leather clusters is to help the expansion of the leather sector by providing focused assistance, encouraging innovation, strengthening the supply chain, and cutting costs through the pooling of resources. Leather clusters provide specialised services

to the leather business sector and its subsidiary industries. Clusters in the leather industry may receive funding from the government or the private sector, with the latter option being the more common. One popular form of management for such groups is the Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV) model (Sainati *et al.*, 2020). Clusters, like those focused on the leather industry, can boost growth in that sector, encourage new ideas, and make exports more competitive. They've helped the economy flourish and new jobs be created in the area. Environmental issues, a lack of readily available capital, and a dearth of qualified workers are just some of the obstacles that may stand in their way.

Henceforth, both state industrial corporations based on industrial estates and industrial leather clusters have played a role in promoting industrial development in India. Leather clusters tend to focus on a specific sector, while SICs and industrial estates serve a wider variety of businesses. Both approaches have their merits and challenges, and a balanced combination of the two strategies can support the overall growth and competitiveness of the Indian economy.

2.13 Clustering Approach and Types of Clusters

Three distinctive approaches to industrial clustering have developed over the years.

2.13.1 National Clusters

These are gatherings of organisations and associations which cooperatively deal with improvement issues for the cluster. They regularly address strategy, framework, and scale-related issues. The North American Industry Classification System (NAICS) and Feser Bergman's manufacturing templates provide up-to-date methods to identify industry clusters at the national level (Kelton, Pasquale and Rebelein, 2008). Technical information sharing and knowledge transfer are usually among the main drivers of such clusters (Akgüngör, Kumral and Lenger, 2003).

2.13.2 Regional Clusters

For a huge number of economic activities, a small number of publications describe region-specific clusters. Some of these studies pinpoint specific "driver" industries in which an

area excels. The clusters around the driver industries are then defined using region-specific inter-industry linkages, such as regional input-output models (Hill and Brennan, 2000). Other research focuses on determining a cluster's (non-administrative) geographic bounds. To do so, they look at the spatial density of enterprises in specific industries (Duranton and Overman, 2005) or the spatial density of patents in specific technological classes (Kerr and Kominers, 2015; Alcácer and Zhao, 2016). The idea is to find areas with a high density of economic activity in a specific subject that will make inter-firm relationships and externalities easier. The majority of region-specific cluster definitions are qualitative and based on case studies that tend to focus on specific clusters (Bresnahan and Gambardella, 2004). To identify clusters, these studies use existing cluster organisations, industry directories, and other primary data sources. They provide extensive information on the enterprises and organisations that make up specific defined clusters, but they may not be the best tool for comparing clusters across regions. Regional clusters are energizers for economic development, and spatial methods are used to identify such clusters (Liu *et al.*, 2021).

2.13.3 Commercial Clusters

These are groups of organisations that have opted to collaborate in different zones. The study of commercial clusters can facilitate urban planning and the development of commercial zones (Ozuduru *et al.*, 2021).

Some interesting case studies discuss the formation of clusters in terms of the decision making of units which choose to relocate to join a geographical cluster, such as in research by Krishna and Sivaraman (2021) and Bhawsar (2021) into examples in India.

2.14 Cluster Strategies

2.14.1 Defensive Cluster Strategies

Defensive cluster strategies are intended to address flaws in a region's economic infrastructure that may have an impact on the performance of a group of existing businesses. Such tactics normally do not necessitate cooperation among cluster members, although they

are more likely to be implemented when companies band together to communicate their demands to government authorities (Neto, 2019).

2.14.2 Offensive Cluster Strategies

Offensive cluster strategies aim to boost a cluster's competitiveness by providing value-added services to its members, either directly or through investment in new regional institutions or skills.

2.14.3 Prospective Cluster Strategies

Prospective cluster strategies, in a process often known as 'cluster engineering,' are initiatives which aim to turn major assets in a region's economic infrastructure into profitable enterprises. The establishment of a university department or research institute to promote the establishment of technology enterprises in relevant sectors is one example. While not all of these techniques are as harmful as Dr. Frankenstein's attempt to produce a walking, talking monster, they are often considered likely to be costly, unruly, and in the long run somewhat risky, like the aforementioned monster.

2.14.4 Cluster-Based Business Recruitment Strategies

Cluster-based company recruitment methods are primarily marketing activities aimed at recruiting specific firms, particularly those with competences that could boost the competitive advantage of other businesses in the cluster, and are usually driven by an economic development agency. These techniques frequently entail expanding an industry's local supply chain in order to maintain more of the cluster's activities in the region and broaden the cluster's breadth (Neto, 2019).

2.14.5 Pre-Cluster Consolidation Strategies

Pre-cluster consolidation techniques are used to try to acquire the benefits of offensive cluster strategies by coordinating collaboration among groups of enterprises that may not have the scale or prominence of a cluster at the outset. Even when a given industrial sector or expertise has significant geographical concentration, crucial links, institutions, or suppliers may be inadequate or absent (Neto, 2019).

Cluster activities, which may include the formation of organisations, government, or research activity, are coordinated endeavours which aim to increase the development intensity of clusters in an area. These activities have become a critical factor in increasing the development intensity of a group of people, as well as the province or nation in which they arise. A growing number of top-down groups may be formed which are initiated by a district or local government. Cluster activity can come from the most basic level, such as a neighbourhood, but it can also come from entities at the provincial or national levels. Figure 2-11 displays actors involved in the creating of cluster initiatives at different levels.

*Figure 2- 11 Actors involved in the creating of cluster initiatives at different levels
(Source: (Sölvell, 2009))*

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Research into 25 cluster initiatives conducted by Solvell and Lindqvist (2003), and presented in *The Cluster Initiative Greenbook* led to the following conclusions:

1. Each cluster effort was distinct, and its characteristics varied based on the extent of progress in the country in which it originated.
2. Cluster projects were most common in developed economies.
3. Cluster projects were formed mostly in high-tech domains such as medical devices, manufacturing technology, information technology, biotechnology, biopharmaceuticals, and the automobile industry.

4. The cluster efforts were initiated after 1999 in 72% of cases.
5. The majority of cluster programmes were developed in countries that promote science, innovation, and research and development.
6. The aims of cluster initiatives differed, and not all of the aims identified were shared by all of the cases studied.
7. Initiatives were typically complex and required the majority of their goals to be achieved; however earlier efforts seem to have been more specialised.
8. The government played an important role in 32% of the cluster projects, industry in 27%, and a combination of groups in 35%.
9. The government offers 54 percent of funding which is comprised for industries in different sectors.
10. Companies had the most influence over cluster initiative management, and only in limited circumstances were members elected by government initiative.
11. In terms of geographical coverage, the initiatives were limited, and half of the units began on the outskirts of an hour's distance.
12. Initiatives should often include a diverse range of participants, including foreign-owned businesses, competitors, and small and medium-sized businesses.

2.15 Clusters in India

Cluster-based tactics have an economic rationale, and we may assume that the strategy will persist. The application of the cluster paradigm to economic impact studies should be able to provide a more complete picture of the possible benefits of a cluster-based strategy.

India's rise as an industrial power in Asia and globally will necessitate not only a macroeconomic boost but also a complete implementation of innovation by MSMEs. As vital as it is to recognise the necessity for a cluster-based approach, innovation is the main solution to the various challenges that entrepreneurs experience. Overall, innovation makes it easier to tackle market difficulties, disseminate information more quickly, share

information and the best insights, and enhance cost efficiency by sharing common costs. It also ensures inter-firm cooperation through networking and trust, which is an effective and dynamic way to create competitiveness. Because of the close proximity of the businesses in a cluster and the commonality of their goods, interventions may be performed for a large number of units, resulting in bigger gains at lower cost and helping to ensure their long-term viability. As a result, the cluster method aspires to generate holistic development that includes attention to infrastructure, shared facilities, testing, technology, and skills upgrades, marketing, and export promotion (Beddig, 2008).

The Small-Scale industry (SSI) sector has made substantial contributions to India's economic growth. It accounts for 40% of the nation's industrial production and 35% of direct exports. The various clusters that have existed for decades, if not for centuries, play an essential role in small-scale industry. There are 350 SSI clusters in India, according to a UNIDO assessment conducted in 1996 and then revised in 1998, in addition to over 2000 rural artisan-based clusters. It is estimated that these clusters account for 60% of India's manufacturing exports as well as providing a large number of jobs (Das, 2017).

Some SSE clusters in India are so large that they account for up to 90% of the country's entire manufacturing output in certain products. Ludhiana's knitwear cluster is a good example, while Surat Mumbai clusters contribute almost all of the gem jewellery exports of the nation. Similarly, leather goods are highly recognised in the clusters of Chennai, Agra, and Kolkata.

The severe difficulties posed to the SSE sector by the liberalisation of the Indian economy, as well as its increased integration into the global economy, have sparked a great deal of interest in India in finding creative ways to develop the sector. As a result, both commercial and public sector entities at the federal and state levels are increasingly focusing on cluster development (Das, 2017) .

With more than 6000 clusters already documented, India has the most vital number of clusters as compared to others. As indicated in analysis by the Cluster Observatory, only 1156 current cluster which join 694,379 endeavours, a total of 15,692,736 used individuals. The state-wise clusters are shown in Figure 2-12.

Figure 2- 12 State-wise Clusters in India (Source: www.clusterobservatory.in)

Of the different states, Uttar Pradesh has the most SME clusters with 159, followed by Tamil Nadu with 103, and then Gujarat with 95. The six states of Uttar Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Kerala, and Andhra Pradesh account for 57% of all SME clusters.

Figure 2- 13 Zone-wise Presence of All Types of Clusters (Source: www.clusterobservatory.in)

Bhawsar and Chattopadhyay (2018) investigated four Indian industrial clusters in order to identify and prioritise the essential indicators of competitiveness for Indian clusters.

The effect of Marshallian agglomeration-localization economies, as well as location-specific policy incentives, were examined in a study of the micro-heterogeneity of the industrial clustering of registered Indian manufacturing enterprises. Only inter-industry buyer-supplier linkages and labour market pooling appeared to play substantial roles in industrial clustering, according to the empirical findings (Naskar, 2022).

Khan (2020) looked at the micro-heterogeneity of registered Indian manufacturing enterprises in industrial clusters, as well as the roles of Marshallian agglomeration-localization economies, and location-specific governmental incentives.

Song and Son (2020) explored the impact of geographical proximity on FDI spillovers from foreign to Indian local companies. Their research demonstrates that the presence of FDI causes large positive backward and negative horizontal spillovers within 30 km–70 km distance, but that these spillovers steadily fade as the threshold increases. In the meantime, negative horizontal spillovers to Indian local enterprises placed within industrial clusters have turned positive, and positive backward spillovers have increased in comparison to non-clustered firms.

2.16 Competitive Analysis Models for Industrial Leather clusters in India

The leather industry in India has played a significant role in the country's economic development, with a rich historical background and a substantial contribution to employment and export earnings. This section aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the leather industry in India by examining its historical context, the role of industrial clusters, and analyzing the industry through the lens of the PESTEL model and other competitive analysis models.

The leather industry in India dates back several centuries, with evidence of leather goods being produced in ancient Indian civilizations. Over time, the industry has grown and evolved, with the modern Indian leather sector encompassing a wide range of activities, from raw material processing to the manufacturing of finished leather goods, such as footwear, garments, accessories, and upholstery (Das, 2017). The post-independence period

in India saw significant growth in the leather industry, with the government establishing several institutions and implementing policies to support the sector. The establishment of organizations such as the Council for Leather Exports, the Central Leather Research Institute, and the Footwear Design and Development Institute have all played a critical role in the industry's development (CLRI, 2022; CLE, 2022).

Industrial clusters, defined as geographical concentrations of interconnected firms, suppliers, and institutions in a particular field, have played a crucial role in the growth and competitiveness of the leather industry in India (Porter, 1998; Das, 2017). Some of the most prominent leather clusters in India include Kanpur, Chennai, Uttar Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Kolkata, which together account for a significant share of the country's leather production and exports (CLE, 2022). Thus, these clusters benefit from economies of scale, access to skilled labor, and knowledge sharing, driving innovation and growth within the industry. Industrial clusters have played a critical role in the industry's growth and competitiveness. However, the industry faces various challenges related to social, environmental, political, economic, technological and legal factors.

2.16.1 PESTEL Analysis

The PESTEL model, which is an analytical framework that examines external factors impacting an industry or business. PESTEL stands for Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal factors. By incorporating the PESTEL model, the below section provides a more in-depth understanding of the macro-environmental factors influencing the leather industry in India.

2.16.1.1 Political Factors

The Indian government has played an essential role in supporting the leather industry through various policies, initiatives, and institutions. The government has focused on developing infrastructure, promoting exports, and encouraging skill development within the sector (Das and Das, 2011).

2.16.1.2 Economic Factors

The leather industry is an important contributor to the Indian economy, generating employment for millions of people and earning valuable foreign exchange through exports. However, fluctuations in global economic conditions and competition from other low-cost producing countries may impact the industry's growth (Das, 2017).

2.16.1.3 Social Factors

The leather industry is a significant source of employment in India, particularly in rural areas. However, the industry has faced criticism regarding working conditions, labor rights, and occupational health and safety, which may affect its social acceptability (Roy, 2012).

2.16.1.4 Technological Factors

Technological advancements have the potential to enhance the leather industry's productivity and competitiveness by improving production processes, reducing waste, and lowering environmental impacts. Adopting cleaner production technologies and sustainable practices is essential for the industry's long-term growth (Singh, 2018).

2.16.1.5 Environmental Factors

The leather industry faces significant environmental challenges, particularly regarding pollution and waste management, water consumption, and the use of hazardous chemicals. Addressing these issues through sustainable practices and cleaner production technologies is vital for the industry's environmental sustainability and reputation (Omoloso *et al.*, 2021).

2.16.1.6 Legal Factors

The leather industry is subject to various laws and regulations concerning labor rights, environmental protection, and trade. Compliance with these regulations is essential for the industry's growth and international competitiveness (Singh, 2018).

2.16.2 Porter's Competitive Analysis Model

Porter's Five Forces is a widely used framework for understanding the competitive forces that shape an industry (Porter, 1990). In this analysis, Porter's model is studied to evaluate the competitiveness of the leather industry in India, both domestically and on a global scale. The five forces include the threat of new entrants, the bargaining power of suppliers, the bargaining power of buyers, the threat of substitute products or services, and the intensity of competitive rivalry which are described below.

2.16.2.1 Threat of New Entrants

The threat of new entrants in the Indian leather industry is considered moderate, primarily due to several factors. Firstly, setting up tanneries and manufacturing facilities demands a high capital investment, acting as a barrier for potential newcomers. Additionally, the industry requires skilled labor and expertise in leather processing and manufacturing, posing a challenge for new entrants to acquire the necessary workforce (Singh, 2018). Strict environmental regulations and compliance requirements further add to the difficulty of entry (Omoloso *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, the presence of established domestic and global market players with strong brand recognition and distribution networks presents formidable competition for newcomers. Despite these challenges, government support and initiatives aimed at bolstering the leather industry, coupled with the potential for technological advancements, may eventually ease the barriers to entry in the future. As a result, while the current barriers are significant, the evolving landscape holds the potential for aspiring entrants to seize opportunities with appropriate support and innovation.

2.16.2.2 Bargaining Power of Suppliers

The bargaining power of suppliers in the Indian leather industry is generally low, influenced by several factors. Firstly, India benefits from an abundance of raw materials, such as hides and skins, due to the country's substantial livestock population (IBEF, 2023). This ample supply reduces dependency on individual suppliers. Secondly, the presence of numerous suppliers and tanneries in the industry further contributes to diminishing the bargaining power of any single supplier (CLE, 2022). Additionally, the availability of alternative

sourcing options, both domestically and internationally, provides flexibility and reduces the reliance on specific suppliers (Das, 2017). Despite these advantages, the bargaining power of suppliers could be impacted by fluctuations in raw material prices and the necessity to maintain quality standards (Rao et al., 2016). Hence, while suppliers currently hold relatively low bargaining power, industry players must remain attentive to market conditions to sustain this advantageous position.

2.16.2.3 Bargaining Power of Buyers

The bargaining power of buyers in the Indian leather industry is notably high, influenced by several key factors. Firstly, buyers have the advantage of a wide range of leather products available from various manufacturers and countries, providing them with ample choices and alternatives. Additionally, consumers in domestic markets are particularly price-sensitive, creating a climate of heightened price-based competition among suppliers. Moreover, with the advent of the digital age, buyers have easy access to information and transparency, enabling them to compare products and prices effortlessly. This increased access to information empowers buyers to make well-informed decisions and negotiate for favorable terms. As a result, the industry must be responsive to the preferences and demands of buyers, fostering innovation, competitive pricing, and superior product offerings to maintain a strong position in the market (Das, 2017) .

2.16.2.4 Threat of Substitute Products or Services

The threat of substitutes in the Indian leather industry is considered moderate, arising primarily from several key factors. Firstly, there is a growing demand for synthetic and alternative materials, such as vegan leather, driven by environmental and ethical considerations. This trend has led to an increased interest in sustainable and cruelty-free alternatives to traditional leather. Secondly, advancements in textile technologies have resulted in the development of new materials that possess similar properties to leather but are offered at lower prices, enticing consumers with more affordable options. Lastly, evolving consumer preferences and fashion trends have the potential to steer buyers away from leather products in favor of other materials that align with changing tastes (CLE, 2022). To mitigate this threat, the leather industry must proactively address sustainability

concerns, invest in research and innovation, and continuously adapt to evolving consumer preferences, positioning itself as a viable and attractive choice in an ever-changing market landscape.

2.16.2.5 Intensity of Competitive Rivalry

The competitive rivalry within the Indian leather industry is characterized by intensity, arising from several key factors. Firstly, the industry possesses a multitude of both domestic and international players competing for market share, intensifying competition in both the domestic and global markets (Mishra and Pal, 2015). Moreover, price-based competition is particularly fierce in lower-value segments of the market, as companies strive to capture cost-conscious consumers. Additionally, rapid advancements in technology and production processes contribute to heightened innovation and competition, as players seek to stay ahead by embracing cutting-edge techniques. To thrive in this challenging environment, companies must focus on differentiation, quality, and continuous improvement to distinguish themselves from competitors and secure a strong position in the market. By leveraging innovation and meeting consumer demands effectively, businesses can navigate the competitive landscape and foster growth in the dynamic Indian leather industry.

Applying Porter's Five Forces model to the Indian leather industry reveals a moderate level of competitiveness within the industry, both domestically and on a global scale (Porter, 1990). While there are barriers to entry and low supplier bargaining power, the industry faces intense competitive rivalry, high buyer bargaining power, and a moderate threat from substitute products. To remain competitive, Indian leather companies must focus on innovation, sustainability, and differentiation in product offerings, while also addressing environmental and social concerns to cater to the evolving preferences of consumers.

2.16.3 SWOT Analysis of the Leather Industry in India

A SWOT analysis is a strategic tool used to identify an organization or industry's internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats (Dealtry, 1992). In this analysis, the SWOT analysis is applied to evaluate the competitiveness of the leather

industry in India, both domestically and on a global scale. This analysis will enable a more comprehensive understanding of the industry's competitive landscape.

2.16.3.1 Strengths

The Indian leather industry benefits from several key strengths that have contributed to its prominence and success. Firstly, the country enjoys abundant raw material availability, due to its substantial livestock population, ensuring a steady supply of hides and skins for the industry. Additionally, India possesses a skilled labor force proficient in leather processing and manufacturing, providing a competitive advantage in the production of high-quality leather goods (Singh, 2018). Moreover, the Indian government actively supports the industry through various schemes and initiatives, such as the Indian Leather Development Programme, bolstering its growth and development. Furthermore, the industry's export-oriented nature has positioned India as one of the leading global exporters of leather and leather products, contributing significantly to the country's foreign exchange earnings (Das, 2017). The combination of these strengths has solidified India's position as a key player in the global leather market and underscores the industry's potential for continued growth and success in the future.

2.16.3.2 Weaknesses

Despite its strengths, the Indian leather industry also faces significant weaknesses that pose challenges to its growth and competitiveness. Firstly, environmental concerns loom large as the industry grapples with pollution and waste management issues, leading to stringent environmental regulations and compliance requirements (Omoloso *et al.*, 2021). Secondly, the industry's fragmented structure, comprising mainly of small and medium enterprises, limits the realization of economies of scale and diminishes its overall competitiveness (Singh, 2018). Moreover, the sector suffers from inadequate infrastructure, including insufficient tanneries and processing facilities, impeding its potential for expansion (Das, 2017). Lastly, a deficiency in investment in research and development and innovation hinders the industry's capacity to create high-value products and compete effectively in the global market (Mazurek, 2013). Addressing these weaknesses is vital for the sustainable growth of the Indian leather industry, necessitating a concerted effort towards improving

environmental practices, encouraging consolidation and modernization, enhancing infrastructure, and fostering a culture of innovation and R&D investment within the sector. By addressing these challenges, the industry can strengthen its competitiveness and secure a more sustainable and prosperous future (Gupta *et al.*, 2018).

2.16.3.3 Opportunities

The Indian leather industry holds promising opportunities that can pave the way for growth and success. Firstly, the industry can capitalize on the growing demand for leather products, driven by increasing disposable incomes and a burgeoning middle class, both locally and globally. Products like footwear, accessories, and garments are in high demand, offering a potential for expanding market reach and sales (Das, 2017). Moreover, the focus on sustainable and eco-friendly practices presents an opportunity for the industry to embrace cleaner technologies and production processes, meeting the rising consumer demand for environmentally conscious products (Gupta *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, the rapid growth of e-commerce provides a platform for the Indian leather industry to extend its reach to a wider customer base and boost sales through online channels (Chakraborty and Chakraborty, 2007). Lastly, diversifying into niche markets, such as luxury products, specialty footwear, and automotive upholstery, can empower Indian leather companies to enhance their competitiveness and profit margins (CLE, 2022). By embracing these opportunities and adapting to evolving market trends, the Indian leather industry can position itself for sustainable growth and continued success in the dynamic global market.

2.16.3.4 Threats

The Indian leather industry faces several critical threats that require careful consideration for its sustained growth. Firstly, competition from synthetic and alternative materials, like vegan leather, poses a significant challenge to the demand for traditional leather products. Moreover, the industry faces fierce international competition from leather-producing giants like China, Italy, and Brazil, potentially impacting its market share and overall profitability (Das, 2017). Fluctuations in the prices of raw materials, particularly hides and skins, further compound challenges for the industry, influencing cost structures and profitability (CLE, 2022). Lastly, with growing environmental concerns, the leather sector may encounter more

stringent regulations and compliance requirements, potentially raising production costs and affecting competitiveness (Chakraborty and Chakraborty, 2007). To overcome these threats, the Indian leather industry must explore innovative ways to stay ahead of the competition, focus on sustainability and efficiency, establish strategic partnerships, and maintain vigilance in navigating evolving regulatory landscapes. By effectively addressing these threats, the industry can strengthen its resilience and secure a more prosperous future amidst a dynamic and competitive global market (Das, 2017).

2.16.4 Value Chain Analysis of the Leather Industry in India

Value chain analysis is a strategic tool that evaluates the activities within an organization or industry to identify areas where value is added or can be enhanced. In this analysis, the value chain framework is applied to evaluate the competitiveness of the leather industry in India, both domestically and on a global scale. By analyzing the value chain of the Indian leather industry, the areas can be identified where value is added or can be enhanced to improve its competitiveness both domestically and on a global scale. Emphasis on sustainable practices, investment in R&D and innovation, and leveraging e-commerce opportunities can contribute to a more competitive and successful leather industry in India. This value chain analysis will enable a more comprehensive understanding of the industry's competitive landscape (Savino, Manzini and Mazza, 2015).

2.16.4.1 Raw Material Procurement

The first aspect to consider in the analysis is the raw material procurement stage. India benefits from an abundant supply of raw materials, courtesy of its vast livestock population, ensuring a consistent availability of hides and skins for leather production (Expo, 2023). However, the industry encounters challenge due to price fluctuations in these raw materials, which can exert pressure on the cost structure and overall profitability of leather businesses. Understanding these nuances in raw material procurement will facilitate better decision-making, enabling the industry to optimize resource utilization, manage costs effectively, and maintain a competitive edge in the market.

2.16.4.2 Tanning and Processing

The tanning and processing stage is a critical aspect of the leather industry value chain, and several factors play a vital role in this phase. India's advantage lies in its access to a skilled labor force, proficient in leather processing techniques (Singh, 2018). However, environmental concerns pose a significant challenge in this stage, as tanning and processing activities are often associated with pollution and waste management issues, prompting the imposition of stringent environmental regulations (Gupta *et al.*, 2018). To navigate these challenges successfully, the industry can seize the opportunity to adopt sustainable and eco-friendly practices, embracing cleaner technologies and production processes that not only reduce the environmental impact but also enhance the industry's overall competitiveness (Chakraborty and Chakraborty, 2007). By prioritizing sustainable practices and balancing environmental responsibilities with business objectives, the leather industry can pave the way for a more sustainable and successful future in the global market.

2.16.4.3 Manufacturing

The manufacturing phase is a pivotal stage in the leather industry's value chain, and several key factors impact its success. One such factor is the fragmented industry structure in India, marked by numerous small and medium enterprises. While this diversity fosters variety, it may also limit economies of scale and diminish overall competitiveness (Hashim, Murthy and Roy, 2010). Moreover, the industry grapples with the challenge of inadequate investment in research and development and innovation, hindering its capacity to create high-value products that can stand out in the market (Thiripurasundari and Ponsakthisurya, 2018). Addressing these issues requires strategic collaboration and collective efforts to foster innovation, stimulate investment in R&D, and promote synergies within the industry. By embracing a collaborative approach, the Indian leather manufacturing sector can unlock new opportunities for growth, foster creativity, and solidify its position as a strong contender in the global marketplace.

2.16.4.4 Marketing and Distribution

The marketing and distribution phase is a crucial element of the leather industry's value chain, and two key factors play a prominent role in this stage. First, India's leather industry has established itself as an export-oriented sector, making a substantial contribution to the country's foreign exchange earnings (Das, 2017). This export-oriented approach opens doors to global markets, allowing the industry to tap into diverse international consumer bases and expand its reach. Secondly, the rapid growth of e-commerce presents a valuable opportunity for the Indian leather industry to further its market penetration and boost sales. The online platform offers a convenient avenue to access a broader customer base, facilitating seamless transactions and supporting the industry's market presence. By capitalizing on its export focus and harnessing the power of e-commerce, the Indian leather industry can solidify its position as a competitive force in the global market, while nurturing a strong domestic presence to cater to the growing demand within the country.

2.16.4.5 Retail and Sales

The retail and sales phase are a critical aspect of the leather industry's value chain, and it is influenced by two key factors. First, the industry benefits from the growing domestic and global demand for leather products, driven by rising disposable incomes and an expanding middle class (Das, 2017). This surge in demand presents a promising opportunity for the industry to cater to a diverse and ever-increasing consumer base. However, the second factor poses a challenge to the industry's traditional dominance. The increasing popularity of synthetic and alternative materials, like vegan leather, has emerged as a potential threat to the demand for traditional leather products (Research, 2023). To thrive amidst this competition, the leather industry must focus on innovation, customer engagement, and consumer education to highlight the unique qualities and benefits of genuine leather products. By proactively addressing consumer preferences and promoting sustainable practices, the industry can cement its position as a sought-after choice for discerning customers, both within India and in the global market.

2.16.4.6 After-Sales Services

In the dynamic landscape of the Indian leather industry, after-sales services play a pivotal role in fostering customer satisfaction and brand loyalty. These services encompass a range of activities aimed at ensuring a positive post-purchase experience for customers. Warranty and repair services instill confidence in the product's quality, assuring customers of its durability. Efficient customer support addresses queries and concerns promptly, leaving a lasting impression on the brand's reputation. Equipping customers with proper care and maintenance guidance extends the lifespan and appeal of leather products. Flexible exchange and return policies build trust and provide peace of mind to customers. Offering personalized options and loyalty programs create a sense of exclusivity and appreciation, encouraging repeat purchases. In the fiercely competitive Indian leather cluster, businesses that excel in after-sales services distinguish themselves and foster positive word-of-mouth referrals, vital for long-term growth. By prioritizing customer satisfaction, companies can build a loyal customer base and establish themselves as trustworthy and esteemed brands within the industry.

2.16.5 Macro Environmental Impact of the Leather Industry in India: Insights from Other Researchers

The macro-environmental impact of the Indian leather industry is vast, encompassing economic, social, and environmental aspects. Understanding these impacts is vital for informed policymaking, industry practices, and future research to foster the sustainable development of India's leather industry.

2.16.5.1 Economic Impact

One of the key economic impacts lies in its role as a significant generator of employment, particularly in rural areas. Studies conducted in other countries, such as Turkey and Brazil, have also explored the employment contribution of their respective leather industries using both quantitative and qualitative methodologies (Blessing, 2017; Omoloso *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, the Indian leather industry plays a crucial role in contributing to the country's GDP, both through exports and domestic sales (Das, 2017). Similar research conducted in

the context of the Chinese leather industry utilized input-output analysis to quantify its economic impact on China's GDP (Liu *et al.*, 2021).

2.16.5.2 Social Impact

The social impact of the Indian leather industry is a complex and critical aspect to consider. One of the significant concerns is the working conditions of the industry's workforce, with potential risks to their health and safety arising from exposure to harmful chemicals and pollutants (Arunkumar Yogaraj and Ravi, 2017). In-depth research conducted in Bangladesh utilized ethnographic methods and interviews to delve into the social implications of the leather industry on the well-being and health of its workers (Arunkumar Yogaraj and Ravi, 2017). Addressing these social issues is crucial for fostering a sustainable and ethical leather industry in India. Improving working conditions, ensuring the welfare of workers, and implementing health and safety measures are essential steps towards creating a socially responsible industry that supports the well-being and dignity of its workforce.

2.16.5.3 Environmental Impact

Efficient pollution control and waste management are vital areas of concern for the Indian leather industry, particularly during the tanning and processing stages (Hansen, de Aquim and Gutterres, 2021). Several researchers have applied life cycle assessment (LCA) methodologies in countries like Italy and Spain to thoroughly evaluate the environmental impact of the leather industry and identify potential avenues for improving waste management and pollution control practices (Rossi *et al.*, 2021). Emphasizing the adoption of sustainable practices is crucial in mitigating the industry's environmental impact and enhancing its competitiveness (Hansen, de Aquim and Gutterres, 2021). Research carried out in Brazil employed case study methods to analyze how sustainable practices have been integrated into the leather industry and the positive environmental outcomes resulting from such initiatives (Omoloso *et al.*, 2021). Implementing environmentally friendly technologies and production processes will not only help reduce the industry's ecological footprint but also foster a more environmentally conscious and resilient leather industry in India.

2.16.5.4 Legal and Regulatory Impact

Adhering to international quality and environmental standards is vital for the Indian leather industry to maintain its competitiveness. Researchers investigating the Vietnamese leather industry employed qualitative research methods, such as document analysis and interviews, to gain insights into the industry's compliance with international standards and the associated challenges (Markets, 2022). Government policies and initiatives play a pivotal role in shaping the development of the Indian leather industry (Das, 2017). Studies focused on the Chinese leather industry have utilized a policy analysis approach to evaluate the effectiveness of government interventions in fostering the industry's growth (Zou, Duan and Jin, 2022). Understanding the legal and regulatory impact is essential for the Indian leather industry to navigate the complexities of compliance and take advantage of supportive government policies, leading to sustained growth and competitive advantage in the global market.

2.17 Role of Indian Government in developing Industry clusters in India

While many clusters have existed for a long time and have shown to be more effective than efforts outside of clusters, cluster-based MSME development in India is just a few decades old. The government of India has made extraordinary arrangements and provided special assistance to establish an MSME division in the country. Cluster development in India from the late 1980s to the late 1990s was based on specific topical areas and was initiated by financial institutions such as the SIDBI, State Bank of India, and the then Ministry of SSI, and was referred to as innovation programmes. In 1996, UNIDO launched a study which identified 138 clusters across the country.

The Abid Hussain Committee on Small Scale Industry, established by the former Ministry of Small-Scale Industry, was the first to recommend the cluster strategy for assisting small medium enterprises in its report in 1997. As a result, in a few Budget discussions, the emphasis was placed on choosing a cluster-based approach to increasing the profitability and intensity of small and medium businesses. Even after the Abid Hussain Committee's recommendations for the complete dereservation of items reserved for SSIs and a grand

total of Rs 5 billion in assistance to the sector, a piecemeal approach to the suggested changes meant that, while quantitative restrictions were removed allowing for more liberal imports, non-SSI units were still unable to produce the reserved items due to the continued reservation (Bhardwaj, 2002).

Using methodologies established in the literature on industrial districts and clusters, the study of (Kennedy, 2017) examines the organisation and performance of the Palar Valley tannery centres. The Indian government has taken a special interest in promoting the leather industry, which is seen as a sector in which India has a significant competitive advantage.

The Indian government has prioritised the promotion of culture in various sections of the country, consequently fostering traditional arts and enterprises. Traditional weavers of Kanchipuram, Tamil Nadu, have benefitted greatly from programmes such as the National Heritage City Development and Augmentation Yojana (Vijayalaxmi and Arathy, 2022).

On the 10th of August 2005, the Indian government announced a plan to make cluster development a priority in order to make Indian SMEs more competitive worldwide. The former Industrial Infrastructure Development (IID) plan was included in the new Small Industry Cluster Development Programme.

In the Budget speech of 2006-07 the then Finance Minister said that “The Cluster Development model can be usefully adopted not only to promote manufacturing but also to renew industrial towns and build new industrial townships. The model is now being implemented, in one form or the other, in nine sectors falling under different Ministries. The sectors include Khadi and village industries, handlooms, handicrafts, textiles, agricultural products and medicinal plants. It would be advantageous to empower a group to oversee cluster development and monitor progress. Hence, the Prime Minister had decided to constitute an Empowered Group of Ministers to lay down a policy for cluster development and oversee the implementation.”

From that point forward, an Empowered Group of Ministers (EGoM) was formed under the chairmanship of the External Affairs Minister to lay out a comprehensive plan for cluster advancement and to direct its implementation by various services of the government of India. Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, and other state governments have

embraced the cluster development method in their industrial policies in order to assist, build, and improve the efficiency of SMEs and make them more globally focused. The Ministry of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises has designated cluster development as one of its priority areas for the 11th Five Year Plan.

Several schemes and programmes have been developed by Central Ministries and Departments and their agencies, as well as state governments and their institutions, to execute the cluster development initiative. Some of the more notable schemes are described in detail here.

2.17.1 Micro, Small and Enterprises-Cluster Development Scheme

The former cluster development programme the Small Industries Cluster Development Programme (SICDP) was renamed the Micro and Small Enterprises Cluster Development Programme (MSE-CDP) in October 2007 (Mazurek, 2013). The previous project, known as Integrated Infrastructural Development (IID), was then absorbed into the new system.

Its objectives are as follows-

1. To promote the long-term viability and expansion of MSEs by addressing common concerns such as improved technology, skills and quality, market access, and access to funding.
2. To strengthen the capability of MSEs for collective action by forming self-help groups, consortia, and upgrading associations, among other things.
3. To establish and improve infrastructural facilities in new and current industrial clusters.
4. To establish a network of shared resource centres.

The system allows for both hard and soft interventions to be carried out under the following main headings:

1. Reports of diagnostic studies
2. Soft strategies as needed
3. Comprehensive executive summary
4. Centres for Hard Intervention/Common Facility (CFCs)

5. Development of infrastructure

6. Hard interventions (setting up of CFCs)

The strategy has been applied to a total of 463 clusters for intervention. Soft interventions were found in 223 clusters, whereas hard interventions were found in 50 clusters. Only one diagnostic study was carried out in the cases of 165 clusters.

2.17.2 Scheme for the Improvement of Industrial Infrastructure

In 2003, the Ministry of Commerce and Industry's Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion introduced the Industrial Infrastructural Up-gradation Scheme to improve industry competitiveness by providing excellent infrastructure through public-private partnerships with financial support up to 75% of the project cost subject to a cap of Rs.60 crores for each project. A Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV) would be established to carry out the programme, and it would be led by a private sector entrepreneur.

During the years 2003-07, a total of 25 projects were sanctioned at a cost of Rs.1766 crores, with a federal grant of Rs.952 crores. There are five projects in the auto components industry, five textiles projects, three chemicals projects, three foundry projects, two leather projects, and two rubber initiatives. Ten of the 25 projects have been completed with central funding of Rs.765 crores and contributions from SPVs, financial institutions, and state governments totalling Rs.63.45 crores.

Five projects totalling Rs. 270 crores were approved during the period of 2007 to 2010. A total of Rs. 58.5 crores was issued, with the SPV/FI/State Government contributing another Rs. 22.5 crores. The clusters involved are as follows:

- I. Chanderi Handloom
- II. Nashik Engineering
- III. Adityapur Auto Component
- IV. Chhindwara Industrial
- V. Jabalpur Garments

2.17.3 Babasaheb Ambedkar Hastashilp Vikas Yojana

In 2001-02, the Baba Saheb Ambedkar Hastashilp Vikas Yojana (BAHVY) was introduced. This scheme's major focus was a need-based approach to integrated the development of prospective handicrafts clusters. It assured the involvement of craftspeople at all levels of implementation, with the ultimate goal of empowering them and thereby ensuring their long-term viability. The project envisioned a package of assistance for a cluster of handicrafts artists that comprises, among other things, basic inputs and infrastructure support, as well as capacity augmentation to cater to target markets (Das *et al.*, 2007). The scheme includes five different sorts of interventions which are detailed below:

- A. Social intervention
- B. Technological intervention
- C. Marketing intervention
- D. Financial intervention
- E. Infrastructure

2.17.4 Integrated Handlooms Development Scheme (IHDS)

Since November 2007, the Integrated Handlooms Development Scheme was implemented by the Development Commissioner for Handlooms at the Ministry of Textiles. This scheme merged four previous schemes, namely the Deen Dayal Hathkargha Protsahan Yojana (DDHPY), the Integrated Handloom Training Project (IHTP), the Integrated Handloom Cluster Development Scheme (IHCDS), and the Work-Shed-cum-Housing Scheme. During the Eleventh Five-Year Plan, 625 clusters were intended to be involved.

2.17.5 Scheme Fund for Regeneration of Traditional Industrial (SFURTI)

The Central Government announced the establishment of a fund for traditional industry regeneration, with an initial investment of Rs. 100 crores and the goal of making traditional industries more productive and competitive, as well as aiding their long-term growth. A central sector scheme entitled the Scheme of the Fund for the Regeneration of Traditional Industries (SFURTI) was designed and authorised as a result of this announcement, at a

total cost of Rs. 97.25 crore. The Union Ministry of Agro and Rural Industries (ARI) and its organisations and institutions were to execute the scheme in conjunction with state governments and their organisations, non-governmental organisations and others. In 2005, the Scheme was introduced by the Ministry of Agro and Rural Industries, which is now the Ministry of MSME (Das, 2017).

The average expenditure per cluster under the scheme is Rs.10 lakhs. The aid is supplied up to 75% of the time, with the recipients contributing 25%. A total of 105 clusters have received assistance, and the total amount released under the plan is expected to be around Rs. 83 crores. The project has resulted in the training of 21,933 craftsmen and 9450 new modal charkhas have been provided. There have been 1139 SHGs founded, with 9579 tool kits and 1025 new looms distributed. The plan that resulted in 2401 craftspeople, and 73 CFCs have also been established.

As a result of the previously stated five key cluster development projects, an estimated 1413 clusters have received assistance, with an estimated expenditure of Rs. 1,328 crores.

2.18 Indian Government Initiatives for Leather Industry

The major obstacles to the healthy development of the leather industry include poor animal management, low offtake and recovery rates, and a lack of high-quality raw materials. Skills, technology, intermediate inputs, and processing equipment are all lacking. Existing tanners face stiff competition, with low capacity utilisation in the industry, and inadequate or non-existent policies for the growth of the sector.

2.18.1 Government Initiatives

Support from the Integrated Development of Leather Sector (IDLS) is provided for the technical upgrading and modernisation of leather plants in the form of investment grants at a rate of 30% to small and micro-units and 20% to other units via nationalised banks, with a maximum assistance of Rs.2 crore for each product line.

The Mega Leather Cluster scheme is intended to provide infrastructural assistance to the leather industry through the construction of Mega Leather Clusters. Each of these requires

a minimum of 25 acres without tanneries and 40 acres with tanneries to be set up. Under the plan, the government of India would contribute up to 50% of the project costs, excluding the cost of land, with a maximum aid of Rs. 125 crores.

In terms of leather technology, innovation and environmental issues, the cost of upgrading or installing Common Effluent Treatment Plants (CETPs) is covered by 50% of project costs. Pilot projects for technology benchmarking for leather units, conducting environment-related workshops, and solid waste management pilot projects are all eligible for funding under the initiative.

2.18.2 Application of Various Duty-Free Import Scheme (DFIS)

There are 3% DFIS grants for exporters of leather garments with a list of qualifying inputs or embellishments notified for import, eligibility requirements, and operative rules, including the production of an Export Performance Certificate and an Import Certificate, as well as payment of service costs for the DFIS.

A DFIS grant of 5% is available for manufacturers and exporters of leather footwear or synthetic footwear and leather products, with separate lists of eligible inputs and embellishments for import for production segments such as leather goods, footwear, footwear components, leather gloves, and saddlery and harness items, while eligibility conditions and operative guidelines include the issue of Export Performance and Import Certificates and payment of service charges for DFIS (Roy, 2012).

Individual exporters are eligible for assistance under the Marketing Development Assistance Scheme for export promotion efforts overseas, such as participation in Export Promotion Councils (EPC)-led BSMs and trade fairs and exhibitions.

2.19 Conclusion

This chapter covered the history and evolution of leather and leather goods and concludes that there are many products of leather goods available throughout the world. The immense use of leather products has given rise to the formation of leather industries in different geographical areas of India. There are huge leather clusters in various different regions of

the country, with the largest found in West Bengal, Tamil Nadu, and Uttar. The evolution and formation of the Kolkata leather cluster were also discussed in this chapter. An overview of cluster theory in relation to several Indian cities was also covered in this chapter.

Chapter Three: Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

To conduct a complete study of the leather industry, a well-structured research approach that incorporates a variety of philosophical underpinnings is necessary. The use of Saunder's research onion as a guide ensures a systematic approach to the study, considering different research philosophies, approaches, strategies, choices, time horizons, and data collection and analysis techniques (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

The current study attempts to fill the gap in regional studies available concerning leather clusters. There are macro studies and statistics available, but only a few addresses the problems and prospects of regional clusters, and the Kolkata cluster is still unexplored in terms of the problems faced by units. This study aims to analyse data from published reports and articles, units, and employees. While the existing literature has examined various aspects of the Indian leather industry, including its historical background, economic contribution, and environmental challenges, there is a noticeable research gap when it comes to the cluster-based development approach, specifically focusing on the case study of Kolkata. There remains a research gap in understanding the differential impact of key factors such as financial support (FS), government policy support (GPS), government programmes (GP), research and development (R&D), commercial legal infrastructure (CLI), internal market openness (IMO), and access to physical infrastructure (PI). It is observed from the case study of Kolkata and literature review chapter that these factors play crucial roles in the growth and development of leather clusters and units in Kolkata. These factors are important for the cluster development in Kolkata's leather industry because they collectively create an enabling environment that promotes investment, innovation, market access, and sustainability. These factors can enhance the competitiveness of leather units, attract domestic and foreign buyers, and contribute to the overall growth and development of the leather clusters in Kolkata. The following sections explain these factors and their role in cluster development as part of research gap. The key factors contributing to the growth and development of clusters are as follows:

3.1.1 Financial Support (FS)

Financial support has been a critical driver in the growth of leather clusters. Access to capital allows businesses to invest in modern machinery, research and development, and skilled workforce training. It also enables them to adopt environmentally friendly technologies and improve production efficiency. Financial support also includes the availability of funds, investment opportunities, and access to credit for businesses within the cluster. The research gap exists in understanding how financial support mechanisms vary across different clusters and how they contribute to the growth and competitiveness of cluster firms in Kolkata.

3.1.2 Government Policy Support (GPS)

Government policies can play a crucial role in fostering cluster development by creating a favorable environment for businesses. Supportive policies can encourage investment, stimulate innovation, and ensure a level playing field for businesses. The government policies are enabled to assess the impact of various policies, such as tax incentives, export promotion measures, and initiatives to improve ease of doing business. Supportive policies and regulations can drive the adoption of cleaner production technologies, promoting energy efficiency and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Additionally, government initiatives for responsible land use and reforestation can minimize the environmental impacts of raw material sourcing, such as deforestation and habitat destruction. The research gap lies in examining the specific policy measures that are most effective in promoting cluster growth and how these policies interact with other factors to influence cluster development.

3.1.3 Government Programmes (GP)

Government programmes refer to initiatives and projects designed to support the development of clusters, such as infrastructure development, skills training, and R&D funding. Government support, beyond just policies, involves active engagement and assistance from local and national authorities. Understanding the extent and effectiveness of government support in terms of capacity-building programs, skill development

initiatives, and market access facilitation are crucial for identifying areas of improvement. Moreover, government support and funding are instrumental in addressing environmental pollution and water waste management within the Kolkata leather cluster. By providing financial incentives and investing in infrastructure for effluent treatment plants, solid waste disposal facilities, and air pollution control equipment, the government can help mitigate the cluster's environmental impact. The research gap involves investigating the effectiveness of these programmes in fostering cluster growth and their role in addressing challenges faced by clusters.

3.1.4 Research and Development (R&D)

Research and development (R&D) are crucial for the leather industry's competitiveness and growth. R&D initiatives can lead to the development of new products and units, improved processes, and sustainable practices within the cluster. Through research, new and innovative techniques can be discovered, leading to improved product designs, materials, and manufacturing processes. Evaluating the R&D activities within the Kolkata leather cluster will shed light on its innovation capabilities and potential for future advancements. The research gap exists in understanding the role of R&D in cluster development, including the interactions between R&D institutions, businesses, and other stakeholders, as well as the impact of R&D investment on cluster performance.

3.1.5 Commercial Legal Infrastructure (CLI)

Commercialization efforts and legal services also play a crucial role in the cluster's development. This factor is essential for smooth business operations. Also, it encompasses the legal and regulatory frameworks that govern business activities within a cluster. Efficient transportation networks, robust logistics, and supportive legal frameworks are crucial for the growth of leather units in Kolkata. By commercializing products effectively, units can access larger markets and attract more customers, ultimately contributing to the cluster's growth. Legal services help protect intellectual property rights, ensuring that innovations and unique designs are safeguarded from unauthorized use, which fosters an environment of innovation and encourages investment in product development. The research gap lies in exploring how much this factor affect cluster development in Kolkata, including

their role in facilitating or hindering collaboration, innovation, and competition among cluster firms.

3.1.6 Internal Market Openness (IMO)

Internal market openness refers to the ease of access to markets, both local and international, for cluster firms. It is facilitated by the cluster's proximity to diverse consumer bases, encourages units to tailor their products to meet specific market demands, increasing their competitiveness both domestically and internationally. The internal market openness refers to the ease with which local businesses can access raw materials, machinery, and other essential inputs. By leveraging research and market insights, units can continuously innovate and adapt, ensuring their long-term growth and success in the leather industry. Understanding the level of internal market openness in the cluster will help identify bottlenecks or constraints that may hinder its growth. The research gap involves examining how market openness influences the growth and competitiveness of clusters, as well as the strategies adopted by cluster firms to navigate market challenges and seize opportunities.

3.1.7 Physical Infrastructure (PI)

Physical infrastructure includes transportation, utilities, specialized zones, tannery clusters and communication systems that support the functioning of a cluster. Investigating the availability and adequacy of physical infrastructure in Kolkata will provide insights into the cluster's overall development. The research gap lies in understanding the role of physical infrastructure in cluster development and its impact on the efficiency, connectivity, and competitiveness of cluster firms.

Limited research has been conducted to explore the dynamic interplay of factors, such as FS, GPS, GP, R&D, CLI, IMO, and PI, in the process of cluster formation. By combining these factors and analyzing their interplay, the research aims to portrait a comprehensive picture of the Kolkata leather cluster's development. This gap includes the investigation of the interaction and relative importance of these factors in determining the success and sustainability of clusters across different products and units. This knowledge will

ultimately contribute to the formulation of effective policies and strategies to promote the formation and growth of competitive and sustainable clusters. This holistic understanding will help identify strengths to build upon and weaknesses to address, enabling policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers to work collaboratively in enhancing the cluster's competitiveness, sustainability, and contribution to India's economy.

3.2 Research Hypothesis

1. Clusters foster the growth of units in multiple respects equally
2. Clusters foster the growth of multiple products equitably
3. Cluster supports equally units of different scales

The three hypotheses in the study investigate the role of clusters in fostering the growth of units, promoting multiple products, and supporting units of different scales. The policy implications of these hypotheses can have significant impacts on the leather industry in India, particularly on small and large units within the clusters which are discussed as below.

3.2.1 Policy Implications of Research Hypothesis

3.2.1.1 Clusters fostering the growth of units in multiple respects equally.

If the hypothesis is proven true, it would mean that clusters provide equal opportunities and benefits to all the units, regardless of their size or product focus. The policy implication would be to encourage the formation of clusters and provide support to ensure that all units can take advantage of the resources, networks, and knowledge available within the cluster.

3.2.1.2 Clusters fostering the growth of multiple products equitably.

If this hypothesis holds, it will indicate that clusters support the development and growth of a diverse range of products within the leather industry. The policy implication would be to promote product diversification within clusters, which can enhance the overall competitiveness and resilience of the industry. This can be achieved through targeted support, such as training programs, R&D funding, and market access initiatives.

3.2.1.3 Clusters supporting equally units of different scales.

The policy implications of this hypothesis would depend on whether the results show equal support for units of different scales or favouritism towards larger units. If larger units receive more advantages, it may be necessary to implement policies that specifically target smaller units, ensuring they also benefit from the cluster's resources and networks. This can include providing financial assistance, training, and mentorship programs to help smaller units overcome the barriers they face.

Regarding the exploration of export contracts and the relationship between large and small units, it would be interesting to investigate whether larger firms indeed receive more contracts due to their ability to make upfront investments and outsource jobs to smaller units. If this is the case, policy interventions could aim to facilitate collaboration between large and small units, ensuring that smaller units can also access export opportunities. This can be achieved through the creation of platforms for networking, sharing knowledge, and pooling resources, as well as by offering incentives for larger units to collaborate with smaller ones.

3.3 Research Philosophy

The realm of research encompasses various paradigms, with quantitative and qualitative being the two main approaches. The quantitative paradigm, rooted in positivism, believes in a single independent reality, while the qualitative paradigm, grounded in interpretivism, acknowledges the existence of multiple contextual realities (Bhatta, 2018). These philosophical assumptions influence the nature of research, including case study research.

Given that the philosophical position shapes the ontological and epistemological characteristics of a study, it becomes crucial in research design process. The fundamental philosophical orientations that influence research endeavors are positivism or quantitative methodology and non-positivism, known as constructivist and interpretivist paradigms (Bhatta, 2018).

Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019) introduced the concept of the "research onion," as shown in Figure 3-1, a comprehensive framework that guides researchers through the

various layers of decision-making in the research process. The research onion consists of three distinct levels, each building upon the other to form a cohesive and well-structured research approach. At the outermost level, the first two rings encompass the research philosophy and research approach, laying the foundation for the overall study. Moving inward, the second level focuses on the research design, encompassing methodological choices, research strategy, and time horizon, which collectively shape the overall structure and methodology of the study. Finally, at the core of the research onion lies the tactics, representing the innermost aspect of the research process, where data collection and analysis techniques are employed to derive meaningful insights and draw conclusions (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

In this study, the quantitative aspects of the leather industry will be examined from a positivist perspective. Additionally, an interpretivist approach will be adopted to explore the qualitative dimensions of the leather industry, including the perspectives of entrepreneurs.

Figure 3- 1 Research Onion Source: (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019)

The Saunder’s philosophy approach will facilitate a profound understanding of the Kolkata cluster’s context and the diverse viewpoints of entrepreneurs involved. By incorporating

both perspectives, this research aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the leather cluster's growth and development factors.

3.4 Research Approach

Inductive approaches are commonly employed in qualitative research, focusing on building theories and understanding phenomena based on observed patterns and data. In contrast, quantitative research often follows a deductive approach, rooted in positivist philosophy, which starts with established theories and hypotheses to test and validate through data analysis. The use of a deductive approach in quantitative research is well-suited as it begins with a clear theoretical framework, allowing researchers to systematically test hypotheses and draw objective conclusions from the data. By employing this deductive approach, quantitative research can effectively contribute to the advancement of knowledge and the validation of existing theories in a structured and systematic manner.

To examine current theories and hypotheses regarding the leather business, a deductive approach will be utilized, drawing on prior literature and empirical information to inform the study. Additionally, an inductive technique will be used to produce new insights and ideas based on the collected data from the qualitative research, enabling the identification of previously unknown patterns and relationships in the leather industry.

3.5 Research Methodological Choices

A mixed-method approach will be used for research questions that necessitate the integration of quantitative and qualitative data to provide a comprehensive understanding of the Kolkata leather industry (Creswell and Poth, 2016). This approach will ensure that both objective and subjective aspects of the industry are considered, leading to more robust findings and conclusions.

3.6 Research Strategy

This research study predominantly involves the application of the case study method, which is suitable for this research based on its scope and objectives. The choice and selection of

an appropriate research method is dependent upon the nature of the research problem (Morgan and Smirch, 1980). Denzin and Lincoln (1995) mention that qualitative research implies an emphasis on examining and measuring quantities, amounts, intensity or frequency. However, in social science, researchers are interested in insights, discovery and interpretation rather than the testing of hypotheses (Merriam, 1988). In fact, over the years, it has been widely accepted that a case study can be both data-rich as well as exciting for researchers. This research study combines different techniques for gathering data with the core research method of the case study approach.

There are several benefits of employing case studies as a research tool. Firstly, the evaluation of the data is most typically undertaken within the context and backdrop of its usage (Yin, 1994); that is, inside the scenario in which the activity takes place. One of the primary motivations for using a case study is to contrast it with an experiment or any other qualitative research study that deliberately separates a research phenomenon from its environment and concentrates on a small number of factors (Zainal, 2007).

There are many variations of the case study method; in terms of intrinsic, instrumental and collective approaches, and both quantitative and qualitative analyses of data can be conducted. Some longitudinal studies rely on qualitative data which give descriptive accounts of the phenomenon being researched. At the same time, many case studies seek evidence from both the numerical and categorical responses of individual subjects (Block, 1986).

It should be noted that (Yin, 1994) argues that researchers should not mix case studies with qualitative research, stating that “case studies might be based ... solely on quantitative evidence.” When obtaining a large sample population is impossible or not necessary for the research subject under consideration, case studies might be a viable alternative to traditional research methods. Although case studies as a research approach have several benefits in terms of a better understanding of real-life circumstances, they have also been questioned for the inability to extrapolate their findings.

Despite the numerous advantages of case studies as a research method, the case study method has been criticised due to its lack of robustness as a research instrument and

scientific methodology. This may, however, be overcome if adequate attention is paid to a case study's design. Depending on the scope of the research study and the topic in question, researchers might work with a single-case or multiple-case design. If no other examples are available for analysis, investigation, and replication, researchers will typically choose a single-case strategy. This method has various limitations. The main disadvantage of a single-case approach is that it cannot make a generalising conclusion. Exploring and capturing some of the study's features, on the other hand, is extremely beneficial. This issue can be solved in a variety of ways, one of which is to check the correctness of the technique by triangulating the research findings with other approaches.

As a result, proper case study design is a critical component of this research technique. One of the most difficult issues is demonstrating that the case study is the only feasible and relevant approach for producing and generating implicit and explicit data from respondents, as well as being the most relevant and appropriate way to answer the research question. Case study research can be made more robust by investigating the 'chain of evidence,' either quantitatively or qualitatively; documenting systematically; and, ultimately, the proper archiving and analysis of direct observation with ties to a theoretical framework (Tellis, 1997).

3.6.1 Case Study as Research Method

As a research approach, the case study has received widespread support as a strategic methodology. The term 'case', according to (Yin, 1994), refers to an event, entity, individual, or unit of analysis. The case study technique allows researchers to comprehend complicated real-life events actions and may include the utilisation of numerous sources of evidence which have been proven to be helpful for an in-depth examination of a topic of interest. It is proposed that case studies become particularly beneficial when researchers need to investigate, comprehend, and analyse a certain topic or scenario in significant length and detail, and when one may uncover instances rich in information (Patton, 1987).

Case study as a research method can be very useful in studying and capturing the emergent and immanent properties of life in organisations and the flow of its activities. According to (Yin, 1994) there are three types of case study research which are exploratory,

descriptive, and explanatory. Case study research has been used for different purposes. In the field of business management, an exploratory study can be used in a pilot study as the basis for further explorations of research questions and the devising of hypotheses. Descriptive case studies are used to describe a particular phenomenon, while explanatory studies are used to study the processes operating in companies. This research study makes use of descriptive and explanatory case study methods, including the gathering of documentary evidence from published sources in collecting information. The objective of the study has a great influence on the choice of the research method, and an in-depth explanation of the problem under study in this research requires a case study method.

Case study research, it has been concluded, centres on the findings of previous studies and aids in the investigation and comprehension of complex subjects. It has been deemed a reliable approach to research, especially when a comprehensive, in-depth inquiry is necessary (Zainal, 2007).

In many social science disciplines, the case study has been acknowledged as a significant tool. The function of the case study approach in research becomes more significant when studying and investigating topics related to education (Gülseçen and Kubat, 2006), sociology (Grässel and Schirmer, 2006), and community-based concerns (Johnson, 2010).

It is also worth noting that one of the primary reasons for the acceptance of case studies as a valid research method relates to the limitations of quantitative approaches in offering comprehensive and in-depth explanations of difficulties in research studies. Researchers have become more worried over the years about the obstacles and issues associated with quantitative research methodologies.

A researcher might go beyond quantitative statistical data by using a case study approach, according to (Tellis, 1997). The focus of research investigations might be to gain a better knowledge of behavioural conditions from the actor's point of view. Furthermore, because case study analysis can include quantitative and qualitative data, it can assist in providing explanations of both the process and consequence of a phenomena by observing, reconstructing, and analysing instances under inquiry.

The case study approach allows a researcher to explore data in depth within a specific context. A case study technique, in general, selects a particular region or a small number of persons as the topic of study. Case studies, in their true spirit and substance, aid in the exploration and investigation of current real-life phenomena through an extensive contextual examination of a small number of occurrences or situations, as well as their linkages. The case study research technique is defined by (Yin, 1994) as “an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context; when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident; and when multiple sources of evidence are used.”

There are several situations where an in-depth longitudinal investigation of a particular case or event is conducted for research purposes. Longitudinal case studies provide for a methodical approach to the observation of occurrences, collection of data, analysis of information, and reporting the findings. A case study is a one-of-a-kind method for the examination of any natural phenomena that may be found in a group of data (Yin, 1994). It should be emphasised that the distinctiveness of case study research stems from the fact that it examines a relatively limited geographic region or number of issues of interest in depth. In addition, unlike quantitative analysis which focuses on observing patterns in data at a macro level, for example based on the frequency of occurrence of the phenomena being studied, case study-based research investigations focus on data at the micro level.

A case study is a unique way of observing any natural phenomenon which is reflected in a set of data. A large number of past research studies into clusters are based on the case study method (Brown, 2000; Kiroff, 2017; Portnov, 2006; Sonobe and Otsuka, 2006; Waits, 2000; Wolman and Hincapie, 2015; Zhang, To and Cao, 2004). These research studies have focused on a particular geographical area; for instance, a region, a country or a city. They have analysed various industries in terms of the phenomenon of industry clusters using a cluster-based approach. The Kolkata leather industry has been chosen as the unit of analysis for the present research project in which the case study technique is used to investigate the cluster-based strategy used for the growth and development of the Kolkata leather industry, which is one of the aims of the research. This case study allows a detailed exploration of a particular case, such as the Kolkata leather cluster, providing rich insights and

understanding. The case study can involve a combination of qualitative and quantitative data collection methods, such as interviews, surveys, document analysis, observation, and data analysis. These methods will help to gather relevant information, capture diverse perspectives, and draw meaningful conclusions about the cluster's development and its various dimensions.

3.7 Time Horizon

A cross-sectional time horizon will be used to collect data at a specific point in time, allowing for the assessment of the current state of the leather industry and the identification of existing issues and opportunities. Certain components of the study will also address a longitudinal time horizon, such as the tracking of industry growth, regulatory changes, and the adoption of sustainable practises through time. This method will shed light on the evolution of the industry and the efficacy of interventions or policies. The Covid-19 outbreak has complicated the situation for data collection and affected the response rate. At the same time, it was necessary to ascertain the effect of the pandemic on the growth and existence of the cluster and member units.

3.8 Techniques and Procedures

3.8.1 Data Collection

To collect the data and information needed, a 3-dimensional approach was adopted, including:

1. A survey of the units
2. Interviews
3. Analysis of agency and government reports

3.8.1.1 Questionnaire Design

The use of a data collection tool such as a questionnaire or a form is often necessary for a strong research design to accomplish a successful study. The survey of units will be conducted through questionnaire. All of the questions required to collect the necessary data

should be included in the data collection tool. One of the most dangerous sources of non-sampling error is questionnaire bias. The study's outcome is also influenced by the mode of administration. The first risk is a mismatch between the information the researcher intends to collect and the information the respondents actually give. Furthermore, a poor questionnaire design may deter respondents from cooperating, resulting in a higher rate of non-responses or mistakes. Response problems such as inaccurate or inaccurately recorded answers can also be caused by poorly written questions.

In this study, the GEM (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor) study-based questionnaire is used as the basis to study various elements and aspects of the cluster. It is observed that various factors such as financial support, government policy support, government programmes, research and development, commercial and legal infrastructure, internal market openness, and access to physical infrastructure play a crucial role in the development of the Kolkata leather cluster industry. The study is deeply rooted in positivism, which emphasizes the importance of observable and verifiable facts. Using the GEM study-based questionnaire, the research aimed to collect data on these crucial factors and evaluate their impact on the cluster development. The questionnaire's structure, divided into two parts, allowed for the collection of essential information about the participating firms and their perspectives on the different factors contributing to the cluster's growth. The first part collects data for inception year, product and product category, number of employees, and total fixed capital in Indian Rupees. The second part has 33 questions related to 7 factors. The Likert scale was used as a measurement scale in this investigation. Because the study is focused on behavioural concerns, seven-point Likert measures in an interval scale were employed. Each scale item contains seven response categories, ranging from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree,' and respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement. The questionnaire is shown in Appendix 1 that presents a summary of the responses for each question.

The following major factors are included in the questionnaire.

1. Financial support
2. Government policy support

3. Government programmes
4. Research and development
5. Commercial and legal infrastructure
6. Internal market openness
7. Physical infrastructure

Furthermore, the careful design and administration of the questionnaire, following the suggestions of Sekaran and Bougie (2016), ensured that the data collected should be of high quality and relevant to the study's objectives. By taking into consideration the wording, language, and sequencing of questions, the research minimized potential biases and response errors, resulting in a more accurate and reliable dataset. Hence, the data collected through the questionnaire is directly linked to the literature review on the Kolkata leather cluster industry development by addressing the key factors identified in the literature and providing empirical evidence to support or challenge the existing knowledge.

Ethics also played a crucial role in the design and administration of the questionnaire. By ensuring the voluntary participation of respondents and carefully considering the wording, language, and sequencing of questions, the potential biases and response errors were minimized. Before the respondents filled out the questionnaire, they were given a brief introduction. The respondents were informed about the basic context of the research in the first section, followed by instructions for completion. Personal information not required for the study's purposes and was not collected as this could have had an impact on the respondents' ability and willingness to answer the questions. Steps were taken to verify the respondents' involvement in the leather industry, adhering to ethical obligation for truthfulness and transparency. Professional affiliations were cross-referenced and roles in the industry were verified through LinkedIn profiles or company websites. The summary statistics of the respondents detailing number of employees, inception year, fixed capital, products and units are provided in the Appendix 2 that help readers better understand the background of the respondents and assess the representativeness of the sample. The completed questionnaire by the respondents is also provided in Appendix 2.

3.8.1.2 Qualitative Data – Interview Questions

Interviews will be conducted to get primary data. This would enable the collection of firsthand information from industry players and the development of new insights. In order to gather valuable qualitative data, a set of five questions was developed for conducting interviews with entrepreneurs and managers of leather product manufacturing units within the Kolkata leather cluster. These questions were thoughtfully designed to explore a wide range of relevant topics and perspectives, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the cluster's dynamics, challenges, advancements, opportunities, competitiveness and growth drivers.

To collect the qualitative data, five questions were designed for the interviews with entrepreneurs and managers of leather product manufacturing units operating within the Kolkata cluster. These questions were thoughtfully designed to explore a wide range of topics and perspectives related to the entrepreneurs' journey, the developments in the leather industry, and the benefits of being part of the Kolkata leather cluster. The first question aimed to gather insights into the entrepreneurs' experiences, challenges, and successes as business owners. The second question focused on their observations regarding the changes and advancements in the leather industry, particularly how those changes impacted their specific firm. The third question delved into the benefits derived from being part of the leather cluster, such as access to government schemes and association initiatives that supported their business growth. The fourth question aimed to understand how the existence of the cluster influenced their company's development and how it shaped their business strategies. Lastly, the fifth question sought to explore the entrepreneurs' perception of how the leather cluster could further enhance their business competitiveness and what opportunities they saw for improvement within the cluster's ecosystem. By addressing these questions, this research will provide a comprehensive understanding of the entrepreneurs' experiences, the industry's progress, and the significant role of the Kolkata leather cluster in shaping their business operations and overall success. The combination of qualitative insights from these five questions will ensure a comprehensive exploration of the various factors influencing the growth and development of the leather

industry within the Kolkata cluster. The interview questions are shown in Appendix 3 that presents a summary of the responses for each question.

3.8.1.3 Analysis of Agency and Government Reports

In addition to conducting in-depth interviews with entrepreneurs and managers of leather product manufacturing units within the Kolkata cluster, the research will also incorporate valuable insights from secondary data sources. A thorough review of relevant literature, publications, databases, and official statistics will be undertaken to provide a comprehensive context and background information for the study.

3.8.1.4 Sample Size

The initial plan to conduct a survey of 200 units and personal in-depth interviews with 20 entrepreneurs was designed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the leather industry in Kolkata. Using a pragmatist approach - it aimed at understanding the practical implications and real-world experiences within the Kolkata leather industry. However, due to the unforeseen circumstances of the pandemic and lockdowns, the plan had to adapt to the changing environment, demonstrating the flexibility inherent in pragmatism approach. The reduction in the number of personal interviews to only 5 heads of units and the shift to remote data collection through Google Forms was a necessary adjustment to ensure the safety during the pandemic. Circulating 210 questionnaires through Google Forms allowed for the data collection process to continue in a remote manner, ensuring the safety of both researchers and participants. The final sample size of 74 responses, after screening for completeness and clarity, still provided a valuable set of data for the research, considering the challenging circumstances.

3.8.1.5 Sampling method

The study used a non-probability convenience sampling procedure. Convenience sampling works well for the purposes of region-specific research. It was stipulated that a respondent should be either an entrepreneur or the manager of a leather product manufacturing unit. Another point of caution was the respondent's linguistic competence, and so they should comprehend English sufficiently to be able to understand and interpret the form.

Furthermore, respondents who did not share an interest in taking part in the research were not included. The use of non-probability convenience sampling in this study aligns with a pragmatic philosophy. As the research is region-specific and faced constraints due to the pandemic, convenience sampling allowed us to collect data efficiently while ensuring the safety of all involved parties. The utilization of non-probability convenience sampling in this study is well-justified for several compelling reasons. First and foremost, the research is specifically centered on the Kolkata leather industry, making convenience sampling an ideal approach to target respondents who possess direct experience and knowledge of the local industry. Additionally, time and resource constraints make convenience sampling a practical choice, as it allows researchers to efficiently gather data from an accessible pool of respondents. Moreover, in the context of the pandemic and lockdown restrictions, convenience sampling proved valuable as it facilitated data collection without the need for face-to-face interactions, ensuring the safety of all involved parties. The requirement for respondents to possess adequate English language skills further strengthened the quality of data collected, as it enabled respondents to comprehensively understand and interpret the questionnaire. Furthermore, voluntary participation ensured that only interested respondents took part in the research, leading to more accurate and reliable data as respondents were more likely to provide thoughtful and comprehensive responses. Despite its limitations, such as potential selection bias and reduced generalizability, convenience sampling stands as the most pragmatic and efficient choice for this study, considering the unique challenges and constraints faced during the data collection process.

3.8.2 Data Analysis

The key to efficient and successful analysis of data is appropriate data preparation. The criteria suggested by (Mazzocchi, 2008) were used since this stage is extremely important once data gathering operations have been completed before the statistical analysis of the data acquired is conducted. Data preparation entailed converting data from the questionnaire form onto a data sheet, which enabled and facilitated further data processing, and the use of Google Form made this process simple.

The data sheet was constructed in Microsoft Excel and then uploaded to the Statistical Program for Social Sciences (SPSS) programme for further analysis. The questionnaire is used as an initial task in data preparation process, which was followed by editing, coding, and transcription (data input), data cleaning, and eventually treating the data for subsequent statistical analysis. For data entry and recording, each response was assigned a code, a transcribed data sheet was generated for data analysis, and tables were produced based on data.

Scores for the number of factors will be analyzed using principal component extraction via SPSS, offering empirically verifiable insights into the industry's current state and its significant contributing factors. The quantitative data will be subjected to appropriate data analysis tools such as ANOVA and regression. Additionally, the interview questions will undergo analysis using different tools. For instance, sentiment analysis will be conducted using the software application Nvivo, while word cloud analysis will be utilized to examine the frequency of terms used in the in-depth interviews. Moreover, word cloud analysis will also be applied to analyze the data collected from research papers, online sources, and government reports. To further enhance the qualitative analysis, quotations from respondents will be used to gain a deeper understanding of their perspectives. Through these comprehensive data analysis techniques, this research aims to provide valuable insights into the industry's current state and the factors influencing it.

3.8.3 Research authenticity, reliability, and robustness

To ensure the authenticity, reliability, and robustness of the research, a well-established and validated data collection tool, the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) study-based questionnaire, was chosen to gather data, guaranteeing the validity and reliability of the information collected. Secondly, utmost transparency was maintained by offering a clear and comprehensive description of the sampling strategy, data collection process, and data analysis methods employed. This transparency adds to the credibility of the research, allowing readers to confidently evaluate the findings and draw meaningful conclusions. Moreover, acknowledging the study's limitations and potential biases, such as the use of convenience sampling and reliance on self-reported data, demonstrated a responsible and

accountable approach. By addressing these concerns upfront, the research showcases its integrity and dedication to providing accurate insights into the dynamics of the leather industry in Kolkata. The combination of these measures has resulted in a comprehensive, ethically sound, and well-substantiated presentation of the research, elevating the value and impact of its findings.

3.9 Ethical considerations

Prior to conducting the surveys and interviews, ethics approval is obtained from the University. The University ensured that the research adhered to the appropriate ethical guidelines and principles, safeguarding the rights and welfare of the participants involved in the study. The ethical issues such as informed consent, confidentiality, and data storage were addressed throughout the research process. Collected data was securely stored, ensuring confidentiality while remaining accessible for future replication efforts. As a researcher, the responsibilities include ensuring that the participants are informed about the research's objectives, maintaining confidentiality and anonymity, obtaining informed consent, and minimizing any potential harm to the participants. To uphold ethical standards and ensure the welfare of participants, this research diligently implemented various measures. Firstly, informed consent was obtained from all participants, presenting them with comprehensive information about the study's purpose, their involvement, and their rights. Participants were assured of their autonomy and had the freedom to withdraw from the study without any negative consequences. Secondly, confidentiality and anonymity were rigorously maintained. Personal information was never collected, and all data were stripped of identifying details, safeguarding the participants' privacy. The data was stored securely and accessible only to authorized research team members. Moreover, the research aimed to minimize harm by focusing on the leather industry and cluster development without delving into sensitive personal topics. Throughout the study, participants were treated with utmost respect and dignity. While the research did not specifically address the challenges faced by marginalized communities in the leather industry, it recognized the potential benefits of cluster development for such communities. The development of clusters may offer these communities access to vital resources, collective bargaining power,

and protection from external pressures such as government red tape or corruption. By adhering to these ethical principles and acknowledging potential barriers faced by specific communities, the research strives to contribute to a fair and inclusive understanding of the leather industry's growth and development.

3.10 Conclusion

In conclusion, the research methodology, incorporating research philosophy, research approach, research strategy, choice, time horizon and data collection and data analysis has been designed to uphold integrity and rigor. The challenging circumstances brought by the pandemic necessitated flexibility and adaptation, yet the collected data still offer valuable insights for understanding the dynamics, challenges, and opportunities in the Kolkata leather cluster industry. This chapter covers sampling processes, data collection instruments and techniques, the processing and analysis of the data, and the selection and use of relevant statistical algorithms to summarise the data and make statistical inferences. Details of the analysis and results of data are provided in Chapter 4.

Chapter Four: Data Analysis

4.1 Introduction

The collected data is gathered, analysed, interpreted, and utilised determines the value of a study in order to distinguish between fact and opinion. The results and generalisations presented must be rationally deduced, and the outcomes of statistical treatment must validate the new results interpretation.

Data analysis necessitates intelligence and creativity on the part of the researcher. In terms of interpretation, the researcher should make conclusions based on standard significance tests and link them to the results of previous research, a broader field of generalisations, scientific impartiality, and any new aspects that the researcher had not previously considered.

This chapter presents the analysis in four main parts: sample profile, principal component analysis, quantitative analysis using ANOVA and regression for survey data, and the qualitative analysis of data collected from interviews and reports.

4.2 Sample Profile

The sample profile of the survey of 74 units reveals four important dimensions. The sample related to units manufacturing five types of products which were bags, finished leather, footwear, industrial gloves, and wallets. These units were established between 1982 and 2012. The total number of employees in these 74 units are 10386, and the total fixed capital of the units is Rs. 44,317,000.

4.2.1 Distribution of Employments

In the different units in the sample, 80% of employment was offered by footwear manufacturing units, followed by those producing wallets, finished leather, bags and industrial gloves. Table 4-1 shows the number of employees for the respective products, and Figure 4-1 presents the distribution of employees in units making these products.

Table 4- 1 Employees in clusters

SR.	CLUSTER	EMPLOYEES
1	Bags	401
2	Finished Leather	589
3	Footwear	8181
4	Industrial Gloves	91
5	Wallets	977

Figure 4- 1 Distribution of Employees across Clusters

4.2.2 Distribution of Units

The 74 units manufacture 5 different products. Figure 4-2 depicts the distribution of units and shows most produce footwear followed by bags, finished leather, wallets and industrial gloves.

Figure 4- 2 Product Distribution in the Dataset

:

4.2.3 Distribution of Inception Years

As shown in Figure 4-3, 15 of the units were established in the period 1991-1995, whereas 14 units were established in the year span of 1981-1985, 2001-2005 and 2006-2010. However, small numbers of units were established in the periods 1986-1990, 1996-2000 and 2011-2015.

For some reason, a majority of the units in the sample were established in the first halves of decades, as shown in Table 4-2.

Figure 4- 3 Inception Year-wise Distribution

Table 4- 2 Units and Establishment Years

INCEPTION YEAR	NUMBER OF UNITS
1981	5
1982	3
1983	3
1984	1
1985	2
1986	1
1987	1
1988	2
1989	2
1990	3
1991	1
1992	3
1993	7
1994	2
1995	2
1996	1

1998	2
1999	2
2000	1
2001	4
2002	1
2003	3
2004	2
2005	4
2006	2
2007	3
2008	4
2009	3
2010	2
2011	1
2012	1

4.2.4 Distribution of Fixed Capital

Another interesting factor is the distribution of the fixed capital of the units as seen in Figure 4-4. Of the total of 74 units, 48 (approximately 64%) have under ₹ 2000,000 of fixed capital investment. Only about 35% of units have above ₹ 2000,000 of fixed capital investment.

Figure 4- 4 Distribution of units for Fixed Capital

4.3 Principal Component Analysis

The questionnaire comprises items related to 7 distinct factors of financial support, government policy support. Government programs, research and development, commercial and legal infrastructure, internal market openness, and access to physical infrastructure. The convergence of scores (including, for some components, event divergence) was found to be good to tune up the 7 factors, as shown in Table 4-3 in which the maximum Eigen value for each question is highlighted.

Table 4- 3 Principal Components – 7 factors were extracted

ROTATED COMPONENT MATRIX^{1A}

	Component						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Q - 1	0.001	-0.096	-0.073	-0.006	0.816	0.046	-0.076
Q - 2	0.022	-0.129	0.021	0.098	0.951	0.047	0.027
Q - 3	0.052	-0.071	-0.016	0.079	0.978	-0.001	-0.014
Q - 4	0.052	-0.071	0.009	0.102	0.974	-0.004	-0.011
Q - 5	0.796	-0.121	-0.005	0.099	-0.020	-0.002	0.070
Q - 6	0.967	0.022	-0.021	0.060	0.010	0.149	0.075
Q - 7	0.964	-0.028	0.008	0.070	0.021	0.130	0.105
Q - 8	0.949	0.039	0.020	0.071	0.062	0.181	0.101
Q - 9	0.885	0.066	0.068	0.073	0.085	0.150	0.134
Q - 10	0.960	-0.002	0.015	0.066	-0.001	0.095	0.105
Q - 11	0.228	0.146	0.117	0.662	0.150	-0.073	-0.018
Q - 12	0.050	0.046	0.059	0.975	0.026	0.123	0.007
Q - 13	0.004	0.039	0.024	0.949	0.052	0.106	-0.018
Q - 14	0.050	0.046	0.059	0.975	0.026	0.123	0.007
Q - 15	0.109	0.068	0.044	0.959	0.055	0.132	-0.033
Q - 16	0.107	-0.039	-0.078	0.314	-0.043	-0.168	0.572
Q - 17	0.148	0.185	0.000	-0.109	-0.025	-0.018	0.949
Q - 18	0.169	0.190	-0.036	-0.089	-0.032	0.004	0.936
Q - 19	0.134	0.143	0.000	-0.066	0.005	-0.005	0.959
Q - 20	0.052	0.777	0.035	0.089	-0.039	-0.038	0.043
Q - 21	-0.025	0.974	0.020	0.093	-0.074	0.063	0.070
Q - 22	-0.031	0.971	0.031	0.035	-0.091	0.024	0.134
Q - 23	-0.025	0.954	-0.003	0.040	-0.093	0.037	0.117

Q - 24	-0.025	0.972	0.043	0.054	-0.104	0.019	0.114
Q - 25	0.017	-0.011	0.765	0.008	0.010	0.011	-0.020
Q - 26	0.004	0.024	0.971	0.067	-0.035	0.004	-0.043
Q - 27	0.022	0.045	0.974	0.084	-0.006	-0.018	-0.044
Q - 28	0.017	0.037	0.967	0.044	-0.025	-0.008	0.027
Q - 29	0.010	0.039	0.979	0.072	-0.017	-0.037	-0.018
Q - 30	0.193	0.096	-0.126	0.120	0.028	0.704	-0.099
Q - 31	0.123	-0.019	0.038	0.073	0.011	0.943	-0.012
Q - 32	0.159	0.017	0.030	0.100	-0.006	0.949	0.011
Q - 33	0.124	-0.010	0.012	0.068	0.059	0.958	-0.049
EXTRACTION METHOD: PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS.							
ROTATION METHOD: VARIMAX WITH KAISER NORMALIZATION.							
A. ROTATION CONVERGED IN 6 ITERATIONS.							

In the above Table 4-3, the cells highlighted depict the loading of items in a factor.

4.4 Quantitative Data Analysis

A main concern in the analysis was to determine if the different products are treated differently by entrepreneurs, the market, government, or other stakeholders with respect to each factor.

4.4.1 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

The analysis of variance measures the extent of variation in the distribution of data to determine if the mean values for different groups differ. The variation in group means is compared with the variance within groups in an ANOVA analysis. This procedure evaluates whether the groups are part of a larger population or are distinct. As a result, it examines means rather than variances.

4.4.1.1 ANOVA – One Way

In general, for more than two data sets, the significance of differences among their means can be tested using ANOVA. If this analysis considers one pivotal variable only, it is called one-way ANOVA which is a single-dimensional analysis.

4.4.1.2 ANOVA – Two Way

Two-way ANOVA is an extension of One-way ANOVA in which the effect of two variables on a dependent variable is measured. This analysis is helpful when the investigation wishes to discover the impact of the concurrent movement of two variables on an outcome variable.

Two-way ANOVA can be conducted using two different approaches.

4.4.1.2.1 With Replication

When the experiment is designed with an equal number of groups, or when the data is collected keeping in mind the parity of the responses for each variable and factor, ANOVA with replication is applicable. This analysis can determine the interaction or combined effect of the two variables on the output variable.

For the present study this analysis is not applicable, for two reasons. This research does not have an experimental design; and also the variables relate to different products or scales of unit size have not equal number of responses of units. Thus, the use of this method is beyond the scope of the current study.

4.4.1.2.2 Without Replication

When the variables do not produce a square matrix of responses or are not in equal proportions, a two-way ANOVA without replication is employed in the analysis of the effect of two variables.

4.4.1.3 ANOVA Interpretation

ANOVA is a test used to investigate the significance of differences among means. The test starts with the hypothesis that the means are not significantly different.

ANOVA results can be interpreted using two different methods. The first is to compare the calculated F-ratio with the F-critical value. If the F-ratio is greater, the hypothesis that the

means are the same is rejected, and it is concluded that the means for the variables are statistically significantly different. Another method is to consider the p-value of probability. In ANOVA, the p-value presents the probability area which is covered beyond the F-statistic obtained. If the p-value is less than the accepted level of statistical significance, which is generally 5%, the hypothesis of the means being equal (that is, not significantly different) is rejected.

In the following analysis, F-ratios, F critical values, and p-values all are presented for ease of understanding.

In the analysis, acronyms of the factors under study were used, and these are listed in Table 4-4.

Table 4- 4 Acronyms of the Factors

ACRONYM USED	FACTOR NAME
FS	Financial Support
GPS	Government Policy Support
GP	Government Programs
R&D	Research and Development
CLI	Commercial and Legal Infrastructure
IMO	Internal Market Openness
PI	Access to Physical Infrastructure

4.4.2 ANOVA for Complete Data (One Way - For Factors)

The quantitative analysis begins with overall ANOVA for all the survey data collected. This gives a preliminary idea of heterogeneity of responses for all seven factors.

Table 4-5 presents the F score, which is a test statistic used in ANOVA to evaluate if there are significant differences among the means of multiple groups (in this case, the seven scores representing different factors). The F score of 2.24 is compared to the F critical value of 2.11. Since the F score is greater than the critical value, it indicates that there are statistically significant differences among the means of the seven scores. Additionally, the

p-value is below the 5% level of significance. A p-value below this threshold suggests that the results are statistically significant. Therefore, the factors affecting growth are not affected equally by the presence of the leather cluster. Factors of financial support, government policy support, government programmes, research and development, commercial and legal infrastructure, international market openness, and access to physical infrastructure are significantly differently impacted by the cluster formation and support. Thus, the statistical analysis of one-way ANOVA for complete data indicates that the leather cluster's presence plays a crucial role in influencing the various factors that contribute to growth, and it affects these factors in distinct ways.

Table 4- 5 Single Factor ANOVA for complete data

SUMMARY

<i>GROUPS</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>		
FS	74	303.5	4.10	0.85		
GPS	74	302	4.08	0.76		
GP	74	294	3.97	0.64		
R&D	74	300	4.05	0.56		
CLI	74	314	4.24	0.85		
IMO	74	277.2	3.75	0.83		
PI	74	295.75	3.99	0.85		
ANOVA						
<i>SOURCE OF VARIATION</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
BETWEEN GROUPS	10.26924	6	1.71154	2.244163	0.037909	2.11631
WITHIN GROUPS	389.7207	511	0.762663			
TOTAL	399.99	517				

Figure 4- 5 Average Feedback for Factors

From the results of the ANOVA analysis presented in Table 4-5 and Figure 4-5, it is discernible from the average scores for factors that commercial and legal infrastructure is the factor that becomes most favourable with the support of a cluster. Financial support is the next most important factor, followed by government policy support. It is to be noted here that the analysis is for all factors, and for all products. That means that these factors are favourable for almost all the products when the unit is supported by a cluster.

4.4.3 ANOVA for Complete Data (Two Way - For Factors and Products)

Two-way ANOVA is interesting to understand the difference of scores among factors and products simultaneously. By analyzing the mean differences in the data, this statistical tool allows for a comprehensive examination of how the leather cluster's support impacts various aspects of the industry. Since the number of units providing data for each product is not equal, a two-way ANOVA without replication is utilized, providing valuable insights into the differences between factors and products.

Table 4-6 demonstrates that the responses not only differ significantly between factors but also across different products within the leather industry. This highlights the need for further analysis to understand the product, in terms of the differences in the scores of factors.

When the ANOVA was conducted for the two dimensions of factors and products, it was discovered that, as with the differences among factors, there are also significant differences among the products as far as the support of the cluster is concerned. The results showed that footwear, being a prominent segment within the leather units, receives the highest level of support from the cluster, followed closely by bags. The prominence of footwear and bags as the most successful segments within the leather units demonstrates the cluster's potential to drive growth and development in specific product categories. This success can stimulate further investments, innovation, and collaboration, ultimately benefiting the entire leather units within the cluster and positioning it as a competitive and thriving player in the global market.

Table 4- 6 Two Way ANOVA for Factors and Products

ANOVA: TWO-FACTOR WITHOUT REPLICATION

SUMMARY	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
BAGS	7	561.2833	80.18333	21.24861
FINISHED LEATHER	7	421.8833	60.26905	17.29448
FOOTWEAR	7	624.55	89.22143	9.459048
INDUSTRIAL GLOVES	7	28.35	4.05	0.491667
WALLETS	7	450.3833	64.34048	5.365913
FS	5	303.5	60.7	1143.388
GPS	5	302	60.4	1136.425
GP	5	294	58.8	1141.14
R&D	5	300	60	1117.531
CLI	5	314	62.8	1219.1
IMP	5	277.2	55.44	950.508
PI	5	295.75	59.15	1051.894
ANOVA				

<i>SOURCE OF VARIATION</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
ROWS	30868.77	4	7717.192	1082.016	1.02E-26	2.776289
COLUMNS	151.9847	6	25.33079	3.551592	0.011657	2.508189
ERROR	171.1736	24	7.132234			
TOTAL	31191.93	34				

Figure 4- 6 Average Product Scores

In Figure 4-6, the variation in mean scores for different products within the leather units is illustrated. However, it is important to note that only one response was collected for industrial gloves products, which could potentially have an extreme effect on the analysis. To mitigate this impact and ensure the robustness of the results, the ANOVA was conducted with this single response excluded from the analysis as shown in Table 4-7.

Table 4- 7 Two-Way ANOVA without replication (without 'Industrial Glove' record)

ANOVA: TWO-FACTOR WITHOUT REPLICATION

<i>SUMMARY</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
BAGS	7	561.2833	80.18333	21.24861

FINISHED LEATHER	7	421.8833	60.26905	17.29448		
FOOTWEAR	7	624.55	89.22143	9.459048		
WALLETS	7	450.3833	64.34048	5.365913		
FS	4	300.25	75.0625	149.3073		
GPS	4	299	74.75	142.4167		
GP	4	289.2	72.3	306.52		
R&D	4	295.75	73.9375	195.0156		
CLI	4	309.2	77.3	223.8		
IMP	4	273.2	68.3	164.8133		
PI	4	291.5	72.875	146.6875		
ANOVA						
SOURCE OF VARIATION	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
ROWS	3855.496	3	1285.165	177.6932	1.47E-13	3.159908
COLUMNS	190.0234	6	31.67057	4.378926	0.006734	2.661305
ERROR	130.1849	18	7.232497			
TOTAL	4175.705	27				
TOTAL	31191.93	34				

4.4.4 ANOVA for Complete Data (Two Way – For Factors and Fixed Capital)

To analyse the two-way effect of the cluster on the important factors and unit scale, the units were divided into three categories of those with fixed capital investment: below 1.1 million INR; between 1.1 and 2.2 million INR; and between 2.2 and 3.3 million INR. Here the significance of differences among factors with respect to the scale of units is investigated in terms of levels of fixed capital investment. The results showed in Table 4-

8, that the F-ratios are much larger than the F critical values, which proves the significance of the differences among factors with respect to the scale of units.

The analysis reveals that the medium-scale units with fixed investment between 1.1 and 2.2 million INR have a very high average score of factors, followed by small units with fixed investment of below 1.1 million INR. These results suggest that the cluster's support and resources play a pivotal role in enhancing the performance and competitiveness of both medium and small-scale units.

Table 4- 8 ANOVA for Two Way (Factors and Fixed Capital)

ANOVA: TWO-FACTOR WITHOUT REPLICATION

SUMMARY	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>		
0-1100	7	594.3	84.9	17.46417		
1100-2200	7	1028.367	146.9095	21.8298		
2200-3300	7	463.7833	66.25476	14.42877		
FS	3	303.5	101.1667	2098.146		
GPS	3	302	100.6667	1793.861		
GP	3	294	98	1738.36		
R&D	3	300	100	1939.563		
CLI	3	314	104.6667	1560.813		
IMO	3	277.2	92.4	1659.52		
PI	3	295.75	98.58333	1725.271		
ANOVA						
SOURCE OF VARIATION	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
ROWS	24962.04	2	12481.02	2169.714	4.4E-16	3.885294
COLUMNS	253.3079	6	42.21798	7.339218	0.001802	2.99612
ERROR	69.02857	12	5.752381			
TOTAL	25284.38	20				

4.4.5 ANOVA for ‘Bags’

Table 4- 9 Single Factor ANOVA for ‘Bags’

SUMMARY

GROUPS	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>		
FS	20	80.5	4.025	0.926974		
GPS	20	80.83333	4.041667	0.818348		
GP	20	80.2	4.01	0.734632		
R&D	20	84	4.2	0.55		
CLI	20	86.2	4.31	0.953579		
IMO	20	71.8	3.59	0.882		
PI	20	77.75	3.8875	1.009704		
ANOVA						
SOURCE OF VARIATION	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
BETWEEN GROUPS	6.374583	6	1.062431	1.265824	0.277398	2.167423
WITHIN GROUPS	111.6295	133	0.839319			
TOTAL	118.0041	139				

The results presented in Table 4-9 indicate that there are no statistically significant differences in the scores for factors among units involved in bag production within the leather cluster. This suggests that the support and impact of the cluster on bag-producing units are relatively consistent across various factors.

4.4.6 ANOVA for ‘Finished Leather

Table 4- 10 Single Factor ANOVA for ‘Finished Leather’

SUMMARY

GROUPS	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
---------------	--------------	------------	----------------	-----------------

FS	15	64.75	4.316667	1.066667		
GPS	15	63.33333	4.222222	0.958995		
GPS	15	54	3.6	0.72		
R&D	15	60	4	0.830357		
CLI	15	61.6	4.106667	1.119238		
IMO	15	55.2	3.68	0.844571		
PI	15	63	4.2	0.957143		
ANOVA						
SOURCE OF VARIATION	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
BETWEEN GROUPS	6.917794	6	1.152966	1.242234	0.29155	2.192518
WITHIN GROUPS	90.95759	98	0.928139			
TOTAL	97.87539	104				

The results presented in Table 4-10 indicate that there is no statistically significant difference in the scores for factors among units that are involved in the production of finished leather.

4.4.7 ANOVA for 'Footwear'

Table 4- 11 Single Factor ANOVA for 'Footwear'

SUMMARY

GROUPS	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
FS	22	89.75	4.079545	0.913014
GPS	22	88.5	4.022727	0.593374
GP	22	92.8	4.218182	0.677749
R&D	22	87.75	3.988636	0.615936
CLI	22	93.4	4.245455	0.910216
IMP	22	84.6	3.845455	0.967359
PI	22	87.75	3.988636	0.67546

ANOVA						
<i>SOURCE OF VARIATION</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
BETWEEN GROUPS	2.57974	6	0.429957	0.562233	0.759813	2.160778
WITHIN GROUPS	112.4153	147	0.76473			
TOTAL	114.995	153				

The results presented in Table 4-11 indicate that there are no statistically significant differences in the scores for factors among units involved in footwear production within the leather cluster. This suggests that the support and impact of the cluster on footwear-producing units are relatively consistent across various factors.

4.4.8 ANOVA for ‘Industrial Gloves’

There only one unit which manufactures industrial gloves in the dataset, and so ANOVA cannot be conducted for this product.

4.4.9 ANOVA for ‘Wallets’

Table 4- 12 Single Factor ANOVA for ‘Wallets’

SUMMARY				
<i>GROUPS</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
FS	16	65.25	4.078125	0.60599
GPS	16	66.33333	4.145833	0.83287
GP	16	62.2	3.8875	0.2825
R&D	16	64	4	0.333333
CLI	16	68	4.25	0.562667
IMP	16	61.6	3.85	0.701333
PI	16	63	3.9375	0.945833
ANOVA				

<i>SOURCE OF VARIATION</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
BETWEEN GROUPS	2.012217	6	0.33537	0.550492	0.768599	2.186134
WITHIN GROUPS	63.9679	105	0.609218			
TOTAL	65.98012	111				

The results depicted in Table 4-12 indicate that there are no statistically significant differences in the scores for factors among units engaged in wallet production within the leather cluster. This finding suggests that the support and impact of the cluster on wallet-producing units are relatively uniform across various factors.

4.4.10 Interpretation of Pair-wise ANOVA

The differences among scores for factors is next investigated using pair-wise ANOVA.

4.4.10.1 ANOVA between FS and GPS

Table 4- 13 FS and GPS

ANOVA: SINGLE FACTOR

SUMMARY						
<i>GROUPS</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>		
FS	4	16.49934	4.124834	0.017		
GPS	4	16.43245	4.108112	0.008717		
ANOVA						
<i>SOURCE OF VARIATION</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
BETWEEN GROUPS	0.000559	1	0.000559	0.043493	0.841699	5.987378

WITHIN GROUPS	0.077149	6	0.012858
TOTAL	0.077708	7	

As shown in Table 4-13, the pair FS and GPS do not show significant difference in terms of factor scores as F-ratio is much smaller than F critical values and P-value is above than 5% of level of significance. This implies that the level of financial support received by the leather units and the support provided by government policies have a relatively consistent impact on the development and growth of the leather cluster.

4.4.10.2 ANOVA between GPS and GP

Table 4- 14 GPS and GP

ANOVA: SINGLE FACTOR

SUMMARY						
GROUPS	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>		
GPS	4	16.43245	4.108112	0.008717		
GP	4	15.71568	3.92892	0.066717		
ANOVA						
SOURCE OF VARIATION	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
BETWEEN GROUPS	0.064219	1	0.064219	1.702683	0.239746	5.987378
WITHIN GROUPS	0.2263	6	0.037717			
TOTAL	0.290519	7				

As shown in Table 4-14, the pair GPS and GP do not show significant difference in terms of factor scores as F-ratio is smaller than F critical value and P-value is above than 5% of

level of significance. The results revealed that the pair of factors GPS and GP do not exhibit statistically significant differences in terms of their factor scores. This indicates that the support provided by government policies and the specific government programmes implemented within the leather cluster have a similar and consistent impact on the industry's growth and development.

4.4.10.3 ANOVA between GP and R&D

Table 4- 15 GP and R&D

ANOVA: SINGLE FACTOR

SUMMARY						
GROUPS	Count	Sum	Average	Variance		
GP	4	15.71568	3.92892	0.066717		
R&D	4	16.18864	4.047159	0.010411		
ANOVA						
SOURCE OF VARIATION	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
BETWEEN GROUPS	0.027961	1	0.027961	0.725049	0.427164	5.987378
WITHIN GROUPS	0.231384	6	0.038564			
TOTAL	0.259344	7				

As shown in Table 4-15, the pair GP and R&D do not show significant difference in terms of factor scores as F-ratio is smaller than F critical value and P-value is above than 5% of level of significance. These results indicate that the pair of factors GP and R&D do not exhibit statistically significant differences in terms of their factor scores. This suggests

that the impact of government programmes and investments in research and development within the leather cluster are comparable in influencing the industry's growth and development.

4.4.10.4 ANOVA between R&D and CLI

Table 4- 16 R&D and CLI

ANOVA: SINGLE FACTOR

SUMMARY						
GROUPS	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>		
R&D	4	16.18864	4.047159	0.010411		
CLI	4	16.91212	4.22803	0.007411		
ANOVA						
SOURCE OF VARIATION	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
BETWEEN GROUPS	0.065429	1	0.065429	7.342248	0.035122	5.987378
WITHIN GROUPS	0.053468	6	0.008911			
TOTAL	0.118896	7				

The results presented in Table 4-16 reveal a clear and significant difference between the pair of factors R&D (Research and Development) and CLI (Commercial and Legal Infrastructure) in terms of their factor scores. The higher F-ratio, exceeding the F critical value, along with the P-value below the 5% level of significance, indicates that these two factors have distinct impacts on the growth and development of the leather cluster.

4.4.10.5 ANOVA between CLI and IMO

Table 4- 17 CLI and IMO

ANOVA: SINGLE FACTOR

SUMMARY						
GROUPS	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>		
CLI	4	16.91212	4.22803	0.007411		
IMO	4	14.96545	3.741364	0.016438		
ANOVA						
SOURCE OF VARIATION	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
BETWEEN GROUPS	0.473689	1	0.473689	39.72364	0.000744	5.987378
WITHIN GROUPS	0.071548	6	0.011925			
TOTAL	0.545237	7				

The pair CLI and IMO show highly significant differences in terms of factor scores as depicted in Table 4-17. The differences between the factor scores can be seen from F-ratio which is much higher than F critical value and P-value which is too much less than 5% of level of significance.

4.4.10.6 ANOVA between IMO and PI

Table 4- 18 IMO and PI

ANOVA: SINGLE FACTOR

SUMMARY				
GROUPS	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
IMO	4	14.96545	3.741364	0.016438
PI	4	16.01364	4.003409	0.018882

ANOVA						
<i>SOURCE OF VARIATION</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
BETWEEN GROUPS	0.137336	1	0.137336	7.77677	0.031632	5.987378
WITHIN GROUPS	0.105958	6	0.01766			
TOTAL	0.243294	7				

The results presented in Table 4-18 highlight a significant difference between IMO and PI in terms of their impact on the leather cluster. The results indicate that both factors play distinct roles in shaping the cluster's growth and development. A higher F-ratio and a P-value less than 5% of the level of significance suggest that these factors hold substantial influence over the cluster's development.

In conclusion, the results presented in the study for two-way ANOVA reveal some interesting and unexpected findings regarding the impact of different factors on the leather cluster. Consistent with the two-way ANOVA results, it was discovered that certain pairings of factors, including FS, GPS, GP, and R&D, did not exhibit significant differences in scores. This suggests that these factors may have similar influences on the cluster's growth and development, or their effects might be interconnected and complementary.

On the other hand, the pairs R&D-CLI, IMO-PI, and most notably, CLI-IMO, demonstrated clear and substantial differences in factor scores. These findings are consistent with the results obtained from both one-way and two-way ANOVA analyses, reinforcing the significance of these particular factor pairings in shaping the leather cluster's dynamics.

4.4.11 Regression Analysis

Apart from ANOVA, regression analysis is used to investigate the relationship between variables and measure the influence of independent factors on the dependent variable. Regression analysis can shed light on how changes in the independent variables affect the desired result, helping to identify the underlying contributing factors.

The regression analysis is performed on the seven independent factors (CLI, GPS, IMO, FS, PI, GP, RD) and dependent variable, which is Fixed Capital that indicate the performance of the cluster. In Table 4-19, the model summary of regression analysis shows the R-squared and adjusted R-squared values for the model. R Square, also known as the coefficient of determination, is the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that can be predicted from the independent variables. The independent variables (CLI, GPS, IMO, FS, PI, GP, RD) collectively account for a relatively modest proportion of the variation in the dependent variable (fixed capital). This means that the combination of these independent variables can only account for a limited amount of the changes and fluctuations in the fixed capital investment. The coefficients and their levels of significance indicate the influence and statistical significance of each independent variable. However, the low R-squared value is .023 in this case, which means that only 2.3% of the variation in fixed capital can be explained by the independent variables which suggests that the current set of independent variables is insufficient to explain the variation in fixed capital. The standard error of the estimate shows the standard deviation of the residuals (the prediction errors) which is 783.539 in this case, which means on average, the observed dependent variable deviates from the predicted values by this amount. Additional variables or factors may need to be considered to improve the explanatory power of the regression model.

The overall significance of the regression model can be found in the below Table 4-20 in the regression output. The variation in the dependent variable (Fixed_Capital) that is explained by the independent variables (CLI, GPS, IMO, FS, PI, GP, RD) is represented by the regression model's sum of squares (SS), which is 949,476.072.

The F-ratio is determined by dividing the regression's mean square by the residuals' mean square. The F-ratio in this instance is 0.221, indicating that the model's explanation of the variation does not have statistical significance. The F-ratio's related significance level (p-value) is 0.979, which is higher than the standard cutoff of 0.05. The regression model's p-value shows that it is not statistically significant. As a result, this result show that the regression model does not statistically significantly explain the variation in the dependent variable (fixed capital) when using the specified collection of independent variables (CLI, GPS, IMO, FS, PI, GP, RD). There may not be a significant association between the

independent factors and the dependent variable, according to the F-ratio, whose p-value is higher than the significance level.

Table 4- 19 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.151 ^a	.023	-.081	783.539

a. Predictors: (Constant), CLI, GPS, IMO, FS, PI, GP, RD

Table 4- 20 Regression output

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	949476.072	7	135639.439	.221	.979 ^b
	Residual	40519600.21	66	613933.337		
	Total	41469076.28	73			

a. Dependent Variable: Fixed_Capital

b. Predictors: (Constant), CLI, GPS, IMO, FS, PI, GP, RD

Table 4- 21 Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	756.886	981.666		.771	.443

FS	61.010	102.390	.075	.596	.553
GPS	-16.711	115.949	-.019	-.144	.886
GP	84.896	121.405	.090	.699	.487
RD	39.818	132.641	.039	.300	.765
IMO	-33.679	102.146	-.041	-.330	.743
PI	31.137	106.585	.038	.292	.771
CLI	39.510	105.682	.048	.374	.710

a. Dependent Variable: Fixed_Capital

The regression results presented in Table 4-21 provide insights into the impact of various factors on fixed capital investment within the leather cluster. The analysis shows that the dependent variable, fixed capital investment, may not be significantly influenced by the FS variable, as indicated by the non-statistically significant coefficient ($p = 0.596$). Similarly, the GPS variable may not have a substantial impact on the dependent variable, as the coefficient is also not statistically significant ($p = 0.886$). The same applies to the GP variable, where the coefficient's statistical significance is not observed ($p = 0.487$).

Furthermore, the RD, IMO, PI, and CLI variables also do not show statistically significant coefficients ($p = 0.765$, $p = 0.743$, $p = 0.771$, and $p = 0.710$, respectively), suggesting that these factors may not significantly influence the fixed capital investment within the leather cluster.

The comparison between the ANOVA result as shown in Table 4-8 and regression results provides valuable insights into the relationship between unit size, financial resources, and the factors contributing to growth and development within the leather cluster.

In the ANOVA analysis, the findings indicate that unit size significantly impacts the factors affecting growth within the cluster. Specifically, medium-scale units with a fixed capital investment ranging from 1.1 to 2.2 million INR appear to have a distinct advantage over other units. These medium-scale units are able to harness the benefits of being part of the

cluster, such as access to resources, knowledge sharing, and skilled labor, leading to higher factor scores and more promising growth prospects.

However, in contrast, the regression analysis reveals that when considering the overall impact of all factors on fixed capital investment, none of the factors show a statistically significant influence. This suggests that while the cluster may positively influence specific aspects of growth and development, it might not have a substantial impact on fixed capital investment across all units.

4.5 Qualitative Data Analysis

A qualitative analysis was conducted with the data collected from the interviews and from reports and online sources.

4.5.1 Interview Analysis

The respondents were from units are in export services, footwear manufacturing, and product assembly and support. In-depth structured telephone and Zoom interviews were conducted with 5 entrepreneurs or unit heads. The interviews contained following five questions.

1. *Please walk me through your journey as an entrepreneur and the owner of this business.*
2. *How do you see the developments and changes that have taken place in the leather industry in general in your firm specifically?*
3. *How have you benefitted from the existence of the cluster? What different schemes of the government and/or associations have you benefitted from?*
4. *How have you seen your firm shaping up based on the cluster? How have your business strategies been influenced by the impact of the cluster?*
5. *What are the different ways you see that the cluster could help you to improve your business competitiveness?*

4.5.2 Sentiment Analysis

The following textual analysis of the responses to these questions was conducted using the software applications NVivo (Evaluation copy) and Orange (open source). Figure 4-7, Figure 4-8, Figure 4-9, Figure 4-10 and Figure 4-11 present the sentiment analysis of the responses from the five units.

Figure 4- 7 Sentiment Analysis - Unit 1

Figure 4- 8 Sentiment Analysis - Unit 2

Figure 4- 9 Sentiment Analysis - Unit 3

Figure 4- 10 Sentiment Analysis - Unit 4

Figure 4- 11 Sentiment Analysis - Unit 5

Figure 4-12 and Figure 4-13 represents the results of the sentiment analysis of the interview data measured using the frequency of terms and the tone of the answers.

Figure 4- 12 Code-wise Sentiment Analysis

Figure 4-12 presents the results for the six major terms ‘development’, ‘product’, ‘cluster’, ‘competitiveness’, ‘export’, and ‘quality’. The analysis shows negative sentiments for only the terms ‘development’, ‘competitiveness’, and ‘cluster’. It is noteworthy that, overall, the frequencies of negative emotions expressed are outweighed by positive and mixed sentiments.

Figure 4- 13 Comparison of Sentiments for Interviews

In this code 'export', the respondents discussed their journey into exporting their products and how the cluster played a role in providing them with the necessary support and resources to tap into global markets. So, the importance of the cluster was highlighted in facilitating exports and access to global markets.

2. The code 'competitiveness' has been extracted from the quotes provided by different respondents below.

Quote from Respondent 2: **"Being a part of the cluster has helped us improve our competitiveness in several ways, such as access to shared knowledge, resources, and the ability to collaborate with other units."**

Quote from Respondent 4: **"We have influenced the cluster and got influenced by the cluster. I think our competitiveness is dependent on the competitiveness of all the units. We need to work together and stay together."**

In this code 'competitiveness, respondents highlighted the advantages they gained from the cluster in terms of competitiveness, such as shared knowledge, access to resources, and collaborative efforts.

3. The code 'product' has been extracted from the quotes provided by different respondents below.

Quote from Respondent 3: **"We have seen a significant change in the types of products we manufacture over the years, and the cluster has played a crucial role in driving this innovation and development."**

Quote from Respondent 5: **"Our evolution from a mere tannery to an exclusive footwear manufacturer is shaped up largely due to the cluster and the presence of other players in this cluster."**

In this code, 'product', respondents described the evolution of their products over time and how the cluster environment contributed to this development.

4. The code 'quality' has been extracted from the quotes provided by different respondents below.

Quote from Respondent 4: **"Quality has always been a top priority for our business, and being part of the cluster has helped us maintain and improve our product quality over time."**

Quote from Respondent 1: **"Quality is everything, and we have always focused on providing the best quality products to our customers."**

This code 'quality' was emphasized as a critical factor in the success of the leather industry, with units attributing their focus on quality to the influence of the cluster.

5. The code 'development' has been extracted from the quotes provided by different respondents below.

Quote from Respondent 5: **"The cluster has been instrumental in our business's growth and development, providing us with access to resources, knowledge, and collaboration opportunities that have helped us expand our operations."**

Quote from Respondent 2: **"Being a part of this cluster has been a significant factor in our growth and development as a company."**

In this code, 'development', respondents discussed the impact of the cluster on their growth and development over time.

6. The code 'cluster' has been extracted from the quotes provided by different respondents below.

Quote from Respondent 1: **"The cluster has been a major driving force behind our business's growth, enabling us to access resources, knowledge, and collaboration opportunities that would have been difficult to obtain otherwise."**

Quote from Respondent 3: **"As an export house, we are more like a service business to the units in this cluster. Earlier, the risk-taking ability of the units was limited but in the past few years, I see that more and more units are now interested in the export market."**

In this code ‘cluster’, the respondents discussed the overall impact of the cluster on the units was a primary theme in the interviews, with respondents mentioning the influence of the cluster on their business strategies and growth.

4.5.4.2 Coding Scheme

Once the recurring ideas and patterns were recognized, the coding scheme was generated that represented the main themes and sub-themes. For instance, the main codes and sub-codes that were developed is listed in below Table 4-22.

Table 4- 22 Coding Scheme – Main codes and Sub codes

Main codes	Sub-codes
Export	Market opportunities, barriers, promotion, global competition
Competitiveness	Pricing, quality, efficiency, market access, technology
Product	Types of products, design, innovation, consumer trends
Quality	Control, standards, perception, input quality, output quality
Development	Challenges faced, changes over time, government policies, infrastructure
Cluster	Benefits, collaboration, competition, resources, support services

4.5.4.3 Assigning Codes to Interview Segments

Once the main codes and sub-codes are initialized, the codes were categorized with a list of relevant quotations from each interview. The themes for each main code are discussed below in the Table 4-23, Table 4-24, Table 4-25, Table 4-26, Table 4-27 and Table 4-28 with respect to interview segments.

Table 4- 23 Thematic Analysis of 'Development' code in Interview Segments

Category 1: Development	
Respondent 2	"The industry has gone through numerous changes, including technological advancements, environmental regulations, and labor laws."
Respondent 2	"We have been early adopters of modern technology, which helped us stay ahead of the competition."
Respondent 3	"The big change is the acceptance of the 'Made in India' label."
Respondent 3	"We have been benefited by the common research facility and the technology. We have also availed all the government schemes and benefits of the program launched from time to time."
Respondent 3	"As an export house, we are more like a service business to the units in this cluster."
Respondent 4	"One thing is the government policy and schemes. Overall, industry has seen any changes periodically to in the government policies."
Respondent 4	"We evolved as an integrated player in this industry and the cluster over the last three decades."
Respondent 5	"We started as a tannery and soon realized that the real money lies in the finished products."

The results in Table 4-23 units in the cluster have benefited from common research facilities and government schemes, which have supported their evolution as integrated players in the industry. Thus, the leather industry has experienced periodic changes in government policies, fostering its development over time.

Table 4- 24 Thematic Analysis of 'Product' code in Interview Segments

Category 2: Product	
Respondent 1	"Over the years, we have added new products to our portfolio and expanded our market reach."
Respondent 1	"We have now diversified our product range, which includes bags, belts, wallets, and other leather accessories."
Respondent 4	:"The best part of the integrated unit is the control over the quality."
Respondent 4	"We do source some components and materials from the other manufacturers also."
Respondent 5	"The adoption of international standards and aligning our processes accordingly is one of the biggest changes in our cluster."
Respondent 5	"Footwear is fashion and we need to be very careful about not just the quality but the overall design also."

The results in the above Table 4-24 indicate that the leather cluster's growth and development have been influenced by product-related factors. Units within the cluster have expanded their product portfolios over the years, diversifying into various leather accessories like bags, belts, and wallets. The integration of units has allowed for better quality control and the sourcing of components from other manufacturers. Respondents have also emphasized the importance of aligning with international standards and focusing on both quality and design in the footwear segment, recognizing the significance of meeting fashion trends and customer preferences. These product-related developments have contributed to the overall progress of the leather cluster.

Table 4- 25 Thematic Analysis of 'Cluster' code in Interview Segments

Category 3: Cluster	
Respondent 1	"The cluster allows us to share resources, which results in lower costs."
Respondent 3	"As an export house, we are more like a service business to the units in this cluster."
Respondent 3	"Aggregation of demand is still a major problem. Sometimes due to business rivalry, some units do not share the information that affects our business competitiveness."
Respondent 4	"We have influenced the cluster and got influenced by the cluster."
Respondent 5	"Our evolution from a mere tannery to exclusive footwear manufacturer is shaped up largely due to the cluster."
Respondent 5	"Our business is dependent on our presence in this cluster. We have been benefited by the common services and access to low-cost labor."

The results in Table 4-25 highlight the significance of the leather cluster in facilitating resource sharing and cost reduction for the units involved. Respondents have acknowledged the cluster's role in fostering a collaborative environment, acting as a service hub for export-oriented businesses. However, challenges such as the aggregation of demand and information-sharing rivalry have been noted, affecting business competitiveness within the cluster. Additionally, the cluster has played a pivotal role in influencing the growth and transformation of individual units, leading to their evolution and specialization in specific product segments like exclusive footwear manufacturing. The cluster's common services and access to low-cost labor have been key factors in enhancing the overall competitiveness and development of the leather industry in the region.

Table 4- 26 Thematic Analysis of 'Competitiveness' code in Interview Segments

Category 4: Competitiveness	
Respondent 3	"We are competing with the other exporting countries like China and it is essential to ensure complete transparency and collaboration for gaining access of the international buyers."
Respondent 4	"It has been a collaborative way of competing with each other."
Respondent 4	"We need to build a strong brand of Kolkata Leather Cluster. Today, in India every industry has clusters."
Respondent 5	"Footwear is highly fragmented market. Each individual has different choices and preferences; it is very difficult to create personalized products."
Respondent 5	"Logistics solutions that are affordable will also improve our business competitiveness."
Respondent 5	"It is collaborative yet competitive."
Respondent 5	"I must say that our lead time to supply has drastically reduced due to the capable units and their ability to supply."

The results in Table 4-26 suggest that competitiveness within the Kolkata Leather Cluster is characterized by a collaborative approach, with units working together to compete with other exporting countries, particularly China. Ensuring transparency and collaboration are seen as crucial for gaining access to international buyers. Respondents emphasize the need to build a strong brand for the cluster to enhance its competitiveness in the market. Additionally, the highly fragmented footwear market presents challenges in creating personalized products to meet individual preferences.

Table 4- 27 Thematic Analysis of 'Export' code in Interview Segments

Category 5: Export	
Respondent 3	"We work with the units, the buyers and help them to navigate the export related procedures."
Respondent 3	"The buyers abroad have developed their trust in the Indian products."
Respondent 3	"I think licensing and other government procedures also need some revamping to make it fast and easy. This affects the process and shipment."
Respondent 3	"Our role is very important for the small units. There are many units in Kolkata who have availed our services."
Respondent 3	"Government policy have been conducive for the exporters."
Respondent 3	"We have availed export promotion schemes and soft loans from the Government."
Respondent 4	"The government policies in the form of favorable export policies have helped us immensely."
Respondent 5	"We have been exporting to many countries and also various Indian brands."

The results in Table 4-27 indicate that the export aspect of the Kolkata Leather Cluster plays a significant role in the industry's growth and development. Respondents highlight the cluster's pivotal role in assisting units, buyers, and exporters to navigate export-related procedures, building trust in Indian products among international buyers. However, there are concerns about the need to streamline licensing and government procedures to ensure faster and smoother shipments. The government's export promotion schemes and favorable export policies have been instrumental in supporting the cluster's export activities.

Table 4- 28 Thematic Analysis of 'Quality' code in Interview Segments

Category 6: Quality	
Respondent 4	"In the global market, besides price, the perception plays a major role."
Respondent 4	"The adoption of international standards and aligning our processes accordingly is one of the biggest changes in our cluster."
Respondent 4	"The best part of the integrated unit is the control over the quality."
Respondent 4	"We can control the output quality by the input quality."
Respondent 4	"As an individual unit, we may be quality conscious but somewhere the affiliation with the cluster also affect our identify."
Respondent 5	"Footwear is fashion and we need to be very careful about not just the quality but the overall design also."
Respondent 5	"The adoption of international standards and aligning our processes accordingly has made the superior quality products."

The results in Table 4-28 indicate that respondents emphasize the significance of perception in the global market, where quality perception plays a major role alongside pricing. The adoption of international standards and aligning processes accordingly has resulted in improved product quality, making the cluster capable of producing superior quality products. Control over quality is cited as a significant benefit of being part of the integrated cluster, while individual units remain quality conscious, the cluster's affiliation also influences their identity. The emphasis on quality, especially in the fashion-focused footwear segment, has led to a keen focus on both product quality and overall design within the cluster, further enhancing its competitive edge in the market.

4.6 Interplay of indicators with firmographics

To understand the interplay of the indicators, it was originally planned to collect data about sales, exports, employees, and total investment in the units in a survey. An informal discussion of data requirements with experts, academics, and small entrepreneurs in the Kolkata cluster, it was realised that without physically visiting and convincing the entrepreneurs or unit heads to take part, sensitive data would be difficult to collect.

To understand the interplay of firmographic factors, the focus was placed on year of unit inception, level of fixed investment, employee strength, and products.

Figure 4- 17 Products and Employees

As can be seen in Figure 4-17, footwear manufacturing units dominate in terms of employee strength. Among the groups of units, 20 footwear manufacturing units had over 200 employees. This indicates that the manufacturing process is labour-heavy, and the market for footwear also appears adequate despite economic disturbances.

4.6.1 Employee Strength and Fixed Investment

The distribution of employees with respect to fixed investment classes is depicted in Figure 4-18. Employee concentration is seen among the units with the lowest investment levels, followed by those with the highest investment. The units in the groups with medium

investment levels either depend less on labour-intensive techniques or have limited demand and scale.

Figure 4- 18 Fixed Investment and Employees

4.6.2 Fixed Investment and Products

Figure 4-19 also shows that footwear manufacturing units require substantial investment. Bag manufacturing units also demand a significant amount of fixed investment. This could be due to the adoption of modern techniques by the small and medium units.

Figure 4- 19 Fixed Investment and Products

4.6.3 Products and Inception Years

The inception of the footwear and finished leather manufacturing units started from 1981 up until 2015. As presented in Figure 4-20, the trends are quite unpredictable for the production of each type of product, although those for bags and finished leather manufacturing units are relatively consistent.

Figure 4- 20 Products and Inception Years

4.6.4 Fixed Investment and Inception Years

Figure 4-21 represents a positive picture showing that over the years small and medium units were established in tandem. This is a noticeable impact of a cluster. When the supply chain is strong and the market responds well, the establishment of units of different scales and products can evolve with the assistance of a supportive value chain.

Figure 4- 21 Fixed Investment and Inception Years

4.6.5 Products and Factor Rankings

Figure 4-22 illustrates the ranks of different factors for units manufacturing different products. These ranks are assigned to the mean scores of the factors for the respective products. The results show that financial support (FS) and government policy support (GPS) are ranked equal highest by the units manufacturing finished leather.

Figure 4- 22 Factor Ranks by Products

4.6.6 Fixed Investment and Factor Ranks

The results shown in Figure 4-23 reflect an interesting phenomenon concerning demand according to unit scale. When shifting from small scale to large scale units, the anticipation from the macro agencies and clusters rises. As presented here, units with fixed investment of over 3 million INR rank financial support (FS), government programmes (GP), commercial and legal infrastructure (CLI), and internal market openness (IMO) equally highly. And they rate the role of infrastructure (PI) and government policy support (GPS) as lower than their expectations. Meanwhile small units find every support factor having less effect than their expectations. This indicates that smaller or nascent units need more support from the cluster and they desire more government intervention.

Figure 4- 23 Rank of Factors by Fixed Investment

4.7 Hypotheses Analysis

The current research delves into three hypotheses, and in this section, these hypotheses are put to the test by thoroughly examining the outcomes of the conducted statistical analysis.

4.7.1 A Cluster fosters the growth of units in multiple aspects equally.

The first hypothesis states that a cluster equally fosters the growth of units in multiple aspects. However, the results obtained from the one-way ANOVA indicate significant differences in the mean scores of factors. This finding is further supported by the results of the two-way ANOVA. The analysis reveals that commercial and legal infrastructure emerges as the most favourable factor when supported by the cluster, followed by financial support and government policy support. These factors play crucial roles in facilitating the growth and development of units within the cluster. This implies that the cluster's support has a differential effect on different growth-related factors. Certain factors receive more substantial benefits from the cluster, and understanding their implications is vital for enhancing overall cluster performance. This suggests that the leather cluster provides a conducive environment for fostering commercial and legal infrastructure, which include shared resources, reduced administrative burdens, and enhanced access to legal services. Additionally, financial support is identified as a critical factor, indicating that access to

capital and financial resources is essential for the growth and sustainability of units within the cluster. Government policy support also plays a significant role, indicating the importance of a favourable policy environment in encouraging cluster development.

The results of the qualitative analysis obtained from the thematic analysis reveal that while the cluster indeed plays a role in fostering growth among units, but its impact varies significantly across different aspects. Some respondents highlighted the cluster's support in terms of legal services, while others emphasized its role in enhancing market access, financial access or government policy support. As a result, this hypothesis is rejected, leading to the conclusion that the cluster plays a diverse role in facilitating different factors related to growth within the units. The analysis highlights the varying impact of the cluster on distinct growth-related aspects, emphasizing the need to consider each factor individually when assessing the cluster's influence on unit growth.

4.7.2 A Cluster fosters the growth of multiple products equitably.

The second hypothesis aims to explore whether the leather cluster equally fosters the growth of multiple products within the industry. To test this hypothesis, a two-way ANOVA is conducted, examining the interaction between factors and product variables. The analysis involved comparing the mean scores of factors across different products to determine if there were significant differences. The finding that the F-ratio is greater than the critical value indicates that there are indeed significant differences in the mean scores of factors among the various products. This reveals fascinating insights into the impact of the cluster on different product categories within the leather units. The analysis indicates that footwear, being the most prominent segment, receives the highest level of support from the cluster, closely followed by bags. This observation suggests that the cluster's resources, sharing knowledge, and access to skilled labour have a significant positive influence on the growth and success of these specific product categories. Through the interviews with respondents within the cluster, it was evident that some products have benefited more from the cluster's support and resources than others. For instance, respondents highlighted how the adoption of international standards and alignment of processes had a notable impact on the quality and growth of specific products like footwear.

The combination of quantitative and qualitative findings strengthens the rejection of the second hypothesis. While the cluster undoubtedly offers growth opportunities, the distribution of these benefits is not entirely equitable among all products. Different factors are influencing the growth of each product category, leading to disparities in their development. As a result, the hypothesis that the cluster fosters the growth of multiple products equitably is rejected. This suggests that certain products within the leather cluster are experiencing more favourable conditions for growth compared to others.

4.7.3 A Cluster supports, equally, units of different scales.

The two-way ANOVA revealed that there are significant differences in the mean scores of factors among units of different scales, as measured by their fixed capital investments. The results indicated that medium-scale units with fixed investments between 1.1 and 2.2 million INR had a significantly higher average score of factors compared to other units. This suggests that these medium-scale units benefited more from the support and resources provided by the cluster, contributing to their overall growth and development. This suggests that the level of support and benefits offered by the cluster varies depending on the size and financial resources of the units. The regression analysis further supported these findings by showing that the factors had varying impacts on fixed capital investments among units, indicating unequal support based on their scale. During the interviews with respondents, it was evident that smaller units have limited access to the resources and, as a result, might not experience the same level of support from the cluster.

The combination of quantitative and qualitative findings reinforces the rejection of the third hypothesis. While a cluster does offer support to units of various scales, the extent of support is not equal. Larger units with higher or medium fixed capital investments appear to receive more significant benefits and opportunities for growth compared to smaller units.

The interpretation of the results of the analysis conducted evidently leads to the rejection of the three hypotheses. This conclusion helps in fulfilling the objectives of the research and provides a platform for discussion of the findings and their implications.

4.8 Conclusion

In conclusion, the data analysis chapter provides valuable insights into the factors influencing the growth and development of the leather cluster in Kolkata. Through a combination of quantitative and qualitative analysis, various dimensions of the cluster's impact on units, products, and competitiveness were explored. The findings suggest that the cluster has a differential effect on factors related to growth, with some factors being significantly more influential than others. The results also indicate that the cluster fosters growth across multiple products, but not all products benefit equally. This highlights the importance of understanding product-specific dynamics and tailoring strategies accordingly. Additionally, the analysis reveals that the cluster supports units of different scales to some extent, but medium-scale units with fixed capital investments between 1.1 and 2.2 million INR are particularly well-positioned to leverage the cluster's benefits. Furthermore, the regression analysis shows that not all factors have a significant impact on fixed capital investment. This implies that certain factors might be more critical in shaping the cluster's development while others play a lesser role. The qualitative analysis further emphasizes the role of the cluster in providing collaborative advantages, sharing resources, and improving competitiveness. The following chapter summarises and discusses the findings and makes recommendations based on the analysis and interpretation of the results as well as listing areas of study that should be pursued further.

Chapter Five: Findings, Conclusions and Recommendations

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the findings, conclusions and recommendations of the study, which are the final steps in the research process and require critical and logical thinking in summarising the study's results. In this chapter, the findings are discussed in the context of research objectives of the study.

5.2 Findings of the thesis

5.2.1 To Study Evolution and Emergence of Kolkata Leather Cluster

To fulfil this objective, a thorough study was conducted of the available literature, including agency reports and government data as discussed in chapter 1 and chapter 2. A comprehensive report was available which was submitted to the SIDBI by Entrepreneurship Development Institute of India. This report gives exhaustive information about the evolution of the leather cluster in Kolkata. Further important information was gathered from the (Association, 2022) (*About – Calcutta Leather Complex Tanners Association*, n.d.), (CSIR-Central Leather Research Institute, n.d.), (Acharya, 2019), and (Roy et al., 2013).

The history of the Kolkata leather industry may be traced back to the 1910s, when an entrepreneurial chemistry graduate, Mr. B.M.Das, became interested in leather tanning. The Bengal Tanning Industries was soon founded in the city. The National Tanning Company Limited was founded by a British group who were fast to follow the trend and brought machinery from England to begin making finished leather. Raw hides and skins were previously sent to Italy and Spain, but following the creation of two leather processing plants, completed leather exports began.

Before independence in 1940, many Chinese people relocated to the city and worked in tanneries and shoe factories. They quickly established their own tanneries in what is today known as Tangra. During the post-independence years of 1972-73, the Indian government established the Sitarammaya Committee which recommended the export of value-added

leather goods rather than wet blue and semi-finished leather. This was a watershed moment for the Kolkata leather cluster, since it saw the emergence of manufacturing facilities for many leather products, and the cluster has never looked back. The former Soviet Union had been the cluster's main export market, but following the disintegration of the Soviet Union this market declined while other European markets grew stronger.

The Government of West Bengal established the Calcutta Leather Complex on the outskirts of Kolkata. All operations relating to the leather industry are expected to be housed there. The tanneries have a daily processing capacity of 1,000 tonnes of raw hides, and the complex will produce around US\$ 1,100 million in exports and 10,000 jobs when it is fully operational.

Another turning point in Kolkata's leather footwear sector occurred in 1936, when Bata Limited, a Czech business, began producing shoes at Batanagar, and Kolkata soon became the centre of all footwear activity. The industry also gradually entered other locations in the country, such as Kanpur, Delhi, and Chennai.

The construction of FREYA, a design development centre as part of the UNDP project, was one of the early initiatives in the Calcutta leather cluster. For the improvement of the tanneries and the cluster, a UNIDO project was also executed. Under the UNIDO-supported Consolidated Project on SME Development in India, interventions have been made in the Shantiniketan leather cluster as well.

MSMEDI has also worked on the Shantiniketan leather cluster as part of a UNIDO initiative. A skill development activity is being planned and will be conducted soon under the National Leather Development Programme of the DIPP led by the Ministry of Commerce and Industry.

Kolkata's 500 tanneries are mostly concentrated in the Tangra, Tiljala, and Topsia neighbourhoods. These neighbourhoods were originally on the fringes of Kolkata and became densely inhabited places over time as the city expanded rapidly. As a result, these communities' tanneries were unable to grow, modernise, or create an adequate solid and water waste management system. This posed major challenges for the tanneries as well as residents of the surrounding areas.

To address this issue, the West Bengal government decided in 1992 to transfer all tanneries in the city to a new complex. This facility would be developed using cutting-edge technology and would include a CETP (Common Effluent Treatment Plant) to manage and treat the tanneries' wastewater and solid waste. To fulfil this aim, a parcel of land of 438 hectares was found just beyond the city's eastern borders. The Calcutta Leather Complex was formed because of this. The Calcutta Leather Complex is a self-contained facility that caters to all the tanneries that are housed there. This entails the provision of energy and water, as well as the removal of waste (*About – Calcutta Leather Complex Tanners Association*, n.d.).

5.2.2 To study the effect of the cluster on the growth of units in all respects.

This objective was achieved in section 4.4 and section 4.5. The findings suggests that the presence of the leather cluster does have a significant impact on the factors affecting growth. Specifically, the factors of financial support, government policy support, government programs, research and development, commercial and legal infrastructure, internal market openness, and physical infrastructure are significantly impacted differently by the existence and support of the leather cluster. The average scores for factors provide significant insights, indicating that commercial and legal infrastructure emerges as the most crucial factor in driving growth when supported by a cluster. This finding highlights the importance of having a robust and well-structured commercial and legal framework to enhance the overall performance and competitiveness of the leather industry cluster. Following commercial and legal infrastructure, financial support emerges as the second most influential factor in fostering cluster development. The availability of adequate financial resources plays a pivotal role in encouraging entrepreneurship, investment, and innovation within the cluster. This finding highlights the significance of ensuring easy access to funding and financial assistance for businesses operating within the leather cluster. Additionally, government policy support is identified as another key factor affecting the cluster's growth. This emphasizes the role of favourable policies and incentives provided by the government to create an enabling environment for businesses to flourish within the leather cluster. Supportive policies can stimulate business activities, attract investments, and foster a conducive ecosystem for sustainable development. The

results indicate that when there is strong government policy backing for sustainable practices and waste management, it positively impacts the overall growth and development of the leather industry. This ensures that tanneries and leather processing units should adopt measures to reduce pollution, properly manage waste, and minimize the ecological footprint of their operations. Furthermore, government policies that support research and development initiatives related to environmental sustainability can lead to the creation and adoption of innovative solutions for waste management and pollution control. This, in turn, can positively influence the leather industry's image in both domestic and international markets, enhancing its reputation as an environmentally responsible and socially conscious sector.

The findings for the pair of factors financial Support and government policy support show they do not exhibit statistically significant differences in terms of their factor scores. This implies that the level of financial support received by the leather units and the support provided by government policies have a relatively consistent impact on the development and growth of the leather cluster. The findings reveal for the pair of factors government policy support and government programmes do not exhibit statistically significant differences in terms of their factor scores. This indicates that the support provided by government policies and the specific government programmes implemented within the leather cluster have a similar and consistent impact on the industry's growth and development. Moreover, the findings indicate that the pair of factors government programmes and R&D do not exhibit statistically significant differences in terms of their factor scores. This suggests that the impact of government programmes and investments in research and development within the leather cluster are comparable in influencing the industry's growth and development. The convergence of government programmes and research and development efforts implies a potential synergy between policy-driven initiatives and innovation-driven activities. The findings reveal a clear and significant difference between the pair of factors R&D and CLI in terms of their factor scores. This finding is noteworthy as it highlights the pivotal role of both research and development activities and the availability of a robust commercial and legal infrastructure in shaping the industry's trajectory. The significance of research and development efforts signifies

that investments in innovation, technology, and product development are key drivers of competitiveness and market relevance for leather businesses within the cluster. On the other hand, the significance of commercial and legal infrastructure suggests that having a well-established framework for trade, commerce, and legal operations fosters an enabling environment for business growth, market access, and compliance with regulations. By addressing the distinct impacts of R&D and CLI, the leather cluster can capitalize on its unique strengths, nurture innovation, and enhance its overall competitiveness in the global market. The compelling findings highlight the highly significant differences between the pair of factors CLI and IMO in terms of their factor scores. Internal market openness signifies the ease with which leather products can be traded within the country, the extent of regulatory barriers faced, and the level of market access for the cluster's products in different regions. This finding highlights the importance of streamlining domestic distribution channels, understanding consumer preferences, and adapting marketing strategies to cater to the diverse domestic market segments. Furthermore, the findings highlight a significant difference between IMO and PI in terms of their impact on the leather cluster. The significant impact of PI highlights the crucial role of robust physical infrastructure in supporting the cluster's operations. Adequate physical infrastructure, such as well-connected transportation networks, reliable power supply, and efficient logistics, are essential for smooth production and distribution of leather products within the country. Improved physical infrastructure enhances supply chain efficiency, reduces transportation costs, and fosters timely product delivery, all of which positively influence the cluster's overall productivity and cost-effectiveness. These findings suggest that for sustained growth and development, the leather cluster must strike a balance between leveraging internal market opportunities and investing in upgrading its physical infrastructure. A holistic approach that emphasizes both the development of domestic market access and the strengthening of local infrastructure will enhance the cluster's resilience and long-term competitiveness.

5.2.3 To determine if the cluster helps equally in the development of all products.

This objective was achieved in section 4.4 and section 4.5. The findings reveal that the scores for the different products show statistically significant differences. Additionally, the mean scores for the factors also exhibit significant variations. The footwear leather product emerges as the most prominent segment within the leather cluster, followed closely by bags, it signifies their strong performance and potential for growth with the support of the cluster. This prominence suggests that footwear and bags have been particularly successful in harnessing the benefits offered by the cluster's resources, infrastructure, and collective efforts. The cluster's collaborative environment likely provides advantages such as access to skilled labour, specialized knowledge, shared resources, and opportunities for innovation and technological advancements. The two leading segments, footwear and bags are likely driving the cluster's overall growth and development.

As the bag production segment represents a significant portion of the leather industry, it becomes even more crucial to ensure that these units are well-equipped to thrive within the cluster, driving sustainable and inclusive development for the entire leather ecosystem. Moreover, there is no statistically significant difference among units that are involved in the production of finished leather. This finding suggests that the leather cluster's support and influence may not have a significant impact on the growth and development of units engaged in this specific segment of the leather industry. As it may imply that the cluster's resources, schemes, or policies may not be optimally benefiting the units in the finished leather production category. This finding highlights the need for careful consideration and targeted interventions to enhance the support and effectiveness of the leather cluster for units engaged in finished leather production. For wallet products, the finding suggests that the support and impact of the cluster on wallet-producing units are relatively uniform across various factors. While this may signify a level of consistency and balanced support within the segment, it also points to certain implications that assure consideration. Despite the absence of significant differences for a wallet product, it is crucial to recognize that individual wallet units may still face specific challenges and opportunities that necessitate

targeted attention. Wallet production holds a valuable position in the leather industry, and understanding the distinct needs and growth potential of each unit is pivotal for driving overall cluster development.

Thus, footwear and bag segments thrive within the cluster, they can act as role models and sources of inspiration for other units, fostering a sense of healthy competition and encouraging other leather businesses to improve their practices and strategies. This virtuous cycle can elevate the overall performance of the leather industry within the cluster, benefiting all units and contributing to the cluster's reputation and attractiveness in the global market.

5.2.4 To study if the cluster helps in the development of units of different sizes.

This objective was achieved in section 4.4 and section 4.5. The two-way analysis of the cluster's impact on important factors and unit scale reveals fascinating insights into the relationship between investment levels and factor scores. These findings highlight the influence of unit size and financial resources on the factors contributing to growth and development within the leather cluster. The data suggests that medium-scale units, falling within the investment range of 1.1 to 2.2 million INR, are particularly well-positioned to leverage the benefits offered by the cluster. These units are likely benefiting from the cluster's resources, sharing knowledge, and access to skilled labor, thereby experiencing higher factor scores and growth prospects compared to units with different investment scales. The data affirms the significant influence of the leather cluster on the growth and development of units with varying fixed capital investments. The findings serve as a valuable guide for the cluster's stakeholders to devise targeted strategies, ensuring equitable growth opportunities for all unit scales and further enhancing the cluster's overall performance and competitiveness.

For small-scale units, the findings highlight the significance of the cluster's role in their growth and sustenance. Despite having lower fixed capital investment, these units benefit from the cluster's collective strength, which enables them to access resources that might be otherwise challenging for individual small units to obtain. By fostering a supportive

environment for small-scale units, the cluster can ensure their continued growth and active participation in the industry.

Thus, the findings emphasize the pivotal role played by the leather cluster in influencing the factors contributing to unit growth, regardless of their scale and fixed capital investment. By leveraging the insights gained from this analysis, the cluster's stakeholders can design targeted strategies and policies to promote the growth of medium and small-scale units, further enhancing the cluster's overall competitiveness and sustainable development.

5.2.5 To investigate the interplay of indicators with firmographics.

This objective was achieved in section 4.6. The findings from the figures presented in the analysis reveal significant insights about the Kolkata leather cluster and its impact on the manufacturing units. Footwear manufacturing units emerge as the dominant sector in terms of employee strength, with 20 units employing over 200 employees, indicating a labour-intensive manufacturing process. The distribution of employees across fixed investment classes shows that units with the lowest and highest investment levels have higher employee concentrations, while medium investment level units may rely on less labour-intensive techniques or have limited demand and scale.

Regarding investment requirements, footwear and bag manufacturing units demand substantial fixed investment, possibly due to the adoption of modern techniques by small and medium units. The establishment of footwear and finished leather manufacturing units started from 1981 up until 2015, with trends being relatively unpredictable for each type of product. However, the establishment of small and medium units occurred in tandem, reflecting the positive impact of the cluster and a supportive value chain.

The ranking of different factors for units manufacturing different products shows that financial support and government policy support are equally highly ranked by units manufacturing finished leather. Additionally, the results highlight that units with fixed investments of over 3 million INR prioritize financial support, government programs, commercial and legal infrastructure, and internal market openness, indicating the

expectations rise with larger unit scale. Conversely, smaller units desire more support from the cluster and government intervention as they perceive the support factors to have less effect than their expectations. This suggests that the cluster plays a vital role in supporting different unit scales and products but needs to address varying needs and expectations of units based on their size and development stage.

5.3 Limitations

Every research has a specific scope and various limitations. The geographical scope of this study is limited to the city of Kolkata. The researcher endeavoured to interact with small entrepreneurs, experts, and other stakeholders about the emergence and impact of the cluster and its sustenance, progress, and prospects. The research succeeded in fulfilling the set objectives but, as in every study, it has its limitations. This research has the six major limitations mentioned below.

5.3.1 Limitations of Sample size

The sample size was originally set at 200 units for the survey, and the initial intention was to conduct 20 in-depth interviews. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic and lockdowns in the region, this sample size could not be attained. However, responses from 74 heads of units were received in the survey and 5 entrepreneurs were interviewed. A larger survey sample and more in-depth interviews would undoubtedly allow better insights. Regarding the adequacy of the results in achieving the research objectives, the statistical power of the sample size can be considered. A sample size of 74 is sufficient for identifying general trends and patterns in the data, although it may not be large enough for more detailed analyses or detecting smaller effects. However, the qualitative data from the in-depth interviews with five heads of units can provide valuable insights that complement the quantitative findings, helping to address the research objectives. There may be potential truncation bias due to the low response rate and sampling method, the results may still be considered adequate in achieving the research objectives. However, it is important to acknowledge these limitations in the study and to interpret the findings with caution, keeping in mind the potential for bias. Future research may aim to address these limitations

by employing different sampling techniques or increasing the sample size to ensure a more representative sample of the leather industry cluster in Kolkata.

5.3.2 Lack of relevant literature

While exploring research articles, books, and reports of studies focusing on the Kolkata leather cluster, it was realised that there is a dearth of relevant material. Although there are web pages and v-logs available, they are in the local languages and their reliability is questionable. However, although the researcher collected data from available research articles, news articles, and YouTube videos, there is a heavy dependence on a small number of studies for the qualitative analysis. At the same time, this makes lack of relevant literature for this study.

5.3.3 Pandemic and lockdowns

Apart from the restricted sample size, the COVID pandemic and lockdowns have impacted heavily on the routine functioning of small units. Lay-offs, reduced sales, logistical issues, a working capital crunch, and other such turbulence has affected many of the small and medium-sized units. The data collected here could be misleading in the sense that it may have been seriously influenced by these difficult times. A study conducted at any normal time might have yielded different and hopefully better pictures for the same groups.

5.3.4 Cluster Impact

As mentioned above, because of the pandemic and lockdowns the units had to bear the loss. Communication had its own challenges, and this hampered the support offered due to the cluster. During informal discussion with stakeholders this came up regularly, and the cluster's effect was thus more difficult to assess.

5.3.5 Dimensions studied

One of the limitations of the thesis is the absence of comprehensive data on exports and revenue for the units within the Kolkata leather cluster. While survey data for the number of employees and fixed investment levels could be collected, the lack of information on exports and revenue poses a challenge in fully understanding the financial and market

performance of the units. In-person interactions with the units could potentially provide more reliable data for these criteria. The available published data on exports and revenues are either outdated or not specified for different product types, making it difficult to assess the overall economic impact and competitiveness of the cluster. Despite the thorough analysis of other factors, the limited data on exports and revenue might restrict a comprehensive evaluation of the cluster's overall success and its contribution to the regional economy. Future research efforts could aim to address this limitation by seeking more up-to-date and specific data on exports and revenue from the units within the cluster.

5.3.6 Limitation of environmental considerations and sustainability

A notable limitation of this thesis is the exclusion of environmental considerations related to the leather manufacturing and related industries within the Kolkata leather cluster. Due to limited time and restricted access to information and relevant stakeholders, the study could not delve into the environmental impact of leather production processes. Leather manufacturing involves various pre-tanning and tanning procedures that utilize a significant amount of chemicals and water, leading to wastewater discharge. The properties of the waste streams vary depending on the type of treatment used, such as vegetable or chrome tanning, and can have environmental implications. Despite the absence of an in-depth analysis of environmental factors, it is worth mentioning that government policies and programs could potentially influence the cluster's development in terms of environmental regulations and water waste management. By enforcing policies that encourage sustainable practices and environmental responsibility, the government can play a crucial role in shaping the cluster's growth in an environmentally conscious manner.

5.4 Implications

A business cluster is a geographic concentration of related enterprises, suppliers, and associated organisations. Clusters are thought to boost company productivity, allowing them to compete on a national and global scale. Research studies on clusters pays attention to the units involved, the geographic location, the problems faced, and the prospects for

the business. The findings of this research study have several implications for the development and growth of the Kolkata Leather Cluster which are discussed as below:

- The research highlights the significant impact of various factors on cluster development, with commercial and legal infrastructure emerging as the most favourable factor with cluster support. This implies that policymakers and industry stakeholders should focus on improving the legal and regulatory environment, providing easy access to business support services, and creating a favourable commercial environment to attract more units to the cluster. Additionally, the study highlights the importance of differentiating product categories within the cluster. Footwear and bags were identified as the most successful segments, indicating that targeted efforts should be made to promote and support these high-potential product categories.
- The research provides valuable insights into the importance of unit scale and fixed investment in cluster development. Medium-sized units were found to have the highest average scores for factors, indicating their potential for growth and success. Policymakers should consider providing tailored support and incentives for medium-sized units to foster their development and expansion. Moreover, the study highlights the need for addressing the financial challenges faced by small-scale units with lower fixed investments, which can be achieved through targeted financial assistance programs and capacity-building initiatives.
- The qualitative analysis of interviews provided rich insights into the perceptions and experiences of industry experts and entrepreneurs within the cluster. Policymakers can utilize this information to address the specific needs and expectations of the units and design policies that resonate with the cluster's collective vision and goals.
- The research highlights the importance of sustainable growth and innovation within the cluster. By understanding the factors that drive growth, policymakers can implement strategies that foster innovation, technology adoption, and skill development. Encouraging research and development activities and facilitating

collaborations between units can lead to the development of new and improved products, positioning the cluster as a hub of innovative leather goods.

- The study's findings and methodology can serve as a framework for analyzing and promoting the growth of business clusters in other industries and regions. The factors identified in this research as critical for cluster development may be applicable to other clusters, enabling policymakers to develop tailored interventions and policies based on specific industry needs and regional contexts.

5.5 Conclusion

The case study of Kolkata Leather Cluster has been an interesting and insightful journey. There are two major areas of learnings achieved in the study. Firstly, the analysis of information from the existing literature and the primary data collected have made it clear that the cluster is persistent and able to fight back in the face of havoc like the pandemic. Despite their difficulties and troubles, there are units which have been functioning on a modest scale for more than three decades. Secondly, the awareness and expectations from the government and other units in the business is remarkable. Also, clarity about the market and facilities is appreciable. With reference to the research objectives, the study has concluded that the various influential factors affect the growth and development of units differently, and different products are differently catered to by the cluster and policy interventions. Strengthening the cluster's support mechanisms, providing skill development programs, and facilitating knowledge exchange among units can create a vibrant ecosystem that fosters innovation, productivity, and long-term success for all participating units, ultimately driving the cluster's growth and prominence in the leather industry. Nevertheless, the overall conclusion is that the prospects for Kolkata's manufacturing of leather and related products are bright.

5.6 Future research recommendations

Although various aspects of the Kolkata leather industry have been considered in this thesis, there are several areas in which the current work could be extended as follows:

- Although many leather industry clusters have formed in India, future work could compare cluster-based development in regional clusters such as Uttar Pradesh and Tamil Nadu. Tamil Nadu is one of India's most industrialised states and Uttar Pradesh is also the fourth largest state in India with the largest industry related to leather goods.
- In addition to the five product types of industrial gloves, foot wears, wallets, handbags and finished leather, some other products such as harness and saddlery goods, safety boots, and leather garments could be explored.
- More extensive interviews could be conducted in a structured manner. Focus group discussions can also be used to explore the problems faced.
- The leather products industry relies heavily on export marketing. Italy, Spain, Germany, and the United Kingdom are the importers of leather products. For the leather industry, the worldwide economic recession is a major issue, because manufacturers rely on exports for the growth of business. Therefore, the case study of leather industries can be extended to explore the export sales of leather clusters and industries.
- Diversification within the leather industry can enhance its resilience and sustainability, reducing the risk of over-reliance on specific products. The cluster's supportive ecosystem should strive to identify opportunities for growth and development in other segments, fostering a well-rounded and dynamic leather industry that can withstand market fluctuations and capitalize on emerging trends.
- Future research could explore the environmental aspects of the cluster and consider its sustainability implications to gain a comprehensive understanding of the industry's impact on the environment and the potential for sustainable growth within the cluster.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Questionnaire

Table 0-1 : Questionnaire

No	Question	Strongly Agree	6	5	4	3	2	Strongly Disagree
Financial Support								
1	Being a part of cluster, there is sufficient equity funding available for new and growing firms							
2	Cluster helps in debt funding							
3	Cluster helps availing government subsidies							
4	Venture capitalists invest more enthusiastically for cluster members							
Government Policy Support								
5	Government policies are consistent for cluster							
6	Support for cluster members are at priority							

7 Licensing and permits can be easily obtained for cluster members

8 Cluster membership is favourable for tax rates

9 Tax and regulations are consistent for cluster members

10 Government policies are effective, for cluster development

Government Programs

11 Government assistance is available with single point contact, for cluster members

12 Business incubators provide effective support for cluster members

13 There are an adequate number of government programs

14 Government agencies are competent and effective in supporting cluster

15 Government programs aimed at supporting clusters

Research and Development

16 New technology, science and knowledge is easily transferred to cluster members

17 Because of clusters, new and growing units can easily access new research and technologies

18 Cluster makes latest technologies more affordable

19 Cluster supports commercialization of new ideas

Commercial and Legal Infrastructure

20 Supply chain, consultancy, and contractors are easily available because of Cluster

21 The cost of availing their services are affordable to cluster members

22 Access to good subcontractors, suppliers, and consultants is easy due to cluster

23 Access to good professional, legal, and accounting services is easy due to cluster

24 Banking services are easily accessible due to cluster

Internal Market Openness

25 Consumer goods and services markets change from year to year

- 26 B2B goods and services markets change from year to year
- 27 Cluster makes new market entry easy for the members
- 28 Cluster makes new market entry affordable for the members
- 29 Cluster reduces barriers to new market entries

Physical Infrastructure

- 30 Cluster helps units set up a good physical infrastructure
- 31 Cluster makes the good access to communication affordable
- 32 Cluster makes the utilities more affordable for the members
- 33 Cluster makes the utilities easily available for the members

Appendix 2: Survey Data

Table 0-2: Survey Data for Q-1 to Q-10

Sr	Cluster	Employees	Inception	FixedCapital	Q - 1	Q - 2	Q - 3	Q - 4	FS	Q - 5	Q - 6	Q - 7	Q - 8	Q - 9	Q - 10	GPS
1	Finished Leather	35	1993	2038	5	7	6	6	6.00	6	4	4	4	3	4	4.17
2	Footwear	433	2011	1139	4	4	4	4	4.00	3	5	5	5	5	4	4.50
3	Bags	18	1982	2205	5	6	6	6	5.75	6	6	6	6	6	6	6.00
4	Bags	20	2003	2161	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
5	Finished Leather	35	1984	1946	3	4	4	4	3.75	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
6	Bags	25	1990	1041	3	4	4	4	3.75	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
7	Bags	18	2009	1647	3	2	2	2	2.25	3	3	3	3	3	3	3.00
8	Finished Leather	42	2006	1262	2	3	3	3	2.75	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
9	Wallets	107	2004	2260	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	5	5	5	5	4	4.67
10	Bags	22	1988	1368	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
11	Footwear	500	2005	1706	2	3	3	3	2.75	4	5	5	5	5	5	4.83
12	Footwear	485	2004	3087	5	4	4	4	4.25	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
13	Footwear	484	1983	2201	4	5	5	5	4.75	4	5	5	5	5	5	4.83
14	Bags	21	2003	2024	4	5	5	5	4.75	2	2	2	2	3	2	2.17

15	Footwear	471	2002	3090	4	5	5	5	4.75	2	3	2	3	3	2	2.50
16	Footwear	486	2003	437	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
17	Bags	23	2005	1744	5	5	5	5	5.00	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
18	Footwear	498	2001	537	4	4	4	4	4.00	3	4	4	4	4	4	3.83
19	Bags	21	1986	868	5	5	5	5	5.00	3	4	4	4	4	4	3.83
20	Finished Leather	31	1988	87	4	4	4	4	4.00	6	6	6	6	5	6	5.83
21	Footwear	493	1988	792	2	2	2	2	2.00	5	5	5	4	4	5	4.67
22	Footwear	459	1993	1516	4	5	4	4	4.25	3	3	3	3	3	3	3.00
23	Footwear	467	2008	1680	3	4	4	4	3.75	3	3	3	3	4	3	3.17
24	Footwear	472	1989	2259	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	4	4	4	4	4	4.17
25	Finished Leather	38	2002	64	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
26	Footwear	213	1983	616	5	5	5	5	5.00	4	4	4	4	3	4	3.83
27	Finished Leather	42	2004	1743	4	3	3	3	3.25	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
28	Bags	21	1994	2877	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	5	5	5	5	5	4.83
29	Wallets	83	1982	2535	3	4	4	4	3.75	6	5	5	5	5	5	5.17
30	Bags	17	1985	2025	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	4	4	4	3	4	3.83
31	Bags	20	1994	651	4	5	5	5	4.75	3	3	3	3	3	3	3.00
32	Wallets	46	2004	3290	5	5	5	5	5.00	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00

33	Wallets	75	1985	1416	3	4	4	4	3.75	3	2	2	2	2	2	2.17
34	Finished Leather	42	2008	675	3	4	4	4	3.75	3	2	2	2	2	2	2.17
35	Finished Leather	45	1999	1037	5	4	4	4	4.25	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
36	Finished Leather	19	1996	1962	4	6	6	6	5.50	6	5	5	5	5	5	5.17
37	Wallets	50	1982	2577	3	4	3	3	3.25	5	4	4	4	4	4	4.17
38	Wallets	26	1987	623	3	3	3	3	3.00	4	5	4	5	5	4	4.50
39	Finished Leather	15	2010	1709	5	5	5	5	5.00	4	3	3	3	3	3	3.17
40	Bags	25	1991	1178	4	3	4	4	3.75	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
41	Finished Leather	14	1987	1289	6	6	6	6	6.00	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
42	Wallets	82	1982	1052	3	4	4	4	3.75	4	5	5	5	5	5	4.83
43	Finished Leather	13	1997	2629	4	6	6	6	5.50	3	4	4	4	5	4	4.00
44	Finished Leather	50	1999	1779	4	3	3	3	3.25	3	3	3	3	2	3	2.83
45	Wallets	26	2002	2111	5	5	5	5	5.00	4	5	4	5	5	4	4.50
46	Bags	8	1987	2343	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
47	Footwear	233	2000	2043	6	6	6	6	6.00	3	3	3	3	3	3	3.00
48	Bags	25	2006	2597	3	2	2	2	2.25	4	3	3	3	3	4	3.33
49	Footwear	230	2003	1503	3	3	3	3	3.00	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
50	Bags	9	2012	2302	2	3	3	3	2.75	3	3	3	3	3	3	3.00

51	Footwear	333	1984	851	5	5	5	5	5.00	3	4	4	4	4	4	3.83
52	Wallets	47	2010	127	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	4	4	4	4	4	4.17
53	Wallets	97	1992	2841	3	3	3	3	3.00	5	4	4	4	4	4	4.17
54	Footwear	431	2003	1576	4	4	4	4	4.00	3	3	3	3	3	3	3.00
55	Finished Leather	33	1998	1649	3	4	4	4	3.75	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
56	Footwear	369	2002	1363	2	3	2	3	2.50	3	3	3	3	3	3	3.00
57	Wallets	27	2008	2682	4	5	4	4	4.25	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
58	Footwear	90	1996	2120	4	3	3	3	3.25	5	5	5	4	4	5	4.67
59	Footwear	346	2010	2123	4	5	5	5	4.75	5	4	5	4	4	5	4.50
60	Footwear	355	2004	1019	3	4	4	4	3.75	4	5	5	5	5	5	4.83
61	Bags	22	1991	1187	4	3	3	3	3.25	3	4	4	4	4	4	3.83
62	Bags	21	1993	1079	5	5	5	5	5.00	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
63	Wallets	82	1990	928	5	4	4	4	4.25	3	4	4	4	4	4	3.83
64	Footwear	333	1982	1025	5	5	5	5	5.00	4	5	5	5	5	5	4.83
65	Wallets	82	1995	1537	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
66	Footwear	119	1989	1442	5	5	5	5	5.00	5	4	5	4	4	5	4.50
67	Wallets	128	2001	1380	5	5	5	5	5.00	2	2	2	2	2	2	2.00
68	Bags	21	2010	1488	5	5	5	5	5.00	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.00

69	Wallets	193	1990	2011	3	4	3	4	3.50	7	5	5	5	4	5	5.17
70	Finished Leather	17	1983	787	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
71	Bags	30	1985	1808	3	3	3	3	3.00	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
72	Wallets	41	1988	1562	5	6	6	6	5.75	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
73	Industrial Gloves	4	1988	233	4	3	3	3	3.25	3	3	3	3	3	3	3.00
74	Bags	32	2010	2124	5	4	4	4	4.25	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.00

Table 0-3: Survey Data for Q-11 to 24

Sr	Q - 11	Q - 12	Q - 13	Q - 14	Q - 15	GP	Q - 16	Q - 17	Q - 18	Q - 19	R&D	Q - 20	Q - 21	Q - 22	Q - 23	Q - 24	CLI
1	3	4	4	4	4	3.80	5	4	4	4	4.25	4	2	2	2	2	2.40
2	5	5	4	5	5	4.80	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	5	4	4	4	4.40
3	5	4	4	4	4	4.20	5	5	5	5	5.00	6	5	5	5	5	5.20
4	5	5	5	5	5	5.00	4	4	4	4	4.00	3	3	3	3	3	3.00
5	5	5	4	5	5	4.80	5	6	6	6	5.75	6	6	6	6	6	6.00
6	3	4	4	4	3	3.60	5	6	6	6	5.75	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
7	2	3	3	3	3	2.80	3	4	4	4	3.75	3	3	3	3	3	3.00

8	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	2	3	3	3	2.75	4	3	3	3	3	3.20
9	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	4	4	4	4.25	5	4	4	4	4	4.20
10	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	5	5	5	5	5.00	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
11	5	5	5	5	5	5.00	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
12	5	5	5	5	5	5.00	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	6	6	6	6	5.80
13	6	6	6	6	6	6.00	4	2	2	2	2.50	3	3	3	3	3	3.00
14	4	3	3	3	3	3.20	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	5	5	5	5	4.80
15	4	5	5	5	5	4.80	5	3	3	3	3.50	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
16	6	4	4	4	4	4.40	3	4	4	4	3.75	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
17	6	5	5	5	5	5.20	4	3	3	3	3.25	3	4	4	4	4	3.80
18	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	4	4	4	4.00	6	5	5	4	5	5.00
19	2	3	3	3	3	2.80	4	5	5	5	4.75	3	3	4	4	3	3.40
20	4	3	3	3	4	3.40	3	4	4	4	3.75	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
21	4	4	3	4	4	3.80	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	4	4	4	4	4.20
22	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	3	5	5	5	4.50	3	5	5	5	5	4.60
23	5	5	5	5	5	5.00	4	4	4	4	4.00	6	5	5	5	5	5.20
24	2	3	3	3	3	2.80	4	4	4	4	4.00	1	2	3	3	3	2.40
25	5	4	4	4	4	4.20	5	5	5	5	5.00	5	4	4	4	4	4.20

26	5	4	4	4	4	4.20	3	4	4	4	3.75	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
27	2	2	2	2	2	2.00	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
28	5	5	5	5	5	5.00	4	5	5	5	4.75	6	6	6	6	6	6.00
29	5	4	4	4	4	4.20	5	5	5	5	5.00	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
30	4	5	5	5	5	4.80	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
31	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	2	3	3	3	2.75	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
32	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	4	3	3	3	3.25	6	5	5	5	5	5.20
33	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	4	3	4	3.75	5	4	4	4	4	4.20
34	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	2	2	2	2	2.00	3	3	3	3	3	3.00
35	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	4	4	4	4.25	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
36	6	4	4	4	5	4.60	4	5	5	5	4.75	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
37	4	5	5	5	5	4.80	4	3	3	3	3.25	2	3	3	3	3	2.80
38	4	3	3	3	3	3.20	4	5	5	4	4.50	5	5	5	4	5	4.80
39	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	3	3	3	3.50	6	5	4	4	4	4.60
40	5	4	4	4	4	4.20	3	3	3	3	3.00	4	5	5	5	5	4.80
41	5	4	4	4	4	4.20	5	4	4	4	4.25	3	2	2	2	2	2.20
42	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	3	4	4	4	3.75	4	3	3	3	3	3.20
43	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	4	5	5	5	4.75	4	4	4	4	4	4.00

44	2	2	2	2	2	2.00	3	4	4	4	3.75	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
45	5	3	3	3	3	3.40	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
46	3	4	4	4	4	3.80	3	4	4	4	3.75	5	6	6	6	6	5.80
47	5	4	4	4	4	4.20	2	3	3	3	2.75	2	3	3	3	3	2.80
48	6	4	4	4	4	4.40	5	4	4	4	4.25	6	6	6	6	6	6.00
49	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	5	5	5	5.00	3	4	4	4	4	3.80
50	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	4	4	4	4.25	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
51	4	3	3	3	3	3.20	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	5	5	5	5	4.80
52	3	4	4	4	4	3.80	3	4	4	4	3.75	6	5	5	5	5	5.20
53	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	5	5	5	5.00	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
54	4	5	5	5	5	4.80	3	5	5	5	4.50	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
55	3	4	5	4	4	4.00	3	4	4	4	3.75	5	5	5	5	5	5.00
56	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	4	4	4	4.25	6	5	5	5	5	5.20
57	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	6	4	4	4	4.50	5	4	4	4	4	4.20
58	4	3	3	3	3	3.20	5	3	3	3	3.50	3	3	3	4	3	3.20
59	4	3	2	3	3	3.00	4	4	3	4	3.75	3	4	4	4	4	3.80
60	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	6	6	6	5.75	5	6	6	6	6	5.80
61	4	3	3	3	3	3.20	4	5	5	5	4.75	3	3	3	3	3	3.00

62	5	6	6	6	6	5.80	5	4	4	4	4.25	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
63	3	4	4	4	4	3.80	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	5	5	5	5	4.80
64	3	5	5	5	5	4.60	2	3	3	3	2.75	5	5	4	4	4	4.40
65	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	3	3	3	3	3.00	6	5	5	5	5	5.20
66	5	5	5	5	5	5.00	6	5	5	6	5.50	3	3	3	3	3	3.00
67	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	3	4	4	4	3.75	4	3	3	3	3	3.20
68	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	5	5	5	5.00	4	3	3	3	3	3.20
69	4	5	5	5	5	4.80	5	4	4	4	4.25	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
70	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	2	4	4	4	3.50	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
71	5	4	4	4	4	4.20	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
72	5	4	4	4	4	4.20	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	4	4	4	4	4.00
73	4	5	5	5	5	4.80	5	4	4	4	4.25	4	5	5	5	5	4.80
74	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	3	4	4	4	3.75	5	4	4	4	4	4.20

Table 0-4: Survey Data for Q-25 and Q-33

Sr	Q - 25	Q - 26	Q - 27	Q - 28	Q - 29	IMO	Q - 30	Q - 31	Q - 32	Q - 33	PI
1	3	4	4	4	4	3.80	3	3	3	3	3.00
2	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	6	6	5	5.25
3	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	5	5	5	5	5.00
4	6	5	5	5	5	5.20	3	3	3	3	3.00
5	4	3	3	4	3	3.40	4	5	5	4	4.50
6	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	3	4	4	4	3.75
7	3	4	3	3	3	3.20	5	5	5	5	5.00
8	5	5	5	5	5	5.00	3	4	4	4	3.75
9	3	4	4	4	4	3.80	5	5	5	5	5.00
10	3	4	4	4	4	3.80	2	3	3	3	2.75
11	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	5	4	5	5	4.75
12	4	5	5	5	5	4.80	4	4	4	4	4.00
13	3	4	4	3	4	3.60	4	5	5	5	4.75
14	3	4	4	3	4	3.60	3	3	3	3	3.00
15	5	4	4	4	4	4.20	5	5	5	5	5.00
16	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	4	4	4	4.25

17	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	6	6	6	6	6.00
18	3	4	4	4	4	3.80	4	4	4	4	4.00
19	2	3	3	3	3	2.80	4	4	4	4	4.00
20	4	5	5	5	5	4.80	4	5	5	5	4.75
21	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	3	3	3	3.50
22	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	5	5	5	4.75
23	4	5	5	5	5	4.80	4	3	3	3	3.25
24	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	4	4	4	4	4.00
25	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	2	4	4	4	3.50
26	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	3	2	2	2	2.25
27	4	3	3	3	3	3.20	5	5	5	5	5.00
28	5	4	4	4	4	4.20	5	5	5	5	5.00
29	5	4	4	4	4	4.20	4	5	5	5	4.75
30	3	2	2	2	2	2.20	4	5	5	5	4.75
31	3	2	2	2	2	2.20	5	4	4	5	4.50
32	4	3	3	3	3	3.20	2	2	2	2	2.00
33	5	4	4	4	4	4.20	2	3	3	3	2.75
34	4	2	2	3	2	2.60	3	4	3	3	3.25

35	4	5	5	5	5	4.80	4	3	3	3	3.25
36	3	2	2	2	2	2.20	6	4	4	4	4.50
37	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	5	5	5	5.00
38	4	3	3	3	3	3.20	3	2	2	2	2.25
39	2	3	3	3	3	2.80	3	5	5	5	4.50
40	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	3	2	2	2	2.25
41	5	4	4	4	4	4.20	5	5	5	5	5.00
42	6	5	5	5	5	5.20	4	5	5	5	4.75
43	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	4	3	3	3	3.25
44	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	5	4	4	4	4.25
45	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	3	5	5	4	4.25
46	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	4	3	4	4	3.75
47	5	5	5	5	5	5.00	3	3	3	3	3.00
48	4	5	5	4	5	4.60	4	4	4	4	4.00
49	4	3	3	4	3	3.40	4	4	4	4	4.00
50	3	4	4	4	4	3.80	3	3	3	3	3.00
51	5	5	5	5	5	5.00	4	4	4	4	4.00
52	4	5	5	5	5	4.80	2	4	4	3	3.25

53	3	2	2	2	2	2.20	3	4	4	3	3.50
54	3	4	4	4	4	3.80	5	4	4	4	4.25
55	4	3	3	4	3	3.40	3	4	4	4	3.75
56	6	5	5	5	5	5.20	3	3	3	3	3.00
57	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	4	4	5	4.50
58	2	1	1	1	1	1.20	4	3	3	3	3.25
59	6	5	5	5	5	5.20	3	4	4	4	3.75
60	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	4	4	4	4.25
61	1	2	2	2	2	1.80	3	4	4	4	3.75
62	3	4	4	4	4	3.80	4	4	4	4	4.00
63	4	3	3	3	3	3.20	3	4	4	4	3.75
64	2	3	3	2	2	2.40	7	5	5	5	5.50
65	3	3	3	3	3	3.00	4	4	4	4	4.00
66	4	3	3	3	3	3.20	3	3	3	3	3.00
67	6	5	5	5	5	5.20	3	4	4	4	3.75
68	4	3	3	3	3	3.20	3	3	3	3	3.00
69	5	4	4	4	4	4.20	5	5	5	5	5.00
70	5	5	5	5	5	5.00	6	7	7	7	6.75

71	4	6	6	5	6	5.40	2	3	3	2	2.50
72	5	4	4	4	4	4.20	5	4	4	5	4.50
73	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	5	4	4	4	4.25
74	4	4	4	4	4	4.00	6	4	4	5	4.75

Appendix 3: Interviews

UNIT 1

1. Please walk me through your journey as an entrepreneur and the owner of this business.

My father started this unit around 30 years ago. He worked as an employee in the leather unit earlier. We have been primarily into the processing of the raw material; I mean leather and other semi-finished goods for different leather products. We did not manufacture any finished goods. Our role has been more like an ancillary unit and supplier to other units who produce the finished goods especially the purse and the bags. I joined this business as an owner-manager almost 15 years ago. We have seen many ups and downs in this period. There have been very interesting time and also the challenging times – like the present Covid-19 challenges.

2. How do you see the developments and changes that has taken place in the leather industry in general in your firm as specific?

Our business has evolved over the years to meet the international standards that ensure the quality products. Automation has been adopted to the extent possible and feasible from the investment perspective. The best part has been the availability of the labour. There are more than 500 units and many tanneries. Hence, the skilled and semi-skilled labour has been always there at least in our case. One big development is the establishment of other support industries like Leather Chemicals, metal fittings, ancillary product suppliers. This has affected the overall leather industry in Kolkata. Our firm has been also evolved with the changes in the overall industry and the business practices. Many of us, have found that that the only way to survive is to stay together and help each other. Of course, we do compete with each other at all levels but for the collective benefits of the entire industry – you call it as cluster; we work together for a shared goal to make Kolkata and the surrounding leather industry resilient and sustainable.

The factories and the manufacturing units have achieved the international standards and met with the necessary compliances. Overall physical infrastructure has improved. The best

part is the access to the utilities and the technology, it has become more accessible and affordable.

3. How have you been benefited by the existence of the cluster? What are the different schemes of the government and / or association you have availed and been benefited by?

As I told you, we are an ancillary unit or a supplier to the other units who manufacture the finished goods. So, for us we have been benefited by the presence of the other leather products, footwear units. We have supplied to many firms in this cluster who in turn export their products to many countries. Physical proximity also enhances the trust and mutual cooperation. We have been doing business with the same units for many years which also helped us to understand their dealings and behaviour.

We have availed soft loans for the technology upgradation and modernization. The loans are facilitated by the government. We also participated in the trade fairs and exhibitions which are either subsidized or facilitated by the government. Some of the research work of government sponsored laboratories have also been useful.

Our association has organized various training programs and skill enhancement workshops. We also availed some of the benefits for the training of our employees. They have received various training and development programs under the different initiatives of the government.

The best part has been putting forward the common economic interest.

4. How have you seen your firm shaping up based on the cluster? How your business strategies have been influenced by the cluster impact?

This is interesting. When we are a part of the cluster. On one hand, we need to maintain our uniqueness as an individual entity and at the same time we need to be part of the overall leather industry. So, I must say, we have evolved with the evolution of the cluster. Some of the business decisions which are influenced by the cluster based thinking are the strategies and decisions around manufacturing processes, product quality, development of common standards and products. I must say our strategic planning is based on the outlook

of the overall cluster and the industry. We do not sell our output outside Koltaka Leather Cluster.

5. What are the different ways you see that the cluster could help you to improve your business competitiveness?

I think the best way to improve my unit's business competitiveness is by the value chain integration. I believe that if we have integrate the entire value chain of the leather products and the footwear. That will help everyone. There are few gaps that needs to be addressed. I also understand that knowledge about the emerging market trends and exposure to latest designs by way of knowledge sharing and training by the cluster could be of great help to individual units. Finally, on one hand we are independent and individual units but some of the problems are common to all and hence the cluster should be the voice of units and a representation should be make to the Government for the policy decisions.

UNIT 2

1. Please walk me through your journey as an entrepreneur and the owner of this business.

I started this unit as the assembly unit for the footwear and other leather products. Essentially, we are an assembling and branding firm. We also do contract manufacturing for other firms. It was a humble beginning with few workers. Now, I employ 100 workers and deploy automated machines. I borrowed a small business loan from the bank to start this unit and later on ploughed back the profits to build the infrastructure. Our product portfolio evolved over the years. At the moment, I focus more on the footwear and bags.

2. How do you see the developments and changes that has taken place in the leather industry in general in your firm as specific?

The big change is the sales process and the role of buyers. We witnessed a big shift towards the use of technology in the customer interactions. Product designs and many other aspects moved to the computer; which was done manually. I think automation and communication technology changed many things. We are connected to the world trends and buyers can reach out to us using many online platforms. The acceptance of the customers for the new designs has been remarkable. Earlier, customers were not open to accept new and trendy designs. Now that is not the case.

3. How have you been benefited by the existence of the cluster? What are the different schemes of the government and / or association you have availed and been benefited by?

The best part for our unit is the access to the other manufacturers. We do not manufacture all the components of the leather product, say the footwear. We can easily work with the other units to source the components and raw material that are available. Experimentation and new design development is also possible because of the clusters. More so in the case of the bags. For the commercialization of the design, we have been fortunate due to the presence of other units. I found the government policies very helpful for our business. Government sponsored and funded laboratories and design institutes have been very helpful in my business. Knowledge programs and exposure visits either subsidized or facilitated by the Government has been very useful to learn new trends in the footwear. The networking

events helped us to form new connections. These network and connections have helped to generate new business and also as a source of idea exchange.

4. How have you seen your firm shaping up based on the cluster? How your business strategies have been influenced by the cluster impact?

In the entire value chain, we are at a very interesting place. Cluster has brought a lot of standardization and common designs; which is good for the volume business but I think innovation in terms of the designs need different approach. Our business decisions around the design, sourcing, new product development, innovation, business development practices are influenced by the cluster impact. Pricing is an important decision that is also shaped because of the presence of the other units.

5. What are the different ways you see that the cluster could help you to improve your business competitiveness?

As an assembly unit, I think we need more of outsourced and low-cost business services say the commercial infrastructure. Though, some shared services are available but they are not very efficient. We need business services that are efficient as well as affordable. This will help us to focus on the core activities of the business and other services can be outsourced. This will also have impact on the cost competitiveness. Right now, bigger challenge is to compete on the costs. We deal with B2B buyers largely. We do not cater to the end users or the consumers directly. A mechanism to acquire customers and generate leads by some common firm could be great help. We can reduce on the cost of the marketing and sales. Our focus will be convert those leads and manufacture the products.

UNIT 3

1. Please walk me through your journey as an entrepreneur and the owner of this business.

Two decades ago, we realized that there are many manufactures who do not have scale and skill to look at the export market. They were either too small or they lacked the know-how or they could not complete the government formalities to acquire the export licence. This is when I saw the business opportunity to form a business unit that is exclusively an export house. We work with the units, the buyers and help them to navigate the export related

procedures. Our role is very important for the small units. There are many units in Kolkata who have availed our services. We also provide warehousing support besides the overall end-to-end solutions of the export services.

2. How do you see the developments and changes that has taken place in the leather industry in general in your firm as specific?

The big change is the acceptance of the 'Made in India' label. The buyers abroad have developed their trust in the Indian products. We have participated in many trade shows and exhibitions abroad and found that buyers are now very keen to procure leather products from India. Earlier, the products were raw material and hides; but not they are keener to buy the finished products. China has been a major competitor. For the real leather, however this is not the case. Buyers abroad have started realizing the significance of the Indian leather industry.

3. How have you been benefited by the existence of the cluster? What are the different schemes of the government and / or association you have availed and been benefited by?

We have availed export promotion schemes and soft loans from the Government. They have been very useful to finance the business operation. Government policy have been conducive for the exporters. There have been some glitches in the taxation related matters but it is becoming now easy to deal with.

4. How have you seen your firm shaping up based on the cluster? How your business strategies have been influenced by the cluster impact?

As an export house, we are more like a service business to the units in this cluster. Earlier, the risk-taking ability of the units was limited but in the past few years, I see that more and more units are now interested in export market due to its margin potential and sometimes the volume business also. We have promoted and advertised our business presence using the strength of the Kolkata leather cluster. It is now more efficient and agile due to the advancement in the communication technology.

5. What are the different ways you see that the cluster could help you to improve your business competitiveness?

Aggregation of demand is still a major problem. Sometimes due to the business rivalry, some units do not share the information that affects our business competitiveness. As an export house, we facilitate the units to access the global markets; but they need to trust us and help each other to make the overall proposition more competitive. We are competing with the other exporting countries like China and it is essential to ensure complete transparency and collaboration for gaining access of the international buyers. I think licencing and other government procedures also needs some revamping to make it fast and easy. This affects the process and shipment. Sometimes shipping is delayed due to such procedures. Though, overall policies are favourable due to strategic nature of the leather industry, the ground level processes and procedure need overhauling to achieve efficiency.

UNIT 4

1. Please walk me through your journey as an entrepreneur and the owner of this business.

We are a family firm with the presence in the end-to-end or the entire value chain of the leather industry. We do source some components and materials from the other manufacturers also. We evolved as an integrated player in this industry and the cluster over last three decades. The best part of the integrated unit is the control over the quality. However, this is sometimes a costly affair. Assembly units are more cost-effective. But, we think that a quality product is the outcome of the quality ingredients and we can control the output quality by the input quality.

2. How do you see the developments and changes that has taken place in the leather industry in general in your firm as specific?

One thing is the government policy and schemes. Overall, industry has seen any changes periodically to in the government policies. Our firm which is an integrated one finds this more relevant. Due to the cost of starting the business going down day by day, we have seen many new entrants in the business. They have expanded the industry but they also impacted the overall equilibrium of the industry. Role of China and Chinese companies has been very influential in the recent past in the Kolkata Leather cluster. See, many things are now mixed up; we import leather and leather products from China and process it or re-sell from here and those Chinese companies also source from here. So, it is very different and

highly competitive. We as a big and integrated player need to read these clues from the market.

3. How have you been benefited by the existence of the cluster? What are the different schemes of the government and / or association you have availed and been benefited by?

We have been benefited by the common research facility and the technology. We have also availed all the government schemes and benefits of the program launched from time to time. The major benefit has been the financial support for the upgradation of the technology, modernisation of the processes and export assistance. The government policies in the form of favourable export policies have helped us immensely. We also get help from other units from the cluster in terms of access to their infrastructure. It has been a collaborative way of competing with each other. We also found the soft loans and the government subsidies very useful. The issues of the pollution and the sustainability has been resolved by the intervention of the government. New leather complex will change the fate of the entire industry.

4. How have you seen your firm shaping up based on the cluster? How your business strategies have been influenced by the cluster impact?

When we started, we were few units, but over the years we expanded. New units sprung up and also opened up new possibilities. So, we have been very fortunate to begin at the initial stage when this cluster was emerging. We have influenced the cluster and got influenced by the cluster. I think our competitiveness is depended on the competitiveness of all the units. We need to work together and stay together. Over the years, design has been a critical decision that has been influenced by the cluster. Pricing power sometimes is not with the units but with the members of the clusters. Our sourcing strategies have also been impacted by the clusters.

5. What are the different ways you see that the cluster could help you to improve your business competitiveness?

We need to build a strong brand of Kolkata Leather Cluster. Today, in India every industry has clusters. So if you are an IT firm based out of Bangalore you are viewed differently by

your clients or buyers. Similarly, we need to brand and emerge as a quality player. See, government schemes and programs are there but very few are able to take real advantage of it. For us, we need relaxed taxation norms and generous financial support to remain competitive. I also think that quality perceptions should change which is the outcome of the product quality. As an individual unit, we may be quality conscious but somewhere the affiliation with the cluster also affect our identify. In the global market, besides price, the perception play a major role.

UNIT 5

1. Please walk me through your journey as an entrepreneur and the owner of this business.

We started as a tannery and soon realised that the real money lies in the finished products. Thus, we evolved as a focused unit manufacturing the footwear. We have been supplying to the big brands through contract manufacturing and help many retailers for their private labels. As focused player in the footwear, we have been exporting to many countries and also various Indian brands.

2. How do you see the developments and changes that has taken place in the leather industry in general in your firm as specific?

The adoption of international standards and aligning our processes accordingly is one of the biggest changes in our cluster. Overall, cluster has been benefited by the world class infrastructure in line with international compliance standards that has made the superior quality products. Footwear is fashion and we need to be very careful about not just the quality but the overall design also. Footwear trends have been very fast. Our key challenge has been tracking the consumer trends. Though, as a contract manufacturer designs are supplied by the buyer; we also have our line of brands that necessitates us to track the consumer trends. Footwear is highly fragmented market. Each individual has different choices and preferences; it is very difficult to create personalized products.

3. How have you been benefited by the existence of the cluster? What are the different schemes of the government and / or association you have availed and been benefited by?

Our business is dependent on our presence in this cluster. We have been benefited by the common services and access to low-cost labours. By nature, this is labour-intensive industry and the cluster makes this possible. It is a complete package. We have the entire infrastructure around the business services, professional agencies and export houses. The best part is the access to the suppliers and other manufactures that ensures ability to fulfil big orders. Dealing with big players is possible only due to the presence of the other units in the cluster. It is collaborative yet competitive. Access to finance and credit by being a part of the cluster has been very helpful. I have also attended knowledge enhancement programs offered by the government. They have been helpful. We also interact with the footwear design institute. This helps to gain new insights and also to hire the talent in the future.

4. How have you seen your firm shaping up based on the cluster? How your business strategies have been influenced by the cluster impact?

Our evolution from a mere tannery to exclusive footwear manufacturer is shaped up largely due to the cluster and the presence of other players in this cluster. We have become highly lean and agile due to the capabilities of other units in the clusters. I must say that our lead time to supply has drastically reduced due to the capable units and their ability to supply. At times we have subcontracted our production and this has been very helpful to complete big orders.

5. What are the different ways you see that the cluster could help you to improve your business competitiveness?

I think design and knowledge sharing is essential. We can also create a common technology platform more like a marketplace to help each other. That will be very helpful. Thought, support services are good but they need upgradation to meet the dynamic nature of the global markets. Logistics solutions that are affordable will also improve our business competitiveness.

